

D4.29 5th Periodic Report on JIPs

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

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Contents

1.	Introduction	5
2.	Summary of the performance of the Joint Integrative Projects	7
2.1	Deliverables and milestones.....	7
2.2	Publications	8
2.2.1	Peer-reviewed scientific papers.....	8
2.2.2	Other published outcomes except meeting reports.....	9
2.2.3	Other outcomes	10
3.	International and national interactions.....	12
3.1	Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs, European, international and national projects	12
3.2	Interactions initiated by JIPs with national focus	13
3.3	Cogwheel Workshops.....	13
3.4	Thematic Integrative Meetings	14
4.	Data Management Plan.....	14
5.	Ethical Assessment	14
6.	JIP03-R2-IA2.3-CARE	15
6.1	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	15
6.2	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes	16
6.3	Project self-assessment	23
6.4	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables.....	24
6.5	Publications and additional outputs	29
6.6	Additional output.....	30
6.7	Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.	30
6.8	Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?	31
6.9	One Health impact.....	31
6.10	Data Management Plan.....	32
6.11	Future dissemination activities	32
7.	JIP04-R2-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	33
7.1	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	33
7.2	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes	35
7.3	Project self-assessment	47
7.4	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables.....	49
7.5	Publications and additional outputs	55
7.6	Additional output.....	57

7.7	Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.	57
7.8	Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?	57
7.9	One Health impact	57
7.10	Data Management Plan	58
7.11	Future dissemination activities	58
8.	JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX	59
8.1	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	59
8.2	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes	60
8.3	Project self-assessment	76
8.4	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	79
8.5	Publications and additional outputs	85
8.6	Additional output	88
8.7	Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.	88
8.8	Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?	89
8.9	One Health impact	89
8.10	Data Management Plan	91
8.11	Future dissemination activities	91
9.	JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparedness-COVRIN.....	93
9.1	Summary of the work carried out.....	93
9.2	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes	93
9.3	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	103
9.4	Publications and additional outputs.....	111
9.5	Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries	114
9.6	List of critical risks.....	114

5TH PERIODIC REPORT ON JIPS

1. Introduction

The joint core mission of partners in the One Health EJP is to provide expertise and services to prevent, detect and respond to societal challenges such as foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats shared by people and animals. The chain of actions from prevention via detection to response defines a series of capacities that need to be maintained and kept up to date by these expert institutes. These pertain to their capacity to design and implement surveillance activities, develop high-quality laboratory methods, access relevant reference materials and data, as well as to their ability to interpret and communicate surveillance information in a timely and appropriate manner, as well as to provide guidance to risk managers about relevant actions, both for prevention and response. Similarly, the purpose of integrative activities and projects within the OHEJP is to strengthen the joint preparedness of partners to prevent, detect and respond to hazards within their joint remit, both nationally and in collaboration with other EU institutes and agencies. Due to the legislated landscape in which OHEJP partners operate, and as a result of the close relationship and collaboration with the key EU stakeholders of OHEJP, ECDC and EFSA, there are already many strategies, initiatives, activities and systems in place to develop the capacity to respond to joint hazards within the field of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

The objective of Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) is not to replicate, but to strengthen existing, well-functioning systems. The guidance and insight of EFSA and ECDC are of major importance to help such alignment. The objective of JIPs is also to bridge the gap between the sectors by successively focusing on the inter-sectorial mechanisms along the chain from preparedness to response and to investigate and improve how the work processes of microbiologists, epidemiologists, and information specialists, function across the Public Health/Animal Health/Food Safety interface at the national level. Strengthening of inter-sectorial mechanisms at the national level will subsequently benefit the supra-national level.

Consequently, the ambition of the integrative activities of the One Health EJP is to develop structures, work processes and platforms that bridge inter-sectorial division within the domains defined by the OHEJP scope, resulting in one European surveillance community. This integrative development should be aligned with European priorities, accommodate, and be adapted to existing EU initiatives and support long-term sustainability in the improved joint capacity. Operational integration is promoted by means of several different instruments, the primary instrument being the implementation of JIPs. Prioritized needs regarding joint collaborative resources were identified in the strategic research agenda (SRA), developed in the context of the EJP proposal. An integrative strategy matrix was developed where the domains Foodborne zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats became the three pillars of the OHEJP. Further, the components that contribute to the improvement of the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” were identified. The prioritized components are reflected in the Joint Integrative Projects, which correspond to each of these components. The OHEJP exercise SimEx corresponds to the final step of the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” i.e. the Action step, which was trained in this exercise.

The JIPs were selected in the two internal calls of the OHEJP. The first two JIPs, ORION and COHESIVE, started in 2018. ORION focused on the semantic and technical interoperability between the sectors, with focus on surveillance information. COHESIVE focused on the ability to pick up, share and communicate signals as well as the ability to conduct joint risk assessments. Both these projects finished in 2021 and were evaluated during Y5. The final reports and the evaluation can be found in D4.24 Final report of 1st call JIPs and evaluation reports at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7732002#.ZBMIZXbMJ3g>

In 2020, three new JIPs started. MATRIX had the aim to extend the efforts of COHESIVE and ORION and to advance the implementation of One Health surveillance in practice, by building on existing resources, adding value to them, and creating synergies among the sectors. OH-Harmony-CAP aimed to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory and the primary diagnostic level. CARE focused on developing new One Health concepts for proficiency testing of laboratories, reference materials and quality/availability of demographic data. These projects were all extended to three-year projects and ended in December Y5. The two-year JIP COVRIN, which started in March Y4, is a response to the SARS-CoV2 pandemic and aims to integrate coronavirus research activities of all project partners. The project will identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2 and generate data to build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2.

During Y5 all second call JIPs had their final meetings. The JIPs CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP and MATRIX had a joint final meeting in September on site in Copenhagen, followed by specific project meetings. COVRIN had their final meeting on 5-6 December in Teramo, Italy. The COVRIN meeting was a hybrid event. The WP4 support team got the opportunity to take part in all of the JIP final meetings.

The topic “Sharing best intervention practice – twinning and simulation exercises” relating to the sixth component “Action” in the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” did not attract any applications in the second call. To partly cover up for this an OHEJP exercise, called SimEx, was set up. The exercise was an outbreak response exercise designed and conducted under task 4.6 of WP4. The aim was to develop the One Health capability, capacity, and interoperability of authorities in Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety and provide an opportunity to practice together. The OHEJP SimEx was performed in Y5 as a complex tabletop exercise with practical tasks on a national level. Eleven European countries and 20 OHEJP partner institutes participated in the exercise. The final project report will be delivered in

M63; D4.30 Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx) – planning and conduction. External evaluation of the project set-up and realization will be performed in Y6.

Since the joint EU capacity is a function of each member state’s capacity, the JIPs are expected to make their developments accessible to all partners and ensure there is transfer of skills and knowledge and promote harmonized approaches wherever it is relevant. In this way, the JIPs will serve to strengthen the scientific capacity within the OHEJP, as well as the future prevention, preparedness, detection and response of the EU to foodborne and other emerging threats across human-animal-environmental sectors. To do this the projects have been encouraged to disseminate results and outcomes in various ways. Among the initiatives within the JIPs are for instance several national pilots to harmonize the work between public health, animal health and food safety sectors. There has also been a supra-national pilot, where new tools are implemented at ECDC and EFSA. Other tools developed by the JIPs have been integrated into already existing tools like the FoodChain Lab. The FoodChain Lab was also demonstrated and used during the OHEJP exercise SimEx. The JIPs and SimEx have been presented both at the two SSB meetings in Y5 and the POC/PMC meeting in November Y5. In addition, the JIP MATRIX organized and delivered a dissemination series during Y5 with in total seven webinars, the Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinar, to present the project’s outcomes. In December the final SimEx project dissemination workshop was held as a digital meeting in collaboration with WP5 as a part of their Dissemination Workshop Series. A report written from this workshop is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7660178#.ZAuALHbMI2x>.

The body of this report is based on the 12-month report for Y5 provided by COVRIN and the final reports provided by CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, MATRIX and SimEx. The results and evaluation of the three JIPs finished in Y5 will be found in D4.28 Final reports of 2nd call JIPs and evaluation reports, due in M65. The results and evaluation of SimEx will be presented in D4.31 Final reports of JIP COVRIN and OHEJP exercise (SimEx) and evaluation reports, due in M66.

2. Summary of the performance of the Joint Integrative Projects

2.1 Deliverables and milestones

The finishing JIPs delivered all of the planned deliverables and milestones. COVRIN delivered 14 out of 24 deliverables and the two planned milestones; the remaining deliverables will be delivered before the project finishes in M63.

JIP	No. of deliverables Y5	No. of finalized deliverables Y5	% of finalized deliverables Y5	No. of delayed deliverables Y5	% of delayed deliverables Y5
CARE	18	18	100	0	0
OH-HARMONY-CAP	8	8	100	0	0
MATRIX	14	14	100	0	0
COVRIN	24	14	58	10	42

JIP	No. of milestones Y5	No. of finalized milestones Y5	% of finalized milestones Y5	No. of delayed milestones Y5	% of delayed milestones Y5
CARE	7	7	100	0	0
OH-HARMONY-CAP	3	3	100	0	0
MATRIX	2	2	100	0	0
COVRIN	2	2	100	0	0

Actions resulting from the follow-up of milestones and deliverables:

- Close communication with COVRIN will continue until the end of the project.
- The WP4 team checks the delivery of each project deliverable and that it is uploaded correctly.
- WP4 takes care of the dissemination of deliverables to stakeholders as indicated by the PLs.

2.2 Publications

As the Joint Integrative Projects are more development-oriented and a natural part of the alignment process, scientific publications are not an expected major outcome of the projects. Accessibility to newly developed or refined web tool applications is equally important.

Publications in scientific peer-reviewed journals in 2022 as well as other published outcomes are listed below.

2.2.1 Peer-reviewed scientific papers

CARE

Guillier L, Palma F, Fritsch L. Taking account of genomics in quantitative microbial risk assessment: what methods? what issues? *Current Opinion in Food Science* 100922; 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2022.100922>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7728014#.ZBMKSXbMJ3g>

OH-HARMONY-CAP

Characterisation of atypical Shiga toxin gene sequences and description of Stx2j, a new subtype. *J Clin Microbiol* 2022 Mar 16;60(3):e0222921.

[https://doi: 10.1128/jcm.02229-21](https://doi:10.1128/jcm.02229-21)

<https://zenodo.org/record/6637837#.YxHBT>

MATRIX

Swanson D, Koren C, Hopp P, Jonsson ME, Rø GI, White RA, Grøneng GM (2022). A One Health real-time surveillance system for nowcasting *Campylobacter* gastrointestinal illness outbreaks, Norway, week 30 2010 to week 11 2022. *Euro Surveill.*2022;27(43):pii=2101121. Available at:

<https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.43.2101121>

Doi reference: <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.43.2101121>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7547289#.ZBMLT3bMJ3g>

Rodríguez A, Iglesias I, de la Torre A (2022). Prioritisation tool for targeting the monitoring of veterinary pharmaceuticals at national level: the case of Spain. *European Journal Soil Science*, 73(4):e13268. Doi reference: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13268>
<https://zenodo.org/record/7546837#.ZBMLI3bMJ3g>

COVRIN

Moreno, A., Lelli, D., Trogu, T., Lavazza, A., Barbieri, I., Boniotti, M., Pezzoni, G., Salogni, C., Giovannini, S., Alborali, G., Bellini, S., Boldini, M., Farioli, M., Ruocco, L., Bessi, O., Maroni Ponti, A., Di Bartolo, I., De Sabato, L., Vaccari, G., Belli, G., Margutti, A., Giorgi, M. SARS-CoV-2 in a Mink Farm in Italy: Case Description, Molecular and Serological Diagnosis by Comparing Different Tests. *Viruses*. 2022 Aug 8;14(8):1738. doi: 10.3390/v14081738. <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4915/14/8/1738>

2.2.2 Other published outcomes except meeting reports

CARE

- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, Jun 9-11 2021 Copenhagen, Denmark and online. De Oliveira Mota J, Aarts H, Guillier L, Desvignes V, editors. Identification of data currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment.
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, 2022 Orvieto, Italy Elina Lahti, Linnéa Blom, Hilde Riedel, Nadja Karamemedovic, Anna Heydecke, Aurora Garcia Fernandez, Claudia Lucarelli, Elisabetta Delibato, Ingegerd Sjögren, Isaac Ring, Jeppe Boel, Karl Lundin, Kees Veldman, Lucas Wijnands, Maria Ugarte Ruiz, Martine Denis, Mia Torpdahl, Renata Kwit, Rene Hendriksen, Cecilia Jernberg "A cross-sectional pilot proficiency test/external quality assessment on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens."
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, 2022 Orvieto, Italy, Jeppe Boel, Sally Hallam, Małgorzata L. Marzeta, Paula Johnson, Mia Torpdahl. «Cross-sectorial one health proficiency test for cluster detection of *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* based on whole genome sequencing»
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13 2022, Orvieto, Italy, Forum Shah, Maria-Beatrice Boniotti, Anne Brisabois, Olivier Chesneau, Dominique Clermont, Emmanuelle Helloin, Rene Hendriksen, Valeria Michelacci, Michel-Yves Mistou and the OH-EJP CARE consortium. The CARE collection, an open panel of microbiological reference materials dedicated to zoonotic and foodborne bacterial pathogens.

MATRIX

- One article focusing on MATRIX and the activities of MATRIX WP2 has been prepared for the next issue of the Italian national bulletin for epidemiology, [BENV - Bollettino Epidemiologico Nazionale Veterinario](#). It will be published in both Italian and English, under the title of "MATRIX: integrated and multisectoral surveillance in a One Health perspective".

COVRIN

- Mendez, M.A. Jiménez-Clavero, C. Calvo, E. Pérez-Ramírez, J. Fernández-Pinero, F. Llorente, T. Sainz, P. Aguilera-Sepúlveda, S. Alcolea, L. Escolano, C. Cano, I. Novoa, A. De la Torre I. Iglesias. (2022) SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain, Abstract, *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, Volume 116: S25. ISSN 1201-9712 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059>

2.2.3 Other outcomes

CARE

- Oral presentation at Agrostat eConference 2021. De Oliveira Mota J, Redondo HG, Bergis H, Poisson S, Dubuisson C, Sanaa M, et al., editors. The Third French Individual and National Food Consumption (INCA3) Survey 2014–2015 and data for microbiological risk assessment: Models for domestic refrigerator temperatures 16th Agro-Industry and Statistical Methods congress; 2021 September 14-15; Online conference.
- Oral presentation at OHEJP JIPs CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP closing meeting, September 20, 2022, Copenhagen Denmark. J. Boel (WP1), MY Mistou (WP2/3), L Guillier (WP4).
- Oral presentation at Campylobacter EURL Annual meeting, September 27, 2022, Sigtuna, Sweden. MY Mistou. <https://www.sva.se/en/about-us/eurl-campylobacter/workshops/workshop-2022/>
- Oral presentation of the OHEJP CARE project, especially pilot PT1 of WP1 at the EURL Campylobacter workshop, Sigtuna, September 27-28, 2022 (Elina Lahti) <https://www.sva.se/en/about-us/eurl-campylobacter/workshops/workshop-2022/>
- Presentation of the OHEJP CARE project with a focus on the inventory of reference materials and database at the Anses internal reference meeting, Maisons-Alfort, France, 19th of May 2022 (A. Brisabois).
- A large collection of well-characterised reference strains of food-borne pathogens (>2500 strains) will be available for scientists and laboratories to use in Dec. 2022.
- The three distributions of well characterized WGS data from clustering and non-clustering *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella* isolates can be used to evaluate cluster detection pipelines in the future.
- Guidance on cross-sectorial proficiency tests/external quality assurance
- Guide for accessing relevant data and models for quantitative microbial risk assessment: <https://guillier.quarto.pub/care-guide-for-data/>

OH-HARMONY-CAP

- The development of the first OHLabCap tool is in itself a major achievement, which is open for adaptation by other key stakeholders in the OH field such as FAO and WHO, who are conducting similar surveys. The inclusion of private food operators and laboratories in the mini survey of this project is – to our knowledge - the first of its kind and could potentially represent an improvement in the communication between the private sector and One Health authorities. Both parties could benefit from the results. The involvement of these stakeholders could in return serve as inspiration for the further development of tools intended to measure the dimensions and targets in the OHLabCap tool (D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.4, M54).
- The e-learning sessions represents an important outcome, being available also for a large public far beyond the project's participants. These video documents will be published, among others, on the OH-HARMONY-CAP website to ensure the maximum dissemination of the contents and impacting in the transfer of knowledge to a larger scientific community.

- Podcast with Flemming Scheutz on the Danish broadcasting company on types of *E. coli*.
- The Annual general peoples meeting on the Island of Bornholm with approximately 120,000 guests, decision-makers and politicians. Two workshops on the detection of foodborne outbreaks.

MATRIX

- Relevant outputs from MATRIX WP2-T1 have been included in the Ph.D. project by an expert from partner 28-IZSAM, member of the MATRIX Consortium and specifically working on MATRIX WP2, as a case study on the application of the One Health approach. The project focused on case studies about the application of One Health in different contexts i.e. vector-borne and food-borne diseases. The project belongs to the Ph.D. course in “Infectious Diseases, Microbiology and Public Health” at the Sapienza University of Rome, Italy.
- One scientific abstract (by partner University of Copenhagen, UCPH) related to *Salmonella* Dublin STOC free Model (described under the work of MATRIX WP3) was accepted as an oral presentation for the [SVEPM conference](#) in Toulouse, France in 2023. Conference proceedings are submitted in December 2022.
- OH-EpiCap Tool – an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS of a hazard of choice, identifying strengths and opportunities for improvement. Additionally, the tool allows the benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities for comparison. More information is available here: [OH-EpiCap tool flyer](#) and [OH-EpiCap tool user guide](#).
- Roadmap to develop national OHS – a guideline that countries can use to develop OHS according to their needs and resources. The roadmap expanded the work of the OHEJP COHESIVE project and is available at <https://www.ohras.eu/page/home> – copy-paste this link in your browser.
- Manual for OHS Dashboards – an online dashboard inventory and practical manual to facilitate the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open-source tools. More information is available here: [Dashboard Information Centre](#).
- Guidelines and checklists:
 - An interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems. A beta version is available [here](#).
 - Best-practices to operationalize cross-sectoral collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results – available [here](#).
 - A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards – available [here](#).

MATRIX also promoted and expanded:

- [The OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform](#) – a framework to integrate various resources that help to implement OHS in all sectors.
- [Food Safety Knowledge Exchange \(FSKX\) Format](#) – a format that supports the One Health community in sharing and re-using mathematical models as well as data analysis procedures.

COVRIN

- Med-Vet-Net Association Workshop – SARS-CoV-2 at the Animal-Human Interface. Recording of the event is available here: <https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/health-and-life-sciences/research/uk-international-coronavirus-network/launch-meeting/>

3. International and national interactions

The aim of the JIPs themselves is to generate integrative activities. Some relevant activities are summarized in sections 3.1 and 3.2. In addition, OHEJP WP4 has arranged in total eight cogwheel workshops to facilitate interactions between JRPs/JIPs and other European projects and initiatives. Another initiative to facilitate interactions between the OHEJP projects is the Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs). Some examples of interactions initiated by JIPs are provided here. Additional and more detailed information can be found in the project reports.

3.1 Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs, European, international and national projects

Many of the outputs from the JIPs have been developed in collaboration with EURLs and provide opportunities for future harmonization between sectors. In JIP CARE available and existing External Quality Assurance (EQA) programs offered to the National Reference Laboratories have been identified. The aim was to develop proficiency testing schemes for the analysis of whole genome sequence data to detect clusters as might be required during an outbreak response. From this information a guidance was set up for new EQA scheme expanding to whole genome sequencing (WGS).

The EUROpanelOH, is a reference database of strains (>2500 strains) and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors, which is now available. A particular effort has been made to ensure that the CARE collection represents the different AMR phenotypes circulating within the food pathogen strains. There is a specific guide for accessing relevant data and models for quantitative microbial risk assessment.

JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP has developed protocols to be used in EQA programmes. Harmonised procedures for the detection and typing of Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), and Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) have been developed and four new subtypes of Shigatoxin genes are described. In collaboration with Center for Vaccine Development, USA and Uniformed Services University of the Health sciences, MD, USA, omni primers for the detection of Stx1, Stx2, and *eae* genes have been tested and implemented. Harmonized procedures to distinguish between Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC) and *Shigella spp.* have been proposed as well as a decision tree for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium*. The harmonized application of the most appropriate methods for sampling and testing food, feed, environmental and human samples, standard characterization priorities and methods complemented by effective data management and reporting systems would ensure reliable data is readily available to EFSA, FAO, etc. to support food safety guidance and policy in the EU and worldwide.

In the development of a “National OH surveillance roadmap” JIP MATRIX identified synergies with the JIP COHESIVE on the topic of OHS roadmaps. MATRIX evaluated and further developed the roadmap presented by JIP COHESIVE. The requirement analysis for the “National OH surveillance roadmaps” was done in collaboration with JIP COHESIVE, JIP ORION and JRP NOVA. MATRIX also collaborated with the JRP BeONE in the evaluation and implementation of national level data sharing.

Another OHEJP output, which was further developed by MATRIX is the “OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform”. This is today included in the toolbox of the Surveillance and information sharing operational tool (SIS OT): an operational tool of the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide by WHO, FAO and WOA. H.

The three JIPs CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP and MATRIX have worked close together. In November 2022 they hosted the third One Health CPD–module with the theme, rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests.

JIP COVRIN cooperates with many nationally funded projects in partner countries, and also with

international organisations like WHO, FAO, ECDC and EFSA. Links have been established with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project. COVRIN research outputs are reported nationally and internationally. All significant results have been reported to the national Ministries and also to ECDC and EFSA as appropriate. COVRIN has also linked closely with the UK International Coronavirus Network.

3.2 Interactions initiated by JIPs with national focus

The results of CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP have the potential to improve One Health interoperability across NRLs on three target areas: Sampling & testing, strain characterization, and data management & harmonised reporting. By identifying gaps, the projects support best practices to detect and characterize foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. Surveillance strategies can then be adjusted based on the developed guidance for improvement of One Health interoperability across NRLs.

MATRIX created solutions for European countries to support and advance the implementation of OHS, also known as the “MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance”:

- OH-EpiCap Tool – an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS of a hazard of choice, identifying strengths and opportunities for improvement
- Roadmap to develop national OHS – a guideline that countries can use to develop OHS according to their needs and resources.
- Manual for OHS Dashboards – an online dashboard inventory and practical manual to facilitate the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open-source tools
- Guidelines and checklists:
 - An interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems.
 - Best-practices to operationalize cross-sectoral collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results.
 - A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards.

The OHEJP exercise SimEx was not a JIP, but a task under WP4, performed by a designated SimEx project with an assigned Project and Exercise Leader. A Steering Board provided the Project Directive and an Advisory Board shared experiences and gave advice to the project. The exercise was performed on a national level and in most countries the public health, animal health and food safety sectors were all involved. In addition to OHEJP partners, additional national institutes with responsibilities in an outbreak situation based on a zoonotic foodborne pathogen were involved. During the exercise the participants were encouraged to use some tools developed within the JIP COHESIVE. Each country performed their own evaluation and part of the evaluations were shared with the SimEx Project team. The general conclusions and recommendations are summarized in D4.30 Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx) – planning and conduction.

3.3 Cogwheel Workshops

The Cogwheel workshops conducted within the OHEJP during Y1-4 were during Y5 presented in a report that summarizes experiences and outcomes from the eight workshops. The aim of the Cogwheel workshops was to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRPs) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), to identify synergies, joint priorities, and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. These workshops have resulted in interactions between and collaborations with JRPs and JIPs as well as with other EU projects and initiatives. The report is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/6838854#.Y-l8VXbMI2w>.

3.4 Thematic Integrative Meetings

In total four Thematic integrative meetings (TIMs) have been arranged by WP4. The TIMs aim to facilitate integration across domains, but within themes, addressing specific thematic integrative needs and opportunities.

The fourth and last Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM) was organised in Y5. The meeting was held as an online workshop in Teams on February 22 with the title “Data Sharing Across Disciplines”. The aim was to elucidate on the legal aspects of data sharing as well as give examples on solutions to cross-sectoral data sharing. The TIM was attended by approximately 120 persons across sectors and from altogether 16 countries. The target groups were the Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects, stakeholders and the EURLs. During the meeting three presentations were given on legal aspects and requirements of data sharing and on examples of solutions how cross-sectoral data sharing can be done in outbreak investigations, research projects and risk assessments. Building trust and know your data was one of the key messages. For more information see D4.26. Report on thematic meeting IV (<https://zenodo.org/record/6802112#.ZAuFUbnMI2w>).

4. Data Management Plan

All projects have appointed DMP Leaders that manage the project specific Data Management Plans (DMPs). For the first call projects three different templates were used. The second call projects and COVRIN use the online software tool CDP (Lisam®). All second call DMP Leaders have got training in the CDP tool. In collaboration with WP5 a link from the CDP-tool to the Outcome Inventory has been set up and the public content of the DMPs can be reached by the stakeholders via a Reader’s view. In this way data can be accessed before the projects are finished. Finalized DMPs have been reviewed by the DMP Committee and suggestions for improvements communicated to the DMP and Project Leaders. The DMPs of JRP/JIPs have annually been reviewed by the DMP Committee.

The overarching OHEJP DMP is also under revision, all OHEJP WPs and Comms Team are asked to provide data and other relevant outcomes that are not listed elsewhere. The work to put this into the CDP-tool is managed by WP4. The original OHEJP DMP, found in D4.4 Data Management Plan, has been completed with a D4.4 annex (still to be uploaded). Finalized DMPs are uploaded to the DMP Group on the OHEJP website and when approved to Zenodo. All DMPs from the first call projects can be found on Zenodo. For the second call projects, 14 DMPs are uploaded on Zenodo and an additional 3 DMPs are expected to be uploaded in the first months of 2023. The DMPs for the Ph.D. projects are managed by the respective university according to their internal routines.

5. Ethical Assessment

Satisfactory answers have been given to all ethical considerations and there are no additional comments to respond to.

6. JIP03-R2-IA2.3-CARE

6.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Proficiency testing (PT), or external quality assurance (EQA) schemes, is an integrated part of quality assurance management for laboratories within the field of human, food, and animal microbiology. Reference materials (RM) for microbiological analyses on zoonotic pathogens are available in the context of reference laboratories (e.g. EURL's) but no mechanisms are in place at EU level combining the reference collections linked to specific reference functions and sectors. Similarly, the culture collections and microbial Biological Resources Centers (mBRCs) and associated data is highly fragmented among the Member States. At EU or national level, risk assessment and management are highly dependent on the availability and quality of data on animal populations, food and feed consumption. The quality and availability of the demographic data including those for food consumption for risk assessment differs between countries.

Thus, the CARE project will focus on developing new One Health concepts for PT of laboratories, reference materials and quality/availability of demographic data. The CARE project aims to develop new proficiency testing schemes that can be used cross-sectorally and thereby used to evaluate the capacity to manage foodborne problems from a One Health perspective. Further, provide insight to available and desirable RM, identifying sources of both strains and genomic data, including the field of antimicrobial resistance, provided by reference laboratories and other relevant sources such as online repositories and national collections. There will be a focus on the visibility of the reference material and data associated for the scientific community. The emphasis will be on the availability and sustainability of this reference collection in order to contribute to the long-term needs of the European research. CARE will also aim to disseminate more widely the information about the accessibility not only of the reference collection but also of CARE partner microbial collections. Lastly, CARE will further assess the quality and availability of the demographic data and focus on how to improve and make the data better by raising awareness of EU authorities collecting and organising demographic data.

In CARE, three new partners, ISCIII in Spain, BIOR in Latvia, and RUOKA in Finland joined the CARE consortium in 2021 and have been active and included in the CARE activities contributing to this report.

The work in WP1 focused on the three PT/EQA trials conducted and provided individual feedback to all participants. The final EQA reports of W1-T2-ST1, W1-T2-ST2, and W1-T2-ST3 have been finalised and W1-T2-ST1 submitted a scientific journal.

A template for planning, execution, and evaluation of cross sectoral PTs was developed by WP1. The template covers all aspects to comply with ISO/IEC 17043 conformity assessment – general requirements for PT providers. The template contains guidance on the general considerations that should be taken before PT is executed. The template was evaluated using pilots from current project as examples.

The work in WP2/ WP3 focused on the extended analysis of the identified genomes for AMR, virulence and other typing regimes. A Web catalog dashboard was developed to ensure visibility and accessibility of the reference materials. Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization-time of flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectrometry (MS) reference spectra were produced for *Campylobacter*, *Yersinia* and *Salmonella* strains in order to set up and share reference libraries. A sustainable development plan for the CARE collection was developed to ensure accessibility of reference material after the closure of CARE.

A risk assessment survey on relevant (meta-)data in relation to quantitative microbial risk assessments was conducted by WP4 shared with WP2 and WP3 and stakeholders to assist by increasing the accessibility of data but also to avoid duplication. Thus, feeding into the quantitative microbial risk assessment analysis on data originating from the last five years and provided by 19 OHEJP members or stakeholders including those from ORION and RADAR. In addition, a user guide for accessing relevant data for risk assessment was developed as a R software tool “rStainSelect” to ease the process

of selecting suitable reference strains based on exposure and risks. Thus, the User guide and R software contribute to and support the developed strategy by EU authorities to raise the awareness of relevant reference material microbial risk assessment analysis.

In summary, the CARE project reached its milestones and deliverables in time and addresses additional assignments from the OHEJP WP4 in a timely manner.

6.2 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP0 Coordination

WP0-T1 Over-all project coordination

DTU and SSI constituted the management team and follow the established comprehensive management system to ensure that all deliverables and milestones for the vast majority was reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project and submitted using the designated OHEJP format. DTU hosted the secretariat, which warranted the successful completion of the proposed work programme. Furthermore, the DTU CARE share-site for storage of all reports, deliverables, milestones, minutes and other documentation was functioning.

CARE status meetings for the management team (DTU and SSI) have been conducted every second week. Furthermore, DTU and SSI organized and conducted work package (WP) lead virtual meetings every 14 days to inform, discuss and delegate news and tasks from the OHEJP management. In addition, WP-leads reported on the work undertaken in each WP as progress, deliverables, delays etc. Minutes of all meetings have been reported and shared on the CARE share site. The implemented review system to ensure high quality work was functional till the closure of the project.

The management team has organized and conducted joint partner virtual meetings every quarter, primarily to allow the 16 partners to provide feedback on progress and accomplishments. The meetings also allowed for the dissemination of information not shared already by email. Minutes of these meetings were shared and saved on the share site.

The three projects CARE, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP participated in each other's meetings sharing knowledge and progress on the projects. In addition, the three projects hosted the third One Health CPD-module with the theme, Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests in 2nd - 4th November of 2022 at DTU and SSI. Twenty-four onsite participants, including both microbiologists and epidemiologists, and 100 online participants participated in the module.

DTU and SSI prepared the final meeting held at SSI in 20-22 September 2022, including a joint day prepared in collaboration with JIPs, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP. External stakeholders were invited for the joint meeting and each JIP presented key elements and outputs from their respective projects. The meeting included a panel discussion where EFSA and OHEJP WP4 were present to discuss how to make best use of the project deliverables. An online very final meeting was conducted as a virtual meeting on 2 December 2022 to inform all partners and invited stakeholders about the outcome of CARE and the future perspectives including how to sustain the resources created.

WP1 Development of cross-sectional PT's (proficiency testing)

WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome

The overall aim of WP1 was to develop EQA/ PT schemes that can be used to assess the combined performance of the OH sector, i.e., the human, food/feed, and veterinary sectors. The WP was divided into three tasks, a **mapping** exercise, which finalized (WP1-T1 Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes), a part where three pilot PTs were organized and documented (WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome), and a third part, WP1-T3 Development of guidance document with suggestions for design of future cross-sectorial PT schemes.

The work conducted focused on development of the guidance document as well as planning, execution and reporting of the three PTs:

- WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens
- WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS
- WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

WP2-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

The aim of this pilot PT was to increase the understanding of the cross-sectorial capabilities to detect and characterize food-borne pathogens in a matrix relevant to the sectors of food safety, animal health, and public health. A total of 15 laboratories (12 OHEJP partners and 3 clinical microbiological laboratories from one country) participated in the PT/EQA organized by SVA, FOHM and SLV in 2021. The participants of the PT/EQA were to detect and characterize the target pathogens to species level (*Campylobacter*), to serovar level (*Salmonella*) and to species and biotype level (*Yersinia*) according to the methods routinely used by each laboratory. A short web-based questionnaire was included in the PT/EQA.

All 15 laboratories analysed for *Salmonella*, 13 for *Campylobacter* and 11 for *Yersinia*. Analytical errors were predominately false negative results. One sample (*S. Stockholm* and *Y. enterocolitica* O:3/BT4) with lower levels of target organisms was especially challenging, resulting in six out of seven false negative results. These findings were associated with laboratories using smaller sample sizes and not using enrichment methods.

Detection of *Salmonella* was most commonly mandatory to notify within the three sectors in the eight countries participating in the pilot whereas findings of *Campylobacter* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* were notifiable from samples from humans, but less common from animal and food samples.

The pilot showed that cross-sectoral panels, in addition to sector-specific ones, could be used for assessment of the One Health capacity to detect and characterise food-borne pathogens. These panels could therefore be a valuable tool to help improve food safety and interpretation of cross-sectoral surveillance data.

A report (D.1.2.1 EJP CARE Pilot isolation-detection of pathogens) of the PT/EQA was finalized in month 53 and uploaded to Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/6575861#.YoyVBKhBxaQ>. A scientific publication of the PT/EQA is in progress and anticipated to be submitted to the special issue of Journal Frontiers in Public Health (see above).

WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS

The second PT in WP1 aimed at assessing the quality and comparability of WGS based on a set of WGS quality metrics and looked into the laboratories ability to detect and assign subtypes/attributes from WGS data from bacterial isolates e.g., sero- and sequence types, antimicrobial resistance genes etc. The aim was to assess both the individual and the collective performance of the participating partner laboratories.

In Y4, the reference material used in the PT, i.e., pure strains and FASTQ sequence files from *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli* was provided and documented. An invitation to participate in the PT was sent to the CARE partner laboratories in September 2021, and instructions and material for the PT was dispatched from DTU, Lyngby, Denmark, in October 2021. The participants received six live strains, two strains of *E. coli*, two strains of *Salmonella*, and two strains of *Campylobacter*, and six pre-prepared DNA samples corresponding to the live cultures. The participants were requested to perform WGS on DNA purified from the live cultures and the pre-purified samples and upload the reads in FASTQ format via a file transfer service (ScienceData). The participants were also requested to upload specific details in relation to the test material and details in relation to their sequencing and analytical methods. It was mandatory to identify the overall Multi Locus Sequence Type

(MLST) lineage of the cultures and it was also mandatory to identify antimicrobial resistance genes, including genes associated with resistance towards extended spectrum beta-lactam antimicrobials, and point mutations that are conferring antimicrobial resistance. The deadline for submission was postponed from 21 December 2021 to 4 March 2022 due to a hacker attack at Corporate IT at DTU. This delayed the submission of the participant data and the downstream analysis. Luckily no data at DTU was compromised and the IT informatics system could be re-activated for submission and evaluation of the participants' obtained results. The submitted reads and corresponding results were evaluated and individual feedback was provided to each of the participants by 14 September 2022.

The participating laboratories (n=15) employed individual downstream pipelines, in terms of DNA preparation, sequencing and bioinformatics tools used, to provide information regarding isolate typing and the AMR profile. Generally, the participants produced good quality of DNA sequences, independently of the pipeline used. Moreover, the participants were very successful in identifying the MLST and serotype of the isolates employed in the present PT. Regarding the *in silico* prediction of AMR, many of the participants identified the expected AMR genes and mutations; however, the data suggest that there were more uncertainties related to the predicted AMR phenotype. Evaluation of the identified AMR determinants (genes, mutations) is a crucial step to accurately predict the AMR phenotype. During data analysis in the present PT, questions related to data evaluation arose, i.e., what is the lowest accepted percent identity and coverage of a specific AMR gene that is accepted, and the presence of cryptic AMR genes, among others. Evaluation of these data contributed to the creation of a standardised genotypic approach as an alternative to the standard phenotypic susceptibility testing methods previously employed.

For future cross-sectoral PTs within this area, important considerations for the setup include which results to request, i.e., to select strains based on the actual scope of the PT. As the scientific community is still introducing WGS and learning how to apply it in the routine work also in the field of AMR, it is necessary that upcoming PTs include components that allow for participants to be guided and challenged. This is for example relevant in relation to the list of antimicrobials included in the analysis. Based on the included list of antimicrobials, it is necessary to make a thorough bioinformatics analysis, including to carefully consider the selection criteria for the genes to include as expected. As PT organizer, it is necessary to confirm for each antimicrobial that genetic mechanisms are known and can be detected by tools available to the scientific community.

The present and future work contribute to the main objective of EJP CARE project, to create a pool of reference material which can be readily used by laboratories in future PTs.

An overall report (D.1.2.2 Report - Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS) presenting and analysing the laboratories' obtained results and sequences is now available for public access via Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7462445#.Y6L08HbMKUk>

WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

The aim of this pilot was to develop proficiency testing schemes for the analysis of whole genome sequence (WGS) data to detect clusters as might be required during an outbreak response.

The pilot PT was executed in the partner laboratories from December 15, 2021 until the end of February 2022. The PT included WGS data from three distributions of 35, 27 and 31 samples of *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*, respectively. The participants were recruited among the CARE partners and, additionally, the Singapore Food Agency participated invited by Anses. The participants could sign up for all or selected parts of the PT. In total, 20 institutions participated. The participants downloaded genome sequence data in FASTQ format from an FTP site for the analysis of the data using their current operational pipelines. The reporting contained general questions on the cluster analysis approach. The laboratories were asked to use their routine quality control (QC), and only include samples that passed QC for further analysis. For all samples, the sequence type (ST) should be reported, and it should be indicated whether the sample was a part of a closely related cluster. Both allele and/or SNP based cluster analysis were used. The PT results were uploaded to a reporting

platform hosted by APHA using a scheme developed for this project. The reported data included information on the applied type of bioinformatics tools and for each of the three distributions the laboratories indicated the number of SNP and or allele differences to selected predefined index strains defined. Individual feedback was provided to the participants on May 23, 2022. The feedback included a document where the submitted results were compared with the expected results from the PT provider.

The Pilot PT showed that most participants were able to correctly identify clusters of closely related sequences and that the reported results were in accordance with the expected results. The pilot PT further showed that the participants were able to correctly determine the quality of the WGS data provided and that most participants were able to identify the correct species, serovar and ST from the sequences.

The participants used either allele or SNP based methods and the results from the study showed that both methods were fit for the purpose. The submitted data also indicated that the approach for defining a cluster, i.e. number of allele or SNP differences varies between laboratories, so within this area there is a lack of harmonisation.

The final report of the PT (D.1.2.3 EJP CARE), Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data is available for public access via Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7462573#.Y6MMI3bMKUk>

WP1-T3 Guidance document for cross-sectoral proficiency testing

A SOP in the form of a template for planning, execution, and evaluation of cross sectoral PTs was developed. The SOP covers all aspects to comply with ISO/IEC 17043 conformity assessment – general requirements for PT providers. The template contains guidance on the general considerations that should be taken before PT is executed. The SOP can be used both when planning WGS based and detection based PTs. The SOP contains guidance on how to relate to objectives, purposes, and basic design of new PT schemes as well as details on samples, strain selection and data collection. The use of technical experts, sub-contractors, verification of PT sample, distribution, reporting, feedback and is also described. The template can act as a checklist for the PT provider. The SOP was evaluated using pilots from current project as examples. The SOP (D.1.3.2, EJP CARE) for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions and are available for public access via Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7467902#.Y6MFLXbMKUk>

The experiences from conducting the three pilot PTs showed that the chosen set up for each of the pilot PT has worked and provided useful information on how to design future one-health PTs. The Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens indicated that that cross-sectoral panels are useful for the assessment of the OH capacity to detect and characterize food-borne pathogens and that such panels are valuable for improving the food safety and the interpretation and comparison of surveillance data. The two WGS based pilots for typing and characterization and outbreak/cluster detection also indicated the usefulness of WGS based cross sectoral PT. But it was also shown that there is a need to develop and invest in improved automated informatics reporting portals. This could reduce the likelihood of human errors in the result uploading phase, reduce the workload both for the PT organizers and participants, and enable faster feedback to the participants from the PT provider. The PT on outbreak detection identified some inconsistency in the criteria used for calling outbreak clusters and is an area for future harmonization.

The final report (D.1.2.3 EJP CARE) of the guidance document (Guidance document for cross sectoral proficiency testing) is available for public access via Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7462573#.Y6MMI3bMKUk>

WP2 Creation of EUROpanelOH, a reference database of strains and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors.

The overall aim of WP2 is to propose and better characterize strains of seven bacterial pathogens to be integrated into a panel of Reference Materials (RM), currently called CARE collection, with the aim to build EUROpanelOH by growing and extending to other initiatives, such as ENOVAT for animal pathogens with which contacts have been made).

From the inventory of 2960 strains finalized in WP2-T1, a first gap analysis was conducted by expert groups during WP2-T2 to select a subset of resources among those proposed by 12 partners of the CARE consortium. This gap analysis identified the WGS data as a prerequisite for success. The first part of the gap analysis was done owing to the recommendations issued by the need assessment document (D.2.3). The second part of this phase (M2.2) was postponed at the end of September 2022 based on what had been programmed for the release of the final database (see WP3) but this document won't be finally provided because there remain a total of 273 strains to be validated by the BRCs at the end of November 2022. The final gap analysis has therefore been included in the sustainability plan as a prerequisite for future developments and continuous enrichment of the CARE collection.

One of the major purposes of CARE is to establish a trustable link between the phenotypes and the genotypes of the strains. Consensual methods and protocols have been applied to fill relevant gaps for the characterization of the strains by each provider or by the Biological Resource Centers (BRCs) that are hosting the RM of the CARE collection. Numerous meetings have been conducted. AMR protocols are available on the CARE web site <https://cirmbp.bio-aware.com/page/PROTOCOLS>.

WP2-T3 Production of additional RM to fill in gaps and/or improve characterization if needed

A total of 830 RMs have been included in WP2-T3 for data completion.

WP2-T3-ST1 WGS characterization

Sequencing of the strains for which WGS was not available began in 2021. WGS data, at least raw reads, have been uploaded to international sequence repositories under the following ENA study accession numbers: PRJEB46213, PRJEB49020, PRJEB49018, PRJEB49008, PRJEB49009, PRJEB48968, PRJEB48148, PRJEB48129, PRJEB47991, PRJEB49418, PRJEB49424, PRJNA799608. A total of 313 novel genome sequences (D.2.4) has been finally deposited by the providers from Dec 2021 to March 2022.

A dedicated folder gathering all the genomes of the seven pathogens has been created at Institute Pasteur for enabling easy file exchange among partners. Whenever necessary, the genomes have been *de novo* assembled at INRAE. The gene content for AMR has been analyzed by Staramr which scans genome contigs against ResFinder, PlasmidFinder and PointFinder. A first release of the AMR database has been delivered (D2.2: <https://zenodo.org/record/6644884#.YqmXVXZByUk>) based on scripts that connect the CARE collection with ResFinder. Other partner analytical services have been used: Kmer analysis for species identification, Multi Locus Sequence Typing for the seven pathogens, Seqsero for *Salmonella* serotyping, VirulenceFinder for *S. aureus* and an ISS pipeline dedicated to the analysis of the serotypes and the virulence of *E. coli*. The results of these WGS analyses have been compared with the characteristics of the strains reported in the original Excel files of the providers. The BRCs have checked the consistency of the reported data.

WP2-T3-ST2 MALDI-TOF characterization

MALDI-TOF Mass spectrometry is now commonly used for bacterial identification but needs representative databases for the correct identification of pathogens such as *Salmonella*, *Yersinia* and *Campylobacter* responsible for gastroenteritis worldwide. To enlarge the database of reference spectra already existing in the Bruker commercial database, and to pave the way for further studies, four partners (IP, ANSES, INRAE, VISAVET) have been working on producing reference spectra for

Salmonella and *Yersinia*. The work on *Campylobacter* has been postponed and will not be done on time due to the difficulties of transfer of the strains originating from Spain (delay and many restrictions coming from the Spanish ministries including Nagoya considerations).

WP2-T3-ST3 Completing metadata and phenotypic data

The updated lists of strains selected for the final database (see WP3) have been checked by the three BRCs (CIRM at INRAE, CIP at IP and BVR at IZSLER) that received the RM from the providers. Follow up actions were conducted with the partners in collaboration with WP3 for transferring the complete set of information in the customized Biolumics software.

WP3 Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

WP3-T1 Development of an information system for making RM more widely accessible and visible

The CARE website (<https://cirmbp.bio-aware.com/>) was implemented, it reports the content of the CARE collection, it enables running basic and advanced searches on the CARE catalog and allows the users to choose their strains of interest. An important functionality of the database is that Information on the AMR phenotypes and AMR gene predicted from WGS data are included and can be used as search parameters to query the CARE DB. The website also contains information to deposit or order strains. The CARE website is publicly accessible.

WP3-T2 Ensure the long-term sustainability of RM collections

The sustainability plan has been drafted and provided as D.3.3.1 (<https://zenodo.org/record/7467976#.Y6MJ33bMKUk>). Materials deposit agreements (MDA) are signed between RM providers and mBRCs when integrating strains into the CARE catalog. A training session attended by 12 CARE partners over two days in May 2022 was organised. Visits of two microbial BRCs (CIP and CIRM) were included. All documents are made available, including the general conditions of transfer and use of the strains of the CARE collection (<https://cirmbp.bio-aware.com/page/ORDER>).

WP3-T3 Ensuring the long-term accessibility of the RM collection and its existence

The deposit of strains in the three microbiological BRCs guarantees the long-term accessibility of the CARE RM collection. A total of 225 strains are currently available for diffusion. In addition, 273 strains have gone through the administrative and logistic processes and are under validation by BRCs. The target of the CARE collection has therefore been reached.

WP4 Investigate, benchmark and improve the availability and the quality of the existing data relevant for risk assessment

WP4-T1 Data and metadata available for risk assessment

Connections were established with other projects and stakeholders during the project period in the perspective to establish the roadmap for sharing information on pathogens and AMR useful for exposure/risk assessment.

CARE WP4's objective and findings for the practices of data sharing for risk assessment were presented to the JIP MATRIX and during the 4th OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting "Data sharing across disciplines". <https://zenodo.org/record/6802112#.YsVyfHZBw2w>

WP4-T2 Metadata web platform

The resources provided by DTU incorporating surveillance data related to antimicrobial resistance and infectious disease data into a web platform was redrawn from central DTU administration during 2021, thus, the task and deliverable were omitted and co-funding redrawn. The other partners of this task (ANSES and RIVM) initiated to draft a user guide describing how to access the data available (D.4.2.1). The user guide; html book, is available via the website <https://lguillier.quarto.pub/care-guide-for-data/> and will be maintained after the closure of CARE. It follows the classical steps of quantitative risk assessments. It considers the information gathered during the survey and related to other OHEJP projects (see D 4.1.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7455276>). In the same way, the two partners developed a guideline document to raise awareness by EU authorities of collecting relevant and high-quality data for risk-assessment (D.4.2.2 <https://zenodo.org/record/7455313#.Y5-BnXbMLIU>). This document was shared and presented to stakeholders and resented to the EFSA Microbial risk assessment network. In the context of improving relation between WGS and risk assessment, CARE partners has published some recommendation and proposed an R tool for selecting strain on risk based criteria.

WP4-T3 Dissemination plan

The 4th OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting “Data sharing across disciplines” was a first realization of the dissemination plan.

The European network of focal points and the EFSA MRA network was used to disseminate the results of this WP.

6.3 Project self-assessment

Originally, the project was described very ambitious but was affected by covid and other factors during the project period why the level of ambition was slightly modified to ensure the project delivered. Thus, the initial project objectives were met to a large degree with no obvious deviation.

The ambition was lowered especially in terms of the EQA scoping analysis which could have been more detailed and published. It was decided that it would not be in a state for a scientific publication. The intention for the 2nd EQA was to have more partners to conduct the analysis of the data in relation to their area of competence according to their reference centre status. Thus, only the EURL Antimicrobial Resistance (AR) as the main organiser analysed the data in relation to all epidemiological traits despite the intention was to illustrate that EQA reference material could be used in a broader context. The CARE collection was thought to be a huge new resource for future work but was limited by difficulties to transfer ownership and legal rights to the partners engaged with the development. Lastly, it was envisioned that an interactive risk assessment dashboard would have been developed but this ambition was reduced to the current deliverable state as co-funding at DTU was ceased and person employed resigned. Nonetheless, the CARE met the original objectives in a satisfactory way.

CARE managed to provide a glimpse into existing EQA programmes and based on the findings to successfully conduct three EQA/ PT trials as well as developing an EQA guidance template for future use. CARE also managed to collect a reasonable number of isolates to be served as reference material in addition to a number of genomes with associated metadata. The data of the reference material was entered a developed web dashboard from where scientists can search for suitable reference material as well as making requests. Finally, CARE conducted risks assessment surveys on which a R script was developed to be further utilized by supranational organizations (include the element in WP4.2 above).

From a management point of view, the EJP construction does not empower the grantee/ lead to push the partners in certain directions to fulfil the ambition objectives due to the financing system and the large portion of co-funding. This makes it difficult to manage the project as the grantee/ lead to not have any financial or legal power to influence the work. In CARE, we learned that it would be possible to set up EQA schemes and share reference material if this is demanded by funding bodies. It also showed that genomic based EQAs are rather labour intensive to prepare and conduct compared to more phenotypic trials. Further, CARE observed how difficult it is to share strains and metadata due to compliance to the Nagoya protocol as well as to private rights (GDPR). Thus, this is a huge barrier in setting up reference material repositories. The risk assessment tool was developed as a R script and show promising potential in future work to extend the portfolio of scripts in R.

In conclusion, there is potential to move EQAs into the genomic area as well as using the reference material in a broader context. We need to address the barriers of sharing reference material as we otherwise will lack these in future outbreak and surveillance contexts. Finally, there is great potential in expanding scripts in R as showed for the risk assessment.

6.4 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

6.4.1 Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP03-CARE	D.0.7	Minutes of all tele-conferences	60	60	Available in the OHEJP CARE website	8 (communication)
JIP03-CARE	D.1.2.1	WP1-T2-ST1: Report - Pilot Isolation/detection of pathogens	54	53	https://zenodo.org/record/6575861#.YoyVBKhBxaQ	1,2
JIP03-CARE	D.1.2.2	WP1-T2-ST2: Report - Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS	54	58	https://zenodo.org/record/7462445#.Y6L08HbMKUk	1,2
JIP03-CARE	D.1.2.3	WP1-T2-ST3 Report - Pilot on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data	54	58	https://zenodo.org/record/7462573#.Y6MMI3bMKUk	1,2
JIP03-CARE	D.1.3.1	Guidance document for cross sectorial proficiency testing	54	58	https://zenodo.org/record/7467622#.Y6MEYnbMKUk	1
JIP03-CARE	D.1.3.2	D.1.3.2 SOPs for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions	54	58	https://zenodo.org/record/7467902#.Y6MFLXbMKUk	2

JIP03-CARE	D.2.2	Sub-database for antimicrobial resistances	48	54	https://zenodo.org/record/6644884#.YqmXVXZB yUk	3,4
JIP03-CARE	D.2.4	Genome assemblies and raw reads deposited at ENA	58	60	https://zenodo.org/record/7467914#.Y6MGE nbMKUk	3
JIP03-CARE	D.2.5	Spectral (MALDI-TOF) database of protein mass fingerprints	58	60	Writing in progress	3,4
JIP03-CARE	D.3.1.3	Searchable online RMs catalogue	46	53	https://cirmbp.bioaware.com/ https://zenodo.org/record/6575874#.YoyW KhBx aQ	3
JIP03-CARE	D.3.2.1	Deposit of all the reference strains within microbial collections considered as “reference collections”	51	58	Public - The CARE collection actually comprised 225 strains available for diffusion (Nov 2022). (Previously D3.2) https://zenodo.org/record/7467959#.Y6MlfnbMK Uk	4
JIP03-CARE	D.3.3.1	Reference strains made accessible <i>via</i> the CARE single entry point portal	46	58	Public - CARE collection website: https://cirmbp.bio-aware.com/ (Previously D3.3)	3,4
JIP03-CARE	D.3.4.1	Signing of an MoU to ensure the sustainability of the CARE IS	59	59	Public - The sustainability plan was provided. (Previously D3.4) https://zenodo.org/record/7467976#.Y6MJ33bM KUk	8 (MoU)
JIP03-CARE	D.4.1	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility			Renamed to D.4.1.3	

JIP03-CARE	D.4.1.2	The establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place	47	54	Available in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/6644910#.YqmZv3ZByUk	1,3
JIP03-CARE	D.4.1.3	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility.	42	47	Deliverable D.4.1.3. Report on the survey related to the availability and quality of data used for risk assessment. Available in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5882651#.Yek9yP7MKUk	4,5
JIP03-CARE	D.4.2.1	User Guide for accessing relevant data for risk-assessment	54	57	The guide is deposited on github (https://github.com/valleemarie/CARE-GuideQMRA) and the first release has been published for the final CARE meeting. The current release is available at: https://lguillier.quarto.pub/care-guide-for-data/ https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7455276	2, 4
JIP03-CARE	D.4.2.2	Implementation of developed strategy to raise awareness by EU authorities	54	59	https://zenodo.org/record/7455313#.Y5-BnXbMLIU	5
JIP03-CARE	D.4.2.3	Web based exchange platform including antimicrobial resistance surveillance data.			D.4.2.3 omitted in AWP Y5	
JIP03-CARE	D.4.3	An executed dissemination plan	54	59	https://zenodo.org/record/7455376	8 (Dissemination plan)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

6.4.2 Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
JIP03-CARE	M.0.3	Closing meeting - 2022	58		
JIP03-CARE	M.1.3	Review of previous tasks (1 & 2) for the production of a guidance document for proficiency testing and SOPs for specific distributions.	50	59	The draft report was discussed at the final CARE meeting in Copenhagen in September 2022 and the report has been issued.
JIP03-CARE	M.2.3	Exhaustive characterization of EUROpanelIOH RM	58	59	
JIP03-CARE	M.3.2	Microbial collection management Training session done	49	53	Organisation of a training session attended by 12 CARE partners over two days in May 2022 which included visits to two microbial BRCs and a set of 15 conferences. All documents were made available.
JIP03-CARE	M.3.3.1	Drafting MoU to be done and circulated among partners	47	59	A sustainability plan was elaborated (D3.4.1)
JIP03-CARE	M.3.3.2	Launching event of the CARE portal where stakeholders will be invited to sign the MoU	50		N.A.
JIP03-CARE	M.4.3	Dissemination plan	50	50	The dissemination plan includes the strategy of dissemination element.

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6.5 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Guillier L, Palma F, Fritsch L. Taking account of genomics in quantitative microbial risk assessment: what methods? what issues? <i>Current Opinion in Food Science</i> 100922; 2022. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2022.100922</p>		Yes	No yet, but the manuscript will be deposited in HAL repository	Costs currently unknown
<p>Lahti E, Karamehmedovic N, Riedel H, Blom L, Boel J, Delibato E, Denis M, van Essen- Zandbergen A, Garcia-Fernandez A, Hendriksen R, Heydecke A, Huby T, Kwit R, Lucarelli C, Lundin K, Michelacci V, Owczarek S, Ring I, Sjögren I, Skóra M, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Torpdahl M, Veldman K, Ventola E, Zajac M, Jernberg C. One Health surveillance – a cross-sectoral detection, characterisation and notification of foodborne pathogens.</p>	Manuscript in preparation	Yes	No	Yes, 3000 €
<p>Chesneau, O., Michelacci V., Helloin, E., Boniotti, MB, Clermont, D., Mistou, MY The CARE collection of foodborne bacteria: A new resource for food safety research and innovation.</p>	In preparation	Yes	No	Yes 5000€

6.6 Additional output

- Oral presentation at Agrostat eConference 2021. De Oliveira Mota J, Redondo HG, Bergis H, Poisson S, Dubuisson C, Sanaa M, et al., editors. The Third French Individual and National Food Consumption (INCA3) Survey 2014–2015 and data for microbiological risk assessment: Models for domestic refrigerator temperatures 16th Agro-Industry and Statistical Methods congress; 2021 September 14-15; Online conference.
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, Juin 9-11 2021 Copenhagen and online. De Oliveira Mota J, Aarts H, Guillier L, Desvignes V, editors. Identification of data currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment.
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, 2022 Orvieto, Italy Elina Lahti, Linnéa Blom, Hilde Riedel, Nadja Karamemedovic, Anna Heydecke, Aurora Garcia Fernandez, Claudia Lucarelli, Elisabetta Delibato, Ingegerd Sjögren, Isaac Ring, Jeppe Boel, Karl Lundin, Kees Veldman, Lucas Wijnands, Maria Ugarte Ruiz, Martine Denis, Mia Torpdahl, Renata Kwit, Rene Hendriksen, Cecilia Jernberg “A cross-sectional pilot proficiency test/external quality assessment on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens.
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, 2022 Orvieto, Jeppe Boel, Sally Hallam, Małgorzata L. Marzęta, Paula Johnson, Mia Torpdahl. «Cross-sectorial one health proficiency test for cluster detection of Campylobacter, Salmonella, and Listeria monocytogenes based on whole genome sequencing”
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13 2022, Orvieto, Forum Shah, Maria-Beatrice Boniotti, Anne Brisabois, Olivier Chesneau, Dominique Clermont, Emmanuelle Helloin, Rene Hendriksen, Valeria Michelacci, Michel-Yves Mistou and the OH-EJP CARE consortium. The CARE collection, an open panel of microbiological reference materials dedicated to zoonotic and foodborne bacterial pathogens.
- Oral presentation at OHEJP JIPs CARE, MATRIX, OH-HARMONY-CAP closing meeting, September 20, 2022, Copenhagen Denmark. J. Boel (WP1), MY Mistou (WP2/3), L Guillier (WP4).RE collection of foodborne bacteria:
- Oral presentation at Campylobacter EURL Annual meeting, September 27, 2022, Sigtuna, Sweden. MY Mistou. <https://www.sva.se/en/about-us/eurl-campylobacter/workshops/workshop-2022/> Th
- Oral presentation of the OHEJP CARE project, especially pilot PT1 of WP1 at the EURL Campylobacter workshop, Sigtuna, September 27-28, 2022 (Elina Lahti) <https://www.sva.se/en/about-us/eurl-campylobacter/workshops/workshop-2022/> resource

6.7 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

- Presentation of the OHEJP CARE project with a focus on the inventory of reference materials and database at the Anses internal reference meeting, Maisons-Alfort, 19th of May 2022 (A. Brisabois).
- A large collection of well-characterised reference strains of food-borne pathogens (>2500 strains) will be available for scientists and laboratories to use in Dec. 2022.
- The three distributions of well characterized WGS data from clustering and non-clustering Campylobacter, Listeria monocytogenes, and Salmonella isolates can be used to evaluate cluster detection pipelines in the future.
- Guidance on cross-sectorial proficiency tests/external quality assurance

- Guide for accessing relevant data and models for quantitative microbial risk assessment: <https://lguillier.quarto.pub/care-guide-for-data/>

6.8 Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

WP1

WP1-T2 have offered cross sectorial pilot PT's, of which three have been provided to the EJP CARE project members. To some extent these have been discussed or implemented already, i.e.:

- WP1-T2-ST1 'Pilot PT on isolation/detection of pathogens' - to our knowledge a cross sectorial PT (or EQA) had not been done before and caused some considerations as the aim for laboratories in the public health sector compared to the food/veterinary sector in relation to isolating/detecting pathogens. Future PT's of this type would be relevant to allow laboratories to quality assure the surveillance data they provide, though, setup of future PT's will require raising awareness of the relevance of such PT's to ensure funding for this activity e.g. by preparing a one-pager for international collaborators, for example ECDC/WHO/FAO/EURL networks.
- WP1-T2-ST2 'Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS' – a PT of this setup is has also been provided for the EURL-AR network and it was agreed that it would be highly relevant to continue this type of PT. Currently, within EU, funding allows the EURL-AR to offer it annually to laboratories in the EURL-AR network.
- WP1-T2-ST3 'Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data' - within EU, clustering PT's have been provided from the EURL *E. coli*, EURL *Campylobacter* and from ECDC. The EURL on *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella* participated in the pilot PT.
- The Framework for setting up new cross sectorial PT was send to the EURL laboratories for commenting

WP3

- The CARE collection has been implemented, and strains have been exchanged with research groups.
- The CARE collection has been presented to *Campylobacter* EURL annual meeting (Sep, 2022) and to the Luxembourg LNS (Nov, 2022)

WP4

- Interaction with EFSA (in relation to WP4): Participation to the "Advisory Group on Data: Sub Group on Digital Platforms and Ecosystems" planned the 28th November 2022 (the meetings will continue in 2023).
- Interaction with EFSA MRA network (in relation WP4): Each member states will be able to add in the Guidance document for accessing data for QMRA (D.4.2.1), the relevant sources of data in the field of foodborne pathogen epidemiology, antimicrobial resistance, consumption (mail sent end of November 2022).

6.9 One Health impact

- Cross-sectorial proficiency tests can be used as an additional tool to assess One Health capacity and cross-sectorial surveillance or monitoring results. The clinical microbiological laboratories from one country participating in the pilot PT/EQA on detection and characterisation of foodborne pathogens found the concept of cross-sectorial PTs/EQAs interesting and useful.
- Obtaining sequences from bacterial isolates and basing the analysis of AMR determinants on

bioinformatic analysis of these is already part of national reference laboratories' routine activities both in the food/veterinary sector and in public health. External quality assessment of this procedure has already proven to be useful and has been a learning experience for both PT-provider and PT participants.

- The three distributions of well characterized WGS data from clustering and non-clustering *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella* isolates can be used to evaluate and compare cluster detection pipelines in the future.
- A particular effort has been made to ensure that the CARE collection represents the different AMR phenotypes circulating within the food pathogen strains. The easy accessibility of these strains is of interest for research in the AMR field
- The CARE project has strengthened cooperation between the health and veterinary safety agencies and the BRCs within the research institutes.
- The “Guide for accessing relevant data and models for quantitative microbial risk assessment” can serve as a reference document for the different stakeholders at European levels involves in microbial risk assessment (MRA). The document gives an almost exhaustive view of the data useful for MRA. In the medium term this document (which will continue to be updated) could be extended to the extra-European level. The guide already integrates data from the world institutions FAO and WHO.
- The RSelectStrain tool proposes formal methods for strain selection. They might be used by the different EU-RLs to support them in the establishment of strain collections.
- The RSelectStrain tool is planned to be used at French level by NRLs *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*

6.10 Data Management Plan

- <https://zenodo.org/record/7463599#.Y6G27nbMJJaQ>

6.11 Future dissemination activities

- EJP CARE outcomes proposed to be included in the training activities to Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA) countries in the future.

7. JIP04-R2-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP

7.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

OH-HARMONY-CAP was a 3-year project that aimed to: 1. Collect information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe by developing an in-depth OHLabCap survey. 2. Examine current and best practices within the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. 3. Produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of pathogens. By the end of 2022, 18 partner institutes from 14 European countries constituted the OH-HARMONY-CAP Consortium.

OH-HARMONY-CAP has achieved the following:

- OHLabCap developed and tested, for the first time a One Health monitoring tool, which collected information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability in EU/EEA countries across all One Health sectors: Human clinical, food, feed, veterinary and environmental laboratories. The tool focused on selected priority parasites (5) and bacteria (6). *Impact: The OHLabCap highlighted major differences between the diagnostic laboratories in the two main sectors human clinical and food/feed/veterinary across the One Health microbiological systems in place in the participating countries. Of particular concern, is the lack of accreditation and standardisation in the human clinical diagnostic laboratories.*
- A first survey of the food business operators HACCP-based self-control programmes; including the sampling and analytical methods food business operators (FBOs) carry out on priority parasites and bacteria to support a more comparable microbiological sampling and testing programmes. *Impact: the analysis revealed gaps and differences between food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes and official monitoring programmes within and between countries. This information provides a baseline for further harmonisation and standardisation of sampling and analytical protocols of foodborne pathogens, not only at a national level but in a European context.*
- Current & best practice in: [1] sampling & testing; [2] characterisation, and [3] data management & harmonised reporting for laboratories testing food, feed, environmental and human samples for Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. across the EU were surveyed using peer reviewed papers, grey literature and questionnaires. The latter were completed by European public health, veterinary, food testing and National Reference Laboratories reached via the EURL network of NRLs, EFSA Zoonoses network, ECDC Food and Waterborne Disease network, amongst others. *Impact: The three reports delivered highlighted current deficits and data gaps with recommendations on how these could be addressed.*
- Developed criteria for a ranking system for an assessment of laboratory protocols. The ranking system was applied on collected protocols for the detection and characterisation of Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp.
- The results of the ranking of submitted protocols were used to select and recommend the currently best procedures and protocols:
 1. Proposed harmonised procedures for the detection and typing of Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), and Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC). The evaluation of the chosen

protocols included examination of PCR primer choices. This resulted in the development of alternative omni-primers for the detection of the STEC and ETEC defining genes as the chosen protocols did not reflect the current knowledge of new subtypes and variants of the genes. As such, four new subtypes of Shigatoxin genes have been described and three of these have been published as part of the OH-HARMONY-CAP project. Publication of the last eight new Shiga toxins is in preparation.

2. No need to issue a unique procedure for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp.
3. Developed and proposed a decision tree for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium*
 - Proposed harmonised procedures to distinguish between Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC) and *Shigella* spp. Both of these groups are often causes of foodborne outbreaks and the project chose to develop and test PCR primers that could separate the two groups from one another.
 - Arranged and provided training sessions for the harmonised procedures
 - The developed protocols are expected to be tested in future EQA programmes

Impact: *The proposed procedures, if implemented, will contribute to an improvement in the standardisation and harmonisation of protocols for the model organisms. The ranking of laboratory protocols also provided and suggested elements for consideration and choice of protocol that can be applied for other organisms and procedures in the OH sectors. The development of new PCR primers for the detection of STEC and ETEC related genes represents an update reflecting the current epidemiology and current knowledge of microbiology organisms that are forever changing. These so-called moving targets are an illustration that microbes constantly evolve and adapt, which in turn makes it increasingly important to update and share front line detection and characterisation methodology.*

7.2 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1 Project coordination

The OH-HARMONY-CAP project changed project leader from Flemming Scheutz to Nadia Boisen in April 2020.

JIP04-WP1-T1: Internal coordination

M25-M60

As part of the internal engagement it has been important to effectively communicate the progress and status of the project. At the Kick of Meeting (KOM) in January, 2020 we communicated a common understanding of the roles and responsibilities, output specifics and expectation.

- January 2020: Formed the OH-HARMONY-CAP project group: WP leaders and WP deputy leaders; Nadia Boisen, Flemming, Scheutz, Mélanie Gay, Mónica Oleastro, Rosangela Tozzoli, Stefano Morabito, Patrizia Rossi, Tryntsje Cuperus, Joke van der Giessen, and Declan Bolton
- Three in- person/hybrid consortium meetings; 21-APHA, Addlestone, UK, 21nd-23rd January 2020, 26-Teagasc, Dublin, Ireland November 9-11th 2021, and 13-SSI Copenhagen, Denmark, 20th – 22nd September 2022
- Several emails to all participants with project overview, status, and decisions
- Frequent individual conference meetings with project leads and co-leads from work packages
- Several conference calls with the OH-HARMONY-CAP project group, including a welcome online meeting with new partners on May 27th 2021
- Online conference calls with the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium: July 14th 2020, November 11th 2020, and January 13th 2021
- In 2021 OH-HARMONY-CAP updated AWP 4 and AWP 5 to include additional tasks under WP2 and WP4 and revise the budget
- The three new partners; The Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII), Spain, The Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment (BIOR), Latvia, and The Finnish Food Authority (RUOKA), Finland, joined the OH-HARMONY-CAP in May 2021. At the OH-HARMONY-CAP welcoming meeting, the WP leaders presented their work packages and tasks were identified where BIOR, ISCIII, and RUOKA could contribute. Following the meeting BIOR, ISCIII, and RUOKA were asked to fill in a document listing all the tasks. Consequently and thereafter, all OH-HARMONY-CAP email lists and budgets have been updated to include the new partners
- September 2021, change in WP5 lead within 27-ISS

JIP04-WP1-T2: External coordination, outreach and engagement

M25-M60

As part of the external engagement and to effectively find synergies with other project, disseminate our project, progress and results, OH-HARMONY-CAP has had an active role in both participation and presentation in various activities: 1) routine communication with the OHEJP WP4 and OHEJP Coordination team. 2) welcoming new partners, 3) communication, collaboration, and presentation with other OHEJP projects (JIPs, DiSCoVer, PARADISE, and TOXOSOURCES), 4) communication and outreach to stakeholders by inviting them to comment on surveys, questionnaires, and OH-HARMONY-

CAP consortium meetings, 5) the three JIPs have regularly presented at each other consortium meetings, 6) arranged and participated in a meeting on possible synergies between the FWD AMR-RefLabCap (Food- and Waterborne Diseases Antimicrobial Resistance - Reference Laboratory Capacity) project and OH-HARMONY-CAP, 7) presented at the annual One Health EJP internal meeting at Statens Serum Institut (SSI) (Joint meeting between all the EJP projects that SSI is involved in), 9) presented to potential new partner institutions, May 2021, 9) presented and participated in the panel discussion at the One Health Session for EPIET and EUPHEM, August 25th, 2021, 10) oral and poster presentations at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting in 2020, 2021, and 2022, 11) presented at the 8th Stakeholder committee meeting of the One Health EJP, November 22nd 2021, 12) participated in the One Health EJP - Online joint meeting of Programme Managers Committee and Programme Owners Committee, November 24th, 2021, 13) presented at the Project Leaders Forum (PLF), April 12th ASM 2022, 14) participated and contributed to the One Health EJP side event at ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference 2022, on the 22nd of June 2022 in Brussels, 15) presented at the OHEJP SSB meeting 28 September 2022 in Riga, 16) presented at the POC-PMC meeting in Stockholm on 22 November 2022. 17) presented at the One Health EJP Final School - Foodborne Zoonoses session on December 7th 2022, 18) plan on presenting at the VTEC2023 satellite workshop in Banff, Canada. Four poster presentations at EJP ASM 2020, 2021 and 2022. 19) presented during the Annual workshop organized by the EURL for Parasites in 2020 [Workshop 2020 \(full content\) - ISS \(EN\) - ISS](#)

Additionally:

A strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs, MATRIX, CARE, and OH-HARMONY-CAP to ensure a joint strong sustainability strategy. Together, we successfully 1) co-hosted a Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM) “EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective” (D4.21) in collaboration with JIP CARE and OHEJP WP4, in May 2021. The meeting included a panel discussion with representatives from ECDC and EFSA. There was a wide agreement, that there is a need for a continuation of the activities performed in the JIPs. Further, there is support from ECDC representatives for activities needed to implement the results (JIP outcome). 2) Organised the third OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2022 with a theme on “Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests” module aiming at bringing the professionals and experiences from different domains and encourage to seek out new synergies and collaborations. 3) participated in each other’s annual/interim meetings sharing knowledge and progress on the projects including, a jointly held final meeting “Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022” in September 2022 in Copenhagen, Denmark. 3) Prepared a joint thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health surveillance. The call was launched in the Journal *Frontiers in Public Health* aiming at collected intermediate achievements of the OHEJP JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects’ methods and strategies.

JIP04-WP1-T3: Data management

M25-M60

The project leader participated in the Data Management Platform (CDP) training on July 29th 2020. The list of data covered in OH-HARMONY-CAP DMP was specified during the first year of the project. The first DMP version (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.1.1) was published M33 and the final DMP was published in M60 (D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap. Final Data management plan) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436715>

JIP04-WP1-T4: Sustainability

Our sustainability activities will be focused on the dissemination of the chosen protocols. The protocols for STEC/EPEC and the decision tree for *Cryptosporidium* represents state-of-the-art is now being and will be tested by various partners and collaborators within Europe and USA (STEC/EPEC). The decision to implement the protocols is up to the partners, collaborators and laboratories outside this consortium.

WP2 Development of the OHLabCap

WP months: M25-M60. WP Leader: 13-SSI. Deputy WP Leader: 30-RIVM

WP2 participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants

The aim of WP2 was to develop a monitoring tool “OHLabCap” to assess One Health laboratory capability, capacity, interoperability and performance, together referred to as competences, across EU/EEA. The focus was on the detection and typing of selected priority foodborne bacteria, AMR determinants, and priority parasites across each sector (human, animal, and food/feed). The main deliverable resulted in the establishment of an OHLabCap instrument that is generically adjustable and sustainable at both an EU/EEA and national level.

JIP04-WP2-T1: Development and testing of the pilot survey

The development of a pilot survey, targeting NRLs, was expanded to include the primary diagnostic services (primary sector). This pilot survey, which became the OHLabCap, was initially drafted covering [1] capability, [2] capacity, and [3] interoperability. The pilot survey covered six priority bacteria and ten priority parasites which were chosen, as model organisms, together with the antimicrobial resistance (AMR) testing of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

The chosen priority microbes:

- Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, and *Listeria*.
- *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella spiralis*, *Echinococcus granulosus*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Trichinella* spp. other than *T. spiralis*, *Giardia lamblia*, *Anisakidae*, *Toxocara* spp. and *Taenia solium*

The survey was adapted for the EU online survey tool (JIP04-WP2-T2-S2) and distributed to the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium on September 7th 2020. The results were compiled, analysed and used to prepare Deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2.1 ‘Completed Pilot Survey’ and Deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2.2, “OHLabCap Result of the Pilot survey”

JIP04-WP2-T2: Scoring of Collected Data and Chosen Indicators

Several modifications to the pilot survey were undertaken and incorporated into the OHLabCap survey:

- Continue with the EUSurvey tool as a survey platform
- OH-HARMONY-CAP parasitologists reduced the number of target parasites to include the top five highest ranked foodborne parasites: *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus* (*sensu lato*), *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii* and *Trichinella* spp.
- Questions targeting laboratory adaptability were included. Note, adaptability is more relevant than ever due to Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, we decided to collect information on adaptability in the adjusted survey.
- The survey was routed on several levels *i.e.*, organism, laboratory functionality and methods
- The classification and scoring of competences, capacity, capability, interoperability, adaptability, and communication have been clarified
- The “NA” option was added to several questions
- The final revised tool is now able to score distribution in the three dimensions (primary diagnostic testing, NRL services, and interoperability and communication) by discipline in the different sectors (human, animal and food/feed) and by country (maps)

After multiple reviews and pilot tests, the OHLabCap survey was distributed on May 7th with a July 31st deadline 2020. The survey link was accompanied by a letter of invitation and a “how to save the survey document”. To ensure an optimal response, the OHLabCap was distributed via the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium, *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit, FWD-network, OHEJP JIPs/JRPs and the Scientific Steering Board, EURL-VTEC, EURL-*Listeria*, EURL-*Campylobacter*, and EURL-*Salmonella*. Concurrently, OH-HARMONY-CAP recipients were also asked to help with the distributions and circulation of the OHLabCap survey, particularly to the national primary laboratories. Identifying laboratory contact points has been a challenge. The survey received 122 responses from 25 different countries.

JIP04-WP2-T4: Scoring of collected data and chosen indicators

JIP04-WP2-T4 has evaluated, assessed, and scored the collected data from the OHLabCap monitoring tool in order to prepare the One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability for the National reference and primary diagnostic laboratories in each of the EU/EEA countries. The overall outcome is an integrated One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability in the two main sectors human diagnostics (PH) and non-human (AH and FS) laboratories for each of the chosen organisms for the NRLs and primary diagnostic laboratories in the EU/EEA countries. This tool does not include an evaluation of surveillance capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap), which is included in MATRIX.

When designing the OHLabCap we used the EULabCap as a model which applies three dimensions and 10 targets. However, the EULabCap is very broad and was only focussed on PH. The OHLabCap covers AH, PH and FS and focuses on fewer pathogens and is therefore more detailed and specific. In light of the Covid-19 pandemic, we also decided to add a fourth target *i.e.* adaptability. The OHLabCap monitoring tool also used three dimensions: 1) Primary diagnostic testing, 2) NRL services, and 3) Interoperability and communication. Of note, this latter dimension was changed from “Surveillance/epidemic response support” in the EULabCap. The number of targets was increased to 15 (see final WP2 report Development of the OHLabCap). At the Dublin meeting participants were divided into groups to discuss the presentation of the results and provide 32-FHI with comments and suggestions. Main outcome of these discussions were the interpretation of the terms, which were originally defined in the EULabCap as follows:

- Laboratory capability - the ability to perform the following functions: manage laboratory activities; perform sample management; conduct testing and analysis for routine and surge capacity; support public health investigations and report results [1].
- Laboratory capacity - consists of output services completed over a defined time period for each capability [2].

Note, in the OHLabCap, adaptability was defined as the ability and preparedness to make organisational, personnel and methodological changes.

The OHLabCap highlighted major differences across the One Health microbiological systems in place in the participating countries. Of particular concern, is the lack of accreditation and standardisation in the human clinical diagnostic laboratories compared to the food/feed and veterinary laboratories, where a few standardised ISO standards are followed.

Further, due to the high participation within some countries we have an (almost) complete picture of the microbiological system within that country.

There are several ways in which the results of the OHLabCap can be visualised *i.e.* by sector, by country. The deliverable will be ready by the end of the project.

JIP04-WP2-T5: Development of a survey targeting the food sectors self-control

WP Leader: 39-SLV. Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI and 9-BfR

The primary aim of this task was to provide an overview of the current procedures for microbiological sampling and analyses among food business operators' Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP)-based self-control programmes in the European Union (EU). A survey was developed within the project and conducted for the first time in EU/ European Economic Area (EEA) countries. Like the OHLabCap, this nine-question-survey was focused on the analyses of microbiological samples for the following six priority bacteria: *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp.; and five priority parasites: *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus* (*Sensu lato*), *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*.

Participating EU/EEA countries distributed an online questionnaire to food business operators' laboratories within their countries; and overall, responses from nine countries were received and feedback from 35 laboratories were considered for data analysis.

Conclusion: the study gathered insight into current practices of microbiological sampling and analyses performed in food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes in EU/EEA countries. However, further efforts are needed for harmonisation and standardisation of analytical protocols and further characterisation of foodborne pathogens. A need for regular participation in EQAs might be considered in the future.

Deliverable, D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.5. <https://zenodo.org/record/6414920#.YpUf1YzP02w>.

WP3 One Health Laboratory Interoperability Guidance

WP months: M25-M57. WP Leader: 26-Teagasc. WP Deputy Leader: 36-INSA

WP3 Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

The data generated from testing food, feed, environmental and human samples for pathogens such as Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp is essential for protecting public and animal health in the EU. Moreover, as the information generated informs European policy and legislation it is critical that the sampling and testing methods are state of the art, that the isolates are sufficiently characterised and the data generated is efficiently stored and communicated to key stakeholders. The overall aim of this WP was, therefore, to examine current and best practices in the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. This was achieved by reviewing the currently available scientific and grey literature and using targeted questionnaires. The outputs included 3 reports which were disseminated via the OHEJP website.

With the ultimate aim of providing guidance for the development of a more efficient and harmonised system the following issues were addressed:

Sampling and testing

- current and best practice in designing statistically based sampling plans
- the most appropriate sampling methods
- currently available testing (detection) methods
- how these are applied
- the latest technologies/technological developments

Strain characterisation

- current routine strain characterisation in Europe
- gaps in strain characterisation that are inhibiting food safety regulation/policy in the EU
- recommendations on what typing methods, AMR and virulence gene testing, etc. should be undertaken as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation
- recommendations on how this harmonised strategy should be implemented

Data management

- current used data management systems in Europe
- a harmonised data management system for the future
- recommendations on how this system should be implemented (software, motivating MSs, etc.).

For the purposes of this work, four target pathogens were selected including:

1. Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
2. Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC)
3. *Cryptosporidium*
4. AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Note, the WP3 tasks were carried out by dividing the WP3 participants into groups of pathogen experts.

JIP04-WP3-T1: A review of current & best practice in sampling & testing food, feed, environmental and human samples for Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. was undertaken using peer reviewed papers, the grey literature and questionnaires. The output was delivered as a technical report (<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-HARMONY-CAP>)

Results - sampling and testing: A range of different sampling plans (statistically based, national, European, etc.) are used. Most testing methods are accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025 or ISO 15189 and use ISO/TS 13136 or equivalent PCR. Culture-based detection methods used were based on immunomagnetic separation (IMS) and/or direct plating on various selective media. Biochemical confirmatory testing varied considerably and the majority of laboratories also used conventional PCR and/or real time PCR accredited confirmatory methods. Isolates are typically stored in their own laboratory and/or in the NRL.

JIP04-WP3-T2: A review of current & best practices in characterising Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. isolated from food, feed, environmental and human samples was undertaken using peer reviewed papers, the grey literature and questionnaires. The results, including recommendations, were provided in a technical report (<https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Yf0PceqZNPY>).

Results - Characterisation: Approximately one quarter of laboratories performed phenotypic characterisation using biochemical assays although the methods varied greatly. The same applied when testing for subgroups, subtypes and specific virulence genes.

JIP04-WP3-T3: A review of current & best practice in data management and harmonised reporting was undertaken using the published literature and questionnaires. Relevant experts within a selection of the

partner institutes were also consulted. The output was delivered as a technical report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6899935>).

Results - Data management and harmonised reporting: The majority of laboratories have an Information and communications technology (ICT) based system for storing data but there is no harmonised reporting within regions, counties and to the relevant European authorities

Local, regional and national laboratories may implement the recommendations of the three technical reports in WP3. Moreover, EFSA has a key role in developing more effective data management and communication practices across the EU. EFSA/ECDC, for example, should take primary responsibility for updating and enhancing the current system of data management and reporting, resulting in the implementation of a LIMS type system. Moreover using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), they can provide an environment for hosting and processing data to support EU science, while directly linking local laboratories with regional, national and European data centres.

WP3 provided a forum for different laboratories across the EU to meet, discuss and agree the best approach/methods for sampling, testing, isolate characterisation (including AMR testing) and more effective communication between themselves, with their regional/national and European (reference laboratories). Thus the network of food, feed, environmental and human testing laboratories across the EU has been strengthened and new connections established that will ensure new technologies, methodologies and expertise are more easily disseminated, shared and/or implemented across the EU.

Recommendations and conclusions:

The main recommendations for testing include greater application of recently developed PCR technologies such as digital PCR and WGS. The latter provides high discriminatory power for foodborne outbreak investigation, source-attribution and hazard identification, potentially leading to a more targeted risk assessment. Moreover, analysis of WGS data allows the identification of virulence factors and antibiotic resistance determinants, which would previously have required a number of PCR tests.

Greater use of WGS is also a key recommendation for characterisation as WGS based typing is able to respond to several hazard characterisation questions all at once, representing a powerful tool for characterisation purposes. There are also recommendations on what typing methods, AMR and virulence gene testing, etc. should be undertaken as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation.

Among the recommendations for data management and harmonised reporting is a suggestion that EFSA/ECDC should evaluate the different software/information management systems available and recommend their use with a target harmonisation date of 2030. The EFSA evaluation should be undertaken in full consultation with all relevant stakeholders and the long lead-in-time would allow laboratories to upgrade or replace their software when their current hardware and software licenses expire. As the same software will then be used across the EU it should be possible to negotiate a more favourable purchase or licensing arrangement which may be subsidised by DG Health. Alternatively the EC could purchase a pan-EU license or recommend the use of open access software. Such a centralised approach would facilitate compatibility in terms of data transfer and could result in the equivalent of a LIMS type system directly linking local laboratories with regional, national and European data centres. It is also consistent with and could provide an additional function of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which provides an environment for hosting and processing data to support EU science.

If these recommendations are acted upon there would be harmonised sampling, testing, strain characterisation, data management and reporting systems across the EU and the data required to underpin future EC food safety and public health protection guidance, policy and legislation would be more readily available.

WP4 Harmonisation of Protocols

WP months: M25-M57. WP Leader: 27-ISS. WP Deputy Leader: I-ANSES

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA, 44-Bior

The aim of WP4 was to produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of the model pathogens. These pathogens were selected as examples for the project's purposes, and identified candidates included Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) and *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. The strategy and the approaches adopted in the framework of WP4 activities may be transferred to other pathogens, enabling harmonisation of methodologies in use in the EU/EEA laboratories. Detailed information can be found in the WP4 deliverable, a technical report (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP4.3)

The model organisms was selected for the following reasons:

- STEC are foodborne pathogens of public health concern, able to induce severe disease in humans, such as haemorrhagic colitis and the haemolytic-uraemic syndrome, and the infection may be fatal
- ETEC strains have frequently been associated to the so-called travellers' diarrhoea, but represent an emerging public health concern, also in high-income countries. In the pig production, ETEC is one of the main causes of post weaning diarrhoea in piglets resulting in the premature death of a large number of piglets each day
- *Cryptosporidium* spp. are important waterborne pathogens worldwide and a leading cause of mortality from waterborne gastrointestinal diseases. Moreover, they are important pathogens for livestock
- AMR is considered an emerging problem in the different sectors of the One Health system.

To propose the harmonized procedures, three tasks have been undertaken:

1. Collection of the laboratory protocols for model organisms in use in the EU/EEA laboratories (JIP04-WP4-T1)
2. Evaluation of the collected laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of selected foodborne pathogens, including STEC/ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, in use in the laboratories operating in public health and veterinary sectors (JIP04-WP4-T2)
3. Ranking and choice of laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of model organisms (JIP04-WP4-T3)

JIP04-WP4-T1

Laboratory procedures and protocols for the selected microorganisms, STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium* spp. and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp., were collected from OH-HARMONY-CAP partners by sending the request to the networks of reference laboratories operating in the areas of public health and veterinary/food safety.

Besides reaching out to the project participants, a request for sharing the protocols was also sent to the Head of ECDC Food and Waterborne Diseases (FWD) programme and to the Directors of the relevant EURLs: EURL for *E. coli*, EURL for Parasites and EURL for Antimicrobial Resistance, who forwarded the request to the respective networks.

Overall, 23 institutions operating in the public health, animal health and/or food safety /fields, including the relevant EURLs, either participants of the OH-HARMONY-CAP project or from other networks, responded to our request. The list of the laboratories responding to the request of sharing protocols can be found in the technical report (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP4.3).

The protocols/documents shared and considered in the following WP4 tasks consisted in:

- 49 protocols on STEC
- 6 protocols on ETEC
- 7 documents on both ETEC/STEC
- 20 protocols on *Cryptosporidium* spp.
- 17 protocols on AMR in *Salmonella* and/or *Campylobacter*
- 2 documents providing information on the detection and typing of STEC, *Cryptosporidium* spp., AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*
- 1 document on *Cryptosporidium* spp., AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Additionally, some institutes also reported that ISO standards and EURL methods were in use.

JIP04-WP4-T2

The collected protocols were subjected to a preliminary evaluation. The aim of this task included a preliminary assessment of the procedures and a summary table to ease the comparison of the protocols. As such, it was possible to identify similarities between the protocols and enable the production of a ranking table and, finally, the selection of harmonised procedures in JIP04-WP4-T3.

Task activities was divided into three different subtasks, carried out by groups of experts consisting of 4-6 WP4 participants:

- WP4-T2-S1: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of STEC/ETEC
- WP4-T2-S2: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*
- WP4-T2-S3: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

JIP04-WP4-T3

The aim of this task was to define the harmonised procedures to be proposed and applied in the training sessions organized in WP5 of the OH-HARMONY-CAP project. Moreover, this output will also be disseminated to the networks operating in different sectors, once the procedures have been assessed. To select the harmonised procedures a ranking approach was applied. Note, depending on the target, different strategies were applied, either to assign scores to the collected protocols or to compare them.

STEC/ETEC: The exercise conducted for STEC and ETEC showed that the scoring approach could be applied and led to the choice of the best suited protocols for STEC and ETEC detection and characterization, based on the ranking (for details please see D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP4.3)

Parallel to the ranking and choice of best suited protocols, an extensive search has been carried out in order to investigate the appropriate targets. During this process, four new subtypes of Stx have been described and three of these have been published as part of the OH-HARMONY-CAP project. Publication of the last of eight new Shiga toxins (Stx2o) is in preparation. More than 865 different alleles of the *eae* gene have been analysed with the purpose of creating a simplified nomenclature for the *eae* genes. For the detection of ETEC related genes a similar approach has been applied and new subtypes of the *eltI* and *eltII* genes have been identified. For the characterisation of ETEC from both humans and animals, a revised database including a total of 518 ETEC related alleles (enterotoxins, colonisation factors and other ETEC related genes) has been developed and is being tested on 1,084 ETEC genomes with the purpose of adding these the WGS tool *VirulenceFinder* at the CGE website (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/VirulenceFinder/>). The database and the accompanying notes file is open source and can be downloaded from the CGE website ([genomic epidemiology / virulencefinder_db — Bitbucket](#)). Variants of the *aggR* gene have also been analysed. As a result of this extensive work, new omni primers for the detection of all subtypes and variants of the *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae*, *eltI*, *esta* and *aggR* genes have been developed. As part of WP5, these new primers have been tested at SSI and will

be further validated and compared with the primers used in the ranked protocols for the final training session of the OH-HARMONY-CAP project WP5. This work has been carried out in collaboration with International stakeholders within the EU, University of Santiago de Compostela, USC, Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Spain and the Department of Microbiology and Immunology, Institute of Biomedicine, Sahlgrenska Academy, University of Gothenburg, Sweden. Outside the EU, this work has involved the Parasites and Microbes Programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute, Hinxton, United Kingdom, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), The Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC), USDA Food Safety and Inspection Service (FSIS), the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), the Uniformed Services University of the Health Sciences (USUHS), Department of Microbiology and Immunology, and the National Institute for Health (NIH) in the USA.

AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp.: Based on the common evaluation criteria the final scores of dilution and diffusion based methods were close (23 for dilution based methods and 25 for diffusion based methods) and both of them are fit-for-purpose. Additionally, several International Bodies (EUCAST, CLSI M45, ISO) have put efforts in harmonizing these methods, therefore it was concluded that there was no need to suggest harmonized procedures.

***Cryptosporidium* spp.:** The collected laboratory procedures for *Cryptosporidium* were divided based on:

- 1) Sample preparation
- 2) Microscopic detection
- 3) Detection by PCR
- 4) Typing

While discussing the results of the evaluation, the partners realized that asking for protocols was not sufficient to be able to rank and compare them afterwards. Therefore, and unlike for STEC and ETEC, it was not possible to rank, based on scores, and put forward one harmonized procedure. Rather, the main output was a decision tree, directing the diagnostic based on the aim of the analysis. This was also supported by *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit, Public Health Wales. The challenges are described in details in the deliverable (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP4.3).

The decision tree has been applied during the training sessions organised in WP5 and the third OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2022 (Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests).

All the procedures deployed in WP4 are being assayed during the WP5 training sessions and will be made available to the different networks supporting dissemination of OH-HARMONY-CAP.

WP5 Training sessions on harmonised protocols

WP months: M40-M60. WP5 leader: 27-ISS. Co-Leader: 13-SSI.

WP5-T1 participants: All OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. WP5-T2 participants: All CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX participants. WP5-T3 participants: 13-SSI and 35-INIAV

The aim of WP5 consists of increasing EU capacity to deal with foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across the One Health interface through partner-to-partner delivery of training. The training will provide opportunities for better communication, knowledge exchange, and knowledge integration within the One Health interface, and not just for the OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. As such, two workshops were held during the final meeting in Copenhagen.

JIP4-WP5-T1 Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap

The final workshop was held in Copenhagen, on September 21st – 22nd for the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium. Each WP was discussed with overall focus on identification of gaps, recommendations, and

dissemination of OH-HARMONY-CAP. The overall consensus; 1) the consortium was very pleased with the useful outcomes and contributions from all WPs particular WP3, WP4, and WP5. 2) The development of OHLabCap proved difficult, particularly the formulation of the 59 questions as the various sectors perceive and understand them differently. One recommendation would entail additional work and focus groups and several pilots before launching the OHLabCap monitoring tool again as discussed in the final deliverable.

JIP04-WP5.T2 Joint workshop between CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX

The three projects jointly held their final meetings on September 20th 2022 in Copenhagen. Highlights from the three projects were presented. The meeting ended with a final roundtable where representatives of JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX, the OHEJP Project Management Team and OHEJP Stakeholders participated. During that discussion the following was discussed and highlighted:

- The JIPs have now concluded and delivered and sustainability of the JIP depends on those who can utilize and advance the generated knowledge and outputs. This is an opportunity of not just partner institutions but also countries and stakeholders
- Social sciences are key to ensure a change (in the direction of One Health) that necessarily requires a change in the knowledge, attitudes and practices of many across different sectors and at different levels of the decision-making process
- Studying the cost-effectiveness of One Health is an opportunity to secure the necessary attention that the approach requires.

JIP4-WP5-T3: Practical workshops (S1) and e-learning activities (S2)

Three practical workshops, focusing on the model organisms (STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*) was planned: 1) Training course for pathogenic *E. coli*, at 27ISS (Rome, Italy) 2) Training course on *Cryptosporidium* detection and characterization at 27-ISS (Rome, Italy). 3) Training course for AMR determination at 13-SSI (Copenhagen, Denmark)

- The practical workshops were held M54-M59
- Presentations and videos on the harmonised protocols will be published on a dedicated web-page on the OHEJP web site in order to disseminate the project achievements
- All the training delivered had a final step of assessment of the achievement of the learning objectives
- The trainings consisted of three days of laboratory activities on the application of the harmonised procedures developed in WP4

The trainees were primarily enrolled from the OH-HARMONY-CAP Consortium; nonetheless, the invitation was extended to other networks due to availability of places. There was no fee for participating in these trainings, however, the participants must sustain their travel expenses (travel, accommodation and allowance) on their own funds (e.g. OH-HARMONY-CAP own budget). An invitation letter and an application form to participate in three trainings was prepared with a deadline in August 10, 2022 and a further extension into mid-September 2022.

Due to logistic and safety reasons, no more than four places were available for each training session either for ETEC/STEC training or for *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Note, no participants signed up for the AMR training in *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* and therefore, the training was cancelled. This supports the output of WP4: Several international bodies (EUCAST,

CLSI M45, ISO) have put efforts into harmonizing methods for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, and it was concluded that there was no need to suggest harmonized procedures.

Training sessions on detections and typing of STEC and ETEC:

Two training sessions on the application of the harmonised procedures was held for pathogenic *E. coli*. These have been organized at ISS, at the European Union Reference Laboratory for *E. coli*, on 3-5 October 2022 and on 23-25 November 2022. Both of them have been accomplished.

Two scientists signed up for the first training session. The methods applied were those proposed following the ranking exercise carried out in WP4, as well as the procedures applied at the EURL for *E. coli*. The training was organised with brief presentations from the ISS personnel, followed by hands-on sessions. The trainees were active and provided a positive feedback on the training, as stated through the administration of a training satisfaction survey. In particular, they both reported that the procedures applied during the training will likely be applied in their laboratory routine, highlighting the transfer of knowledge.

The second session of the training included the new procedures deployed for STEC detection in particular, as discussed in the session on WP4, trying to target the different subtypes and alleles of STEC detected in the procedures. This is in line with the continuous improvement of the harmonised procedures, supported by the OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium and according to the evolving scientific knowledge and the epidemiological picture linked to STEC infections. This session was held at ISS in Rome, and was carried out jointly by ISS and SSI personnel, supporting three trainees.

Moreover, a set of the OH-HARMONY-CAP procedures will be incorporated in the training session on the “detection and characterisation of pathogenic *E. coli*” held at the EURL for *E. coli*.

Training sessions on detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp.:

Two training sessions on the application of the harmonised procedures was held for detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium* spp. at ISS, at the European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites, on 3-5 October 2022 and on 23-25 November 2022.

The training provides for conventional microscopic detection by immunofluorescence (IFA), species identification and genotyping by two independent molecular methods (nested PCR). The three methods used have been selected on the basis of the “decision tree” developed in WP4. These methods represent the key points in the different workflows and can be applied directly on the most common matrix (stool) for the pathogen detection. The training consisted of a brief presentation on the theoretical aspects of *Cryptosporidium* spp. detection followed by the practical activity which focused on the execution “hands on” of the three methods. The three methods were also the subjects of three video tutorials that were distributed among the participants before their participation to the training. The training also includes a lecture on “*Cryptosporidium* genotyping” held by Karin Troell from the National Veterinary Institute SVA (Sweden).

During the second training session an updated version of the video tutorials was used based on suggestions and comments of participants at the first training.

Overall, the two sessions of training on *Cryptosporidium* saw the participation of 8 members of institutions of Harmony-CAP consortium. The harmonized protocols and the final version of the three tutorials will be released as e-learning tools and deployed after the completion of the second training course.

7.3 Project self-assessment

The OH-HARMONY-CAP consortium demonstrated impressive expertise and commitment. The work was consistently conducted in full collaboration and transparency. The project managed not only to deliver all the expected outputs, but also to include the publication of two scientific papers and an additional seven in preparation.

Much of this work involved stakeholders outside the EU demonstrating that harmonisation of laboratory methodology has an International dimension and that coordination on an International scale is of utmost importance. The extensive examination of possible new targets in the model organisms (STEC and ETEC) was primarily based on results obtained from the increasing number of WGS submissions to International databases such as NCBI and ENA. OH-HARMONY-CAP has thus contributed to an update of our knowledge of new emerging types of virulence genes and the need to keep laboratory methodology up to date. We would highly recommend that an EU body for the recommendation and standardisation of detection and characterisation of microorganisms in the Public Health sector is established, somewhat similar to FDA's Bacteriological Analytical Manual (BAM) <https://www.fda.gov/food/laboratory-methods-food/bacteriological-analytical-manual-bam>. Extensive differences related to the requirements for laboratory methods were observed between the PH and the AH/FS sectors. The recommendations and guidelines on an EU level for human clinical primary diagnostics is non-existing and characterised by a level of autonomy that can best be described as chaotic and random. Also, one major concern expressed by many of the participants was the absence of representatives from ECDC during this project. As a result, EU citizens are not guaranteed that adequate and updated laboratory methods specifying harmonised requirements are used across the EU.

Considerable data generated by the human, animal, food, feed and environmental testing laboratories throughout Europe are not reported to neither EFSA nor ECDC because this is not required under the current regulatory framework. These data are essential to provide the scientific basis for food safety policy development. The conceptual harmonised data reporting and management system will also address this issue and provide a user-friendly mechanism for harvesting this information.

OH-HARMONY-CAP has from the beginning focused on collaboration with EURLs and the PH-NRLs. This includes ongoing sharing of outputs and reports, allowing the opportunity for these stakeholders to suggest and comment on activities related to the OH-HARMONY-CAP project.

Originally, the development of the OHLabCap was divided into two pilot surveys targeting the National reference Laboratories (NRLs) and the primary diagnostic services. However, due to time constraints, it was determined, to combine the two pilot surveys into one pilot survey running Y3 followed by an adjusted survey, Y4. This early change prevented further delays. Also, one new and important observation that emerged during the analysis of the OHLabCap pilot survey was related to adaptability i.e., the capacity and ability to adjust preparedness, methodology and organisation of each laboratory. Year 2020 saw the coming of a new microorganism: The Covid-19 pandemic which illustrated that adaptability is more relevant than ever, and additional focus will be placed on adaptability in the development of the instrument.

In Y3, we identified a gap regarding sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programmes. Therefore, we included an additional deliverable, which surveyed this sector. We developed and launched an anonymous nine question survey distributed to the laboratories.

While discussing the results of the evaluation in WP4 (harmonization of protocols), the partners realized that they would not be able, sufficiently, to rank and compare the Cryptosporidium protocols. Given that protocols for Cryptosporidium detection are strictly dependent on the type of matrix to be tested. As such, they concluded on the need to build a questionnaire to be joined to the protocol request allowing a more precise evaluation of the methods. Consequently, recommending one harmonized method for cryptosporidium proved, scientifically, unfeasible. However, key processes have been defined and

methods of choice for each type of process have been assessed.

We had planned for the training on AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. to be held at SSI however, no one registered even though we had extended the deadline and sent out reminders. Note, WP4 also found no need to issue a unique procedure for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

Sustainability and implementation of protocols will depend on the abilities to adapt and implement the recommended protocols. Past experience suggests that this will happen over time and is often related to the ongoing proficiency testing and External Quality Assurance (EQA) programmes organised by EFSA and ECDC.

7.4 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

7.4.1 Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.1.1	Preliminary data management plan	M33	M36	This report is publically available https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-HARMONY-CAP	8
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2.1	Completed pilot survey	M36	M36	This report is publically available https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-HARMONY-CAP	1
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.1	Technical report on the current and best practice in sampling	M36	M36	https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-HARMONY-CAP	2, 4, 6

OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP.2.2	Technical report of the survey results	38	38	https://zenodo.org/record/4588483#.YJt4wldxc2w	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP.2.3	Adjusted survey	42	41	10.5281/zenodo.5464722	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP.3.2	List of methods used to characterise pathogens	48	48	https://zenodo.org/record/5788415#.Yf0PceqZNPY	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 2.5	Technical report: overview of the sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs	50	51	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6414920	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 3.3	A harmonised food safety data management system for Europe	57	56	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6899935	2, 4, 6

OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 4.3	Technical Report: Designing and Implementation of Harmonised Protocols for the Detection and Typing of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC), Enterotoxigenic Escherichia coli (EPEC), Cryptosporidium and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in Salmonella and Campylobacter spp. in the European Union	54	55	https://zenodo.org/record/7038212#.Y3NqaHbMKUk%20Doi:%2010.5281%2Fzenodo.7038212	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 5.1	Workshop: Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap	57	57	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7398691	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 5.2	Workshop: Joint workshop between CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX	57	57	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7398691	

OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 5.3	Training programs for the application of the harmonised protocols	54-59	54-59	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436595	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 5.4	E-learning modules on the application of the harmonised protocols	60	60	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434576 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434304 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434358	2, 4, 6
OH-HARMO NY-CAP	D-IA2.2.O H-HARMO NY-CAP 2.4	Integrated OneHealth Instrument	54	60	Completed. Will be public before December 31st	2, 4, 6

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

7.4.2 Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.1	Kick-off meeting completed	M25	M25	
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.2	WP3-T1-ST1 completed	M36	M36	
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.3	Preparing a list of methods for the detection, Characterisation and typing of the selected pathogens in the EU/EEA NRLs	M36	M36	
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.4	WP3-T1-ST2 completed	M36	M36	
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.5	WP3-T2 completed	M46	M46	
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.6	Assessing protocols for detection and typing of the selected foodborne pathogens	M39	M39	

JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-HARMONY-CAP.7	Delivery of practical workshops on the harmonised protocols	54-59	54-59	Four practical workshops have been held at 27-ISS. The workshop at 13-SSI on AMR was cancelled as no one signed up.
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-HARMONY-CAP.8	Delivery of e-learning sessions on the harmonised protocols	60	60	

7.5 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Characterization of Clinical <i>Escherichia coli</i> Strains Producing a Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtype in Sweden and Denmark https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6630847 https://zenodo.org/record/6630847#.Y43h43aZOUk		Yes	November 17 th , 2021	
Characterisation of atypical Shiga toxin gene sequences and description of Stx2j, a new subtype. <i>J Clin Microbiol</i> 2022 Mar 16;60(3):e0222921. doi: 10.1128/jcm.02229-21 https://zenodo.org/record/6637837#.YxHBTXbP2Uk . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6637837		Yes	March 16 th , 2022	
Flemming Scheutz, Camilla Hald Nielsen, Astrid von Mentzer. Construction of the ETECFinder database for the characterisation of enterotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (ETEC) and revision of the <i>VirulenceFinder</i> webtool at the CGE website.	In preparation	Yes		
Flemming Scheutz, David W. Lacher, Jorge Blanco, William Klimke, William Klimke, Julie Haendiges, Daniel Haft, Michael Feldgarden and Narjol Gonzalez-Escalona. Sequence-based analysis of intimin (<i>eae</i>) genes and standardizing <i>eae</i> nomenclature for subtyping of <i>eae</i> and for detection by PCR.	In preparation	Yes		
Rebecca Lindsey, Bill Klimke, Mike Feldgarden, Curtis Kapsak, Jenny Truong, Angela Melton-Celsa, Peyton Smith, Heather Harbottle, and Narjol Gonzalez-Escalona. Identification and Characterization of <i>Escherichia coli</i> Strains Producing Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtypes, Stx2n and Stx2o in the United States.	In preparation	Yes		
Microbiological sampling and analyses in the food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes. Mariel Stephanie Aybar Espinoza, Catarina Flink, Nadia Boisen, Flemming Scheutz, Annemarie Käsbohrer	Submitted to <i>Frontiers in Food Science</i>	Yes		

	and Technolog y, section Food Safety and Quality Control			
An update of A method for fast and simple detection of major diarrhoeagenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> in the routine diagnostic laboratory	In preparatio n	Yes		
Epidemiology of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. infection in Portugal over a 12-year period (provisional title; M. Oleastro)	In preparatio n	Yes		
Antibiotic resistance and molecular characterization of pathogenic <i>E. coli</i> and non-typhoidal <i>Salmonella</i> in pets (provisional title; A. Pista, L. Silveira)	In preparatio n	Yes		
Characterization and antibiotic resistance and molecular characterization of pathogenic <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> spp. in food-producing animals (provisional title; A. Pista, L. Silveira)	In preparatio n	Yes		

7.6 Additional output

- Podcast with Flemming Scheutz on the Danish broadcasting company on types of *E. coli*.
- The Annual general peoples meeting on the Island of Bornholm with approximately 120,000 guests, decisionmakers and politicians. Two workshops on the detection of foodborne outbreaks.
- General communication

7.7 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

The development of the first OHLabCap tool is in itself a major achievement, which is open for adaptation by other key stakeholders in the OH field such as FAO and WHO, who are conducting similar surveys. The inclusion of private food operators and laboratories in the mini survey of this project is – to our knowledge - the first of its kind and could potentially represent an improvement in the communication between the private sector and One Health authorities. Both parties could benefit from the results. The involvement of these stakeholders could in return serve as inspiration for the further development of tools intended to measure the dimensions and targets in the OHLabCap tool (D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.4, M54).

The e-learning sessions represents an important outcome, being available also for a large public far beyond the project's participants. These video documents will be published, among others, on the OH-HARMONY-CAP website to ensure the maximum dissemination of the contents and impacting in the transfer of knowledge to a larger scientific community.

Finally, all the work packages have underlined the importance of being able to adjust and adapt to the ongoing and ever-changing challenges in the field of microbiology.

7.8 Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

We have had a close collaboration with Center for Vaccine Development, USA and Uniformed Services University of the Health sciences, MD, USA. They have both tested and implemented the omni primers for the detection of *Stx1*, *Stx2*, and *eae* which was developed as part of WP4. We have communicated to the consortium, that the primers are available and we plan on publishing the final multiplex PCR method as soon as possible. Notably, there will be no impact without the implementation of the new protocols.

7.9 One Health impact

The OHLabcap has revealed some of the gaps and short comings of the competences in the surveyed One Health laboratories. However, we have also provided recommendations on how to address this.

The results of OH-HARMONY-CAP can improve One Health interoperability across NRLs on three target areas: Sampling & testing, strain characterisation, and data management & harmonised reporting. By identifying gaps, the project supports best practices to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. Surveillance strategies can then be adjusted based on the developed guidance for improvement of One Health interoperability across NRLs.

The proposed harmonised procedures will have an impact, as they will not only be the subject of training sessions, but also represent methodologies available to the scientific community through the dissemination of the OH-HARMONY-CAP results. Moreover, the strategy designed for ranking protocols

can represent a tool that may be applied, following ad hoc re-modulation, for the definition of fit-for-purpose procedures for microorganisms other than those considered in this project.

Harmonised application of the most appropriate methods for sampling and testing food, feed, environmental and human samples, standard characterisation priorities and methods complemented by effective data management and reporting systems would ensure reliable data is readily available to EFSA, FAO, etc. support food safety guidance and policy in the EU and worldwide. These methods include digital PCR and WGS. The high discriminatory power of WGS, for example, would greatly enhance foodborne outbreak investigation including source-attribution and facilitate earlier identification of emerging threats. More widespread application of WGS would also provide considerably more information about antibiotic resistance determinants and their dissemination, thus facilitating a more accurate assessment of the success of otherwise current strategies aimed at reducing AMR development and spread between bacterial populations.

7.10 Data Management Plan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436715>

7.11 Future dissemination activities

- It is expected that several posters will be presented at VTEC 2023 to be held in Banff, Canada 7th to 10th of May 2023, www.vtec2023.org.
- International networking with NRLs will continue in order to maintain and develop current knowledge on emerging and new types
- The developed protocols will be recommended and tested by the EURL and network. They will also be circulated to the participants in the ECDC funded EQA programmes. It is expected that the stakeholders will pick up this outcome and use it.

Reference list

1. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Public health preparedness capabilities: national standards for state and local planning. Atlanta, Georgia, USA: CDC; 2011 [109-18]. Available from: https://www.cdc.gov/phpr/readiness/00_docs/DSLRCapabilitiesJuly.pdf
2. Witt-Kushner J, Astles JR, Ridderhof JC, Martin RA, Wilcke B, Downes FP, et al. Core functions and capabilities of state public health laboratories: a report of the association of public health laboratories. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (MMWR)*. 2002 September 20;51(RR14):1-8.

8. JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX

Important note

During the annual review of the One Health European Joint Programme for 2021, external reviewers misinterpreted the MATRIX Annual Report for Year 4 (2021). In the part related to the possible risks of the project, they erroneously stated: “*there were delays in the deliverables for the 2nd round of JIPs largely attributable to the COVID pandemic, but particularly noticeable for the MATRIX project at only 17% which reported that there were issues of lack of commitment and conflicts between partners*”.

This statement is incorrect and the MATRIX Annual Report for Year 4 (2021) reported the opposite (Part 7. List of critical risks, page 28): “No conflict, lack of commitment, poor relationships or other negative experience has been reported”. Moreover, no deliverable was late on 31/12/2021, as per the agreed deadlines. The OHEJP Coordination acknowledged this mistake in October 2022.

The Joint Integrative Project MATRIX never experienced any lack of commitment or any conflicts among the partners in the project. Additionally, no deliverable was ever delayed beyond the deadlines of the work plan and its amendments.

8.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

JIP05-MATRIX (here below MATRIX) was an EU-co-funded project within the framework of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP). It aimed to advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in European countries, by identifying and extending existing cross-sectoral programmes including animal health (AH), public health (PH) and food safety (FS). By the end of 2022, 19 partner institutes from 12 European countries constituted the MATRIX Consortium.

MATRIX created solutions for European countries to support and advance the implementation of OHS, also known as the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**. They are:

- OH-EpiCap Tool – an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS of a hazard of choice, identifying strengths and opportunities for improvement. Additionally, the tool allows the benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities for comparison. More information is available here: [OH-EpiCap tool flyer](#) and [OH-EpiCap tool user guide](#).
- Roadmap to develop national OHS – a guideline that countries can use to develop OHS according to their needs and resources. The roadmap expanded the work of the OHEJP COHESIVE project and is available at <https://www.ohras.eu/page/home> – copy-paste this link in your browser.
- Manual for OHS Dashboards – an online dashboard inventory and practical manual to facilitate the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open-source tools. More information is available here: [Dashboard Information Centre](#).
- Guidelines and checklists:
 - An interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems. A beta version is available [here](#).
 - Best-practices to operationalize cross-sectoral collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results – available [here](#).

- A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards – available [here](#).

MATRIX also promoted and expanded:

- [The OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform](#) – a framework to integrate various resources that help to implement OHS in all sectors.
- [Food Safety Knowledge Exchange \(FSKX\) Format](#) – a format that supports the One Health community in sharing and re-using mathematical models as well as data analysis procedures.

The problem-oriented approach of the project was reflected in the creation of hazard-specific tracks (HT) to ensure that the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* were relevant to specific pathogens. In actuality, MATRIX meant “a frame of solutions and hazards”. The hazards were chosen based on the operational priorities of MATRIX partner institutes and their One Health relevance. They were *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance (AMR), viruses and parasites.

MATRIX invited European institutes working in the AH, PH and FS sectors to consider the opportunity to adopt these solutions and to further build upon them. In addition to the manifold initiatives that project partners and WP leaders took to further disseminate their work, the MATRIX Consortium organized and delivered a series of seven webinars, [the Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars](#) in 2022, to present the project’s outcomes.

The [MATRIX webpage](#) provides a complete list of the project achievements and outputs.

8.2 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1 Existing frameworks and OH capacity

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T1 Generate an inventory of existing frameworks for surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards, by sector (AH, PH, and FS) – M25-36 – This task was completed and the related deliverable *D-WP1.1 Report on the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in Animal Health (AH), Public Health (PH), and Food Safety (FS)* was submitted as per deadline in M36. The related report was then updated in Year 4 (June 2021) with new available evidence from MATRIX partner institutes, and made public via the Zenodo platform.

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T2 Generate suggestions for adaptation of existing frameworks into a common sectorial framework (AH, PH, FS) which can support surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards (OHS) – M37-54 – The objective of this task was to provide recommendations in the form of a guideline to adapt existing sectorial frameworks into one common system for AH, PH and FS. The task performed a comprehensive review of existing OHS systems, based on interviews of persons executing existing OHS systems, scientific literature and the hazard-specific experiences of MATRIX partners and other institutes outside of the project’s Consortium.

The task focussed exclusively on data mechanics, by which we mean the flow of data from collection through to database storage, then analysis and finally interpretation. Data from MATRIX WP1-T1, a literature review, qualitative interviews (Table 1), and expert solicitation from the MATRIX consortium informed the guideline development. As part of the literature review task, we systematically searched the available scientific and grey literature for articles relating to One Health and surveillance (more details on search terms can be provided). Papers (n=1590) were then screened by a pre-defined and prescriptive process to identify suitable candidates for data extraction. Data pertinent to the guidelines were extracted from the selected literature. For each selected paper, if a clear OHS system was identifiable, details of a contact were collected in anticipation of inclusion in the interview task described next. We then deepened our understanding of factors that support successful

implementation of OHS systems from existing frameworks, by conducting qualitative interviews with representatives of existing or previously existing systems. An interview guide was developed and interviews started in March 2022.

In addition, MATRIX partner institutes shared information on existing OHS systems, with a focus on relevant hazards (*Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, emerging threats, including AMR), and the mechanics of data flow. This work was conducted in close collaboration with MATRIX WP5 (literature review), MATRIX WP4 (interviews), MATRIX WP2 (guidelines). This task provided the content of deliverable D-WP1.2 *Description of a common framework for One Health surveillance* (delivered in M54).

Table 1. Completed interviews of OHS systems, 30 July 2022

Country	Pathogen(s) under surveillance	Interview Status	Sector represented by interviewee(s)
Italy	<i>West Nile Virus</i>	Completed	Animal Health
Austria	<i>West Nile Virus</i>	Completed	Animal Health
France	<i>Salmonella</i>	Completed	Food Safety
England	AMR	Completed	Animal Health
Tanzania	Zoonotic pathogens	Completed	Animal Health
The Netherlands	Zoonotic pathogens	Completed	Human Health
Norway	<i>Listeria</i>	Completed	Food Safety
Portugal	<i>Teania</i> spp (Cystercercosis)	Completed	Human Health

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T3 Evaluation of the sectoral frameworks, for specific inter-sectoral hazards – M49-60 – This task completed the work initiated in the previous task where we produced an interactive guide to adapt existing AH, PH and FS surveillance frameworks into multi-sectoral systems. This task ensured the development and testing of the aforementioned interactive guide. We organized a series of case studies where participating countries among the project partners evaluated the applicability and suitability of the common framework for developing OHS. The MATRIX HTs served as the case studies, but upon interest in specific countries, further hazards were evaluated. Problems identified in the process were evaluated, and the sectoral frameworks adapted and modified. Case studies included *Salmonella* in Germany, *Campylobacter* in Niedersachsen (Germany) and psittacosis in Denmark. This task also provided the content of deliverable D-WP1.3 *Report on the evaluation of the common framework using examples within the consortium* (delivered in M58).

The interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems is available [here](#) (beta version).

WP2 Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T1 Mapping of the surveillance chain across all sectors for each hazard-track – M25-35 – The mapping started in Year 3 (2020) and continued in Year 4 (2021), since additional countries were involved at a later stage. Per each HT, including Hepatitis E (chosen as the emerging pathogen of interest), a specific food chain was selected to explore the different realities in detail. Twelve online questionnaires were implemented based on the “farm to fork” approach for the three sectors (AH, PH and FS) and each hazard-food chain combination. Surveillance activities in place were investigated in at least two countries for each combination. *Salmonella* was investigated in humans and pork meat; *Listeria* in humans and dairy products; *Campylobacter* in humans and poultry meat; Hepatitis E in humans and wild boar meat. Answers were categorized and graphically displayed in terms of events, actors, data, metadata, event producing data, identified data sources, and sharing potential. Categorized answers represented the starting point for the identification of cross-sectorial linkages across surveillance chains. The following countries and hazards were investigated (Figure 1):
i) *Salmonella* in humans and pork meat, in France, Spain, Germany, Norway and the United Kingdom;
ii) *Listeria* in humans and dairy products, in Norway and Italy; iii) *Campylobacter* in humans and

poultry meat, in France, Norway and Germany; iv) Hepatitis E in humans and wild boar meat, in Portugal, the Netherlands, Italy and Norway. Results from this task were regularly presented at Consortium and WP specific meetings, and contributed to the work of MATRIX WP1, WP3 and WP4. The task and its related deliverable (*D-WP2.1 - Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages* – delivered in M48 because attached to WP2-T2) were completed.

Figure 1. Hazard track, selected food chain combinations, and countries that participated to the JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T1

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T2 Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, particularly, which outputs should be shared and how they should be shared for OH orientated decision making – M30-48 –

Building on the work done and the information collected about maps of integrated hazard-food surveillance chains in MATRIX WP2-T1 during Year 3 (2020), this task identified cross-sectorial linkages for integrated OHS systems. A workshop was conducted among MATRIX partners to explore the dynamics of information sharing among sectors. The workshop explored the following hazards and countries: i) *Salmonella* in Germany and France; ii) *Listeria* in Norway and the Netherlands; iii) *Campylobacter* in Sweden and Denmark; iv) Hepatitis E in Italy; v) Sars-CoV-2 in the United Kingdom. An outcome to highlight was that information was mainly shared during outbreaks in all participating countries, and that information including datasets are not publicly available resources in some countries. The results of the workshop also informed the purposes of MATRIX WP2-T3, WP5-T1 and WP5-T2. Case studies were developed based on the findings of MATRIX WP2-T1, WP2-T2 and the related hazard-country combinations. The deliverable *D-WP2.1 Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages* was originally expected in M36 and was postponed to M42 during Year 3 (2020). In May 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 6 months to December 2021 (M48), which was granted. *D-WP2.1 - Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages* was finalized as per the deadline in M48.

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T3 Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis, and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial OH collaboration, for each specific hazard-track – M33-54 –

This task developed hazard-specific best practices for multi-sectorial collaboration and put OHS into practice. A format was defined to document best practices for data collection, data sharing, data analysis and interpretation, and the communication of results, for three different surveillance purposes: i) measure the levels and temporal trends of exposure and burden of disease; ii) support early detection and response to outbreaks; iii) identify risk factors to implement control measures. A document providing general information on the context and contents was finalized, which included four table-type attachments, one per sector (data collection, data sharing, data analysis, communication of results). In each table, the sector was split into aspects, features, and steps, where relevant general and hazard-specific annotations are gathered. This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP2.2 Suggested*

best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks) (delivered in M54).

The lessons learned harnessed from the activities in this WP contributed to the following: i) writing a scientific manuscript (see below Section 7); ii) organizing one webinar of the ***Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022***, together with MATRIX HTs; iii) contributing to organize the OHEJP WP5 Dissemination Workshop, Improving One Health Preparedness to (re)emerging infectious threats in March 2022.

The best-practices to operationalize cross-sectoral collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results are available [here](#).

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T4 Identify commonalities across the tracks, to propose a common OHS framework when applicable – M46-60 – This task summarized the information collected by previous tasks, particularly MATRIX WP2-T1, in which surveillance chain maps were constructed per HT, and MATRIX WP2-T3, in which hazard-specific best practices for multi-sectoral collaboration were explored and described. Within this task, we created a map of commonalities across countries for each of the HTs (excluding emerging threats), and then from there, further summarised the hazard specific maps to develop one, overall common OHS framework. This common map transcended hazards and country specific contexts, laying out a backbone for OHS based upon current systems across Europe. The common framework is not to be interpreted as a one size fits all solution, but rather a starting point for the design and development of an OHS system of any zoonotic hazard in any European country. Additionally, the common OHS framework includes a summarised list of best practices (based upon those from MATRIX *D-WP2.2*), which also transcend the HTs and gives general advice regarding data collection, sharing, analysis and interpretation.

This task provided the content for deliverable *D-WP2.3 Common framework of OHS* (delivered in M58) and summarized the results of activities conducted under MATRIX WP2.

WP3 Output-based surveillance evaluation

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T1 Inventory of previous work and current practice – M25-36 – MATRIX WP3 was impacted by the turnover of key personnel during 2020, including the WP leader. Therefore, activities related to this task continued to be implemented until the end of Year 4 (2021). No deliverable was attached to this task. A review of evidence (both peer-reviewed and grey literature) about output-based surveillance within the three sectors AH, PH and FS informed the work of other tasks in the WP.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T2 Identification of operational partners and stakeholders – M25-60 – The originally planned stakeholder mapping exercise was postponed due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and Avian Influenza outbreak, as this WP was primarily implemented by partners working in the AH sector. However, this task spanned the entire duration of MATRIX and the postponement did not affect its outcome. A specific case study about *Echinococcus multilocularis* was set up and conducted. This task used input from the RISKSUR project (about risk-based surveillance systems) and from the COHESIVE project (about stakeholder mapping). No deliverable was attached to this task.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T3 Selection of appropriate output-based surveillance systems – M37-54 – Participating partners identified appropriate output-based methodologies according to the specific objective of the surveillance system they have selected i.e. *Salmonella* in layer flocks (21-APHA), *Salmonella* in pigs (41-SVA), *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle (University of Copenhagen), SARS-CoV-2 in companion animals (31-WBVR) and *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red fox and stray dog populations (34-PIWET). This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP3.1 Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible* (delivered in M54).

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T4 Development of evaluation strategies for surveillance systems based on output-based metrics – M40-60 – This task looked at strategies to evaluate the effectiveness of output-based surveillance systems within the three sectors: AH, PH and FS. The work was also postponed in consequence of previous tasks. Participating partners reviewed the appropriate output metrics that were used to develop a country-specific standard for evaluation. Deliverable *D-WP3.2 Combined report for all subtasks within the development of output-based metrics* (delivered in M58) incorporated and summarised i) the inventory of previous work (based on a literature review); ii) the stakeholder mapping and iii) the development of evaluation strategies. The deliverable comprised of a non-prescriptive guideline for conducting output-based surveillance regarding current practices, stakeholder engagement and evaluation strategies. It took the form of a guidance manual (not best practices) and was a combined report for all other tasks from MATRIX WP3.

The guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards is available [here](#).

WP4 Benchmarking tool for characterising, monitoring and evaluating OH capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap)¹

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T1 Review of existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation – M25-39 – This task was postponed during Year 3 (2020), with the expected deliverable finalized as per plans in M39: *D-WP4.1 Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities for One Health surveillance*. The task reviewed existing One Health evaluation tools, identifying indicators that are common across the different tools. Inspired by the EU-LabCap approach, the EU-EpiCap tool is structured with three dimensions and four targets per dimension. During the MATRIX Consortium meeting held in Berlin, Germany in March 2022, it was agreed to change the name of the tool from EU-EpiCap to OH-EpiCap tool. This change was operated: to highlight the One Health approach of the tool; to be more inclusive of non-EU countries that are also represented in the MATRIX Consortium and co-fund the project; to align with the OH-LabCap survey that is developed by the JIP OH-Harmony-Cap.

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T2 Development of the surveillance capacity benchmarking tool – M37-54 – Building on MATRIX WP4-T1, a questionnaire was defined, with a scoring system, to evaluate a system's OHS capacities and capabilities against a specific hazard. An R Shiny-based interface was also developed to deploy the tool and automatically generate synthetic country profile report, as well as explore outcomes through various visualization options. The second iteration of this interface is available at <https://freddietafreeth.shinyapps.io/OH-EpiCap/>

A tutorial was created (https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/OHEJP_MATRIX_OH-EpiCap_user_guide_2022_06.pdf) to explain how to use the tool. The tool was reviewed by the MATRIX consortium and experts in One Health and multi-sectoral surveillance, including experts from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP4.2 OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial* (delivered in M54), as well as a publication currently under review.

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T3 Application and evaluation of the tool – M49-60 – The OH-EpiCap tool and the questionnaire were piloted with AMR in Portugal and France, *Salmonella* in Germany, the Netherlands and France, *Campylobacter* in Norway and Sweden, *Listeria* in Finland, the Netherlands and Norway, and psittacosis in Denmark. Based on these results, we highlighted the common strengths and barriers to One Health in existing multi-sectoral surveillance systems. We also provided some recommendations for improving the OHS capacities and capabilities based on the solutions developed in the MATRIX and JIP COHESIVE projects, as well as from the literature. This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP4.3 Report on the implementation of the OH-EpiCap evaluation tool on several studies cases* (delivered in M58). The title of the deliverable was changed to include all study cases. A manuscript for

¹ During the MATRIX Consortium meeting held in Berlin, Germany in March 2022, it was agreed to change the name of the tool from EU-EpiCap to OH-EpiCap tool.

publication was finalized with the objective to evaluate the tool. In addition, in the framework of the CoEvalAMR project, the tool was applied to AMR surveillance systems in several countries and the tool itself was also evaluated.

WP5 Outreach and roadmap

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T1 Perform a requirement analysis for national OH surveillance roadmaps – M25-51 – An initial workshop, which included MATRIX WP1, WP2, and WP4 leaders and HT leaders, was conducted in April 2021 to discuss various inputs and ideas for the requirement analysis and the roadmap. The requirement analysis aimed to investigate barriers and facilitators to OHS implementation at the national level and aided in the development of a national OHS roadmap. The requirement analysis included: i) a review of OHEJP deliverables and outputs including JIP COHESIVE, JIP ORION, JRP NOVA, and other MATRIX WPs; ii) a focused systematic literature review following the PRISMA reporting methodology; iii) an analysis of user stories collected from the participants in the MATRIX WP2.2 workshop that took place in October 2021. Deliverable *D-WP5.1 Report on requirement analysis for “OHS roadmap template”* was originally expected in M45. In May 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 3 months to December 2021 (M48), which was granted. Then, in October 2021, MATRIX requested to postpone it by 3 additional months to March 2022 (M51), which was granted. The task and its related deliverable (D-WP5.1) were completed in M51 as per the updated Annual Work Plan (AWP) Year 5.

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T2 Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap – M37-60 – In late 2021, MATRIX identified additional synergies with the JIP COHESIVE on the topic of OHS roadmaps and the two projects strengthened their collaboration and exchanges. Accordingly, the activities of the WP5-T2 were adapted (see the updated AWP Year 5). MATRIX evaluated and further developed the roadmap developed by JIP COHESIVE (<https://www.ohras.eu/> – copy-paste this link in your browser). The first three steps of the roadmap were piloted and Systems Thinking workshops were conducted in Sweden and Denmark during spring 2022. The webpage and guidelines of the roadmap were updated considering the results of the requirement analysis (MATRIX WP5-T1), and results/solutions from other WPs that could contribute to different steps of the roadmap. User stories from workshops performed in Sweden, Denmark and Norway were also included. This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP5.2 OHS roadmap template document* (delivered in M58).

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T3 Knowledge-Integration Platform – M25-60 – A Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) was established on the basis of the OHS Codex, which was developed in the JIP ORION project. This work resulted in what is today known as the “OHS Codex: The Knowledge integration platform” (OHS Codex/KIP, <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). The following extensions/changes were implemented to the original platform as developed by JIP ORION:

- Extended the scope and purpose of the OHS CODEX/KIP; updated the existing principles; added a new principle that focuses on surveillance planning and management;
- Created new sections for training materials and examples for OHS reports; added trainings under the Dissemination section; added a new section about the use of the OHS CODEX/KIP;
- Synchronized wording/keywords from the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (added specific keywords to the principles);
- Optimized search engine results;
- Added a description of the MATRIX project in the introduction of the OHS Codex/KIP; added MATRIX as funding;
- Adapted colour and style to the OHEJP design templates; added OHEJP logo to the heading; created a new logo of the OHS CODEX/KIP.

Changes have been implemented in the public Read-the-Docs version of the OHS Codex/KIP.

In 2022, MATRIX partners agreed on integrating all of the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* into the OHS Codex/KIP. The OHS Codex/KIP also aims to raise awareness of the work achieved by other OHEJP projects (e.g. OHEJP Outcome Inventory) and to create synergies with other initiatives relevant for the One Health community, such as the Surveillance and Information Sharing (SIS) Operational Tool (OT) developed by Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH, former OIE) and the World Health Organization (WHO). The OHS Codex/KIP is today included in the toolbox of the [Surveillance and information sharing operational tool \(SIS OT\)](#) : an operational tool of the tripartite zoonoses guide, by FAO, WOAH and WHO.

Within the MATRIX WP5-T3, MATRIX partners also contributed to the adoption of the harmonized information exchange format FSKX (see <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fskx-food-safety-knowledge-exchange-format/>) that allows the efficient exchange of mathematical models across One Health sectors. In June 2022, two dissemination activities took place to promote the adoption of the FSKX format by One Health professionals and modellers (see *JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination* here below). Furthermore, during 2022 several new models for *Campylobacter* (download at: [single-hit dose-response](#), [exposure model](#) and [population risk model](#)) were provided as FSKX files. Further, a dose-response model of *Campylobacter jejuni* and a source attribution model for salmonellosis were implemented and published in FSKX format. Both models are available in the Food and Ecological Systems Modelling Journal (FESMJ) where they can be downloaded and executed online (<https://fmj.pensoft.net/article/63309/>; <https://fmj.pensoft.net/article/70008/>). In addition, MATRIX partners 45-ROAKA and 9-BfR contributed to the extension of the FSKX format towards additional model classes relevant in different One Health sectors. This work will be integrated into the next release of the FSKX format specification. Partner 33-NVI explored applying the FSKX format to annotate/share IRIDIA sequencing pipelines: the general approach proved to be useful, but some modifications on the FSKX format need to be implemented before it can be widely applied in pipelines for bioinformatics. Dedicated workshops were organized in October 2021 to introduce the tools that support the use of the FSKX format, e.g. the RAKIP-Web Model Repository (<https://knime.bfr.berlin/landingpage/RAKIP-Model-Repository>) and the FSK-Lab software (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-lab/>). New training materials (videos, manuals and tutorials) were created and made available under the 9-BfR eLearning platform <https://bfr-elearning.de/> (Username: fsk-workshop21, Password: Matrix.2110).

MATRIX project partner 9-BfR also added new features and content to the open Food Safety Model Repository (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/openfsmr/>) that helps to disseminate the knowledge on food safety models available within different software tools in the One Health community. Finally, 13-SSI and 45-RUOKA became members of the [RAKIP Initiative](#), which was founded by 9-BfR, 12-DTU Food and 1-ANSES, ensuring the long term maintenance of the FSKX format and the development of supporting software resources. No deliverable was attached to this task.

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination – M25-60 – MATRIX partners contributed to the enrichment of the opportunities for training and dissemination, which were planned in frequent task-specific meetings. No deliverable was attached to this task.

List of conducted training and dissemination activities in 2020, 2021 and 2022

Year 3 (2020)

OHS Briefings e.g. webinars/meetings informing about OHS initiatives and projects; actively involving OHEJP stakeholders
Presentation – 28 Apr 2020 – OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop 5 with JPIAMR – Introduction about MATRIX
Presentation – 27-29 May 2020 – OHEJP 2020 Annual Scientific Meeting – Presentation about MATRIX WP5
Poster – 30 Oct to 3 Nov 2020 – World One Health Congress – Poster about MATRIX WP5 work
Presentation – 6 Nov 2020 – National, 9-BfR-internal pilot – Berlin, Germany and online
Presentation – 25 Nov 2020 – OHEJP Cogwheel workshop – Introduction on MATRIX Cogwheel Workshop 6 with SafeConsume

Year 4 (2021)

Presentation – Jan 2021 – EJP Discover stakeholder meeting – Introduction to MATRIX
Presentation – Jan 2021 – SafeConsume-ORION-MATRIX meeting – One Health Surveillance Codex/KIP – additional communication in April 2021
WP6 presentation – 03 Mar 2021 – Introduction to WP6 and preparation for the full consortium meeting – Gustafsson 41-SVA
WP6 presentation – 25 Mar 2021 – Presentation of the Norwegian One Health website Sykdomspulsen – Grøneng, White 32-FHI/NIPH – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/MatrixWP6_25032021.pdf
WP6 presentation – 28 Apr 2021 – Possible activities for outreach, dashboard platform discussion – Gustafsson 41-SVA
Presentation – May 2021 – 13-SSI (Denmark) OHEJP activity meeting – MATRIX Work Plan – Benedetti
Abstract – May 2021 – ARPHA Conference Abstracts 4:e68820 – An interactive online IT tool to aim the environmental surveillance of veterinary antibiotics in agriculture and pasture lands – Rodríguez, de la Torre 16-INIA – available at: https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68820
Presentation – 7-8 Jun 2021 – ASM Satellite Workshop. Virtual meeting – An interactive online IT tool to aim the environmental surveillance of veterinary antibiotics in agriculture and pasture lands – Rodríguez, de la Torre 16-INIA
Presentation – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting ² – MATRIX WP5 related work: “Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format: a Flexible Exchange Format for (Joined) Models in the Area of Food Safety and One Health” – Sundermann 9-BfR
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – GIS as a tool for mapping Salmonella serovars in pigs in Poland between 2014-2018 – Ziętek-Barszcz 34-PIWET
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – Building political will for One Health risk analysis systems – Nordeng 32-FHI/NIPH
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – Evolving at the speed of risk – Kausrud 33-NVI
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – Mapping the surveillance activities for food-hazards across Europe – Cito 28-IZSAM
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – Food surveillance data on <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> in Spain (2016-2018): Spatial visualization and descriptive analysis – Rodríguez 16-INIA
Poster – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting – Analyses of environmental factors associated with the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in wild boars (<i>Sus scrofa</i>): A generic data pipeline approach – Günther, Kramer-Schadt, Fuhrmann, Belik 9-BfR

² MATRIX team members supported the organization of the OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting in June 2021.

WP6 Presentation – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop Software Fair – Sykdomspulsen One Health – A real time surveillance system in an infrastructure coping with half a million analysis a day – Koren, White 32-FHI/NIPH – abstract available at: https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68891
Presentation – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop Software Fair – Kausrud 33-NVI
Presentation – Jun 2021 – OHEJP 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop Software Fair – Sundermann 9-BfR
WP6 presentation – 23 Jun 2021 – Making linked data accessible for One Health Surveillance with the One Health Linked Data Toolbox – Günther, Filter 9-BfR – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/MATRIX_The-OH-EJP-LOD-Toolbox_TG_230621.pdf
Presentation – 25 Aug 2021 – One Health Session of the ECDC EPIET/EUPHEM Fellowship Project Review Module – Co-chairing, participation in the related round table and presentation about the MATRIX project and integrated One Health Surveillance – Benedetti 13-SSI
Presentation – 7-10 Sep 2021 – XXXIX Reunión Anual de la Sociedad Española de Epidemiología. XVI Congreso de la Asociación Portuguesa de Epidemiología. León (España). Gaceta Sanitaria vol 35 pp226,supp congreso. ISSN:0213-9111 – Análisis espacial y de factores de riesgo de zoonosis aviares en base a la bioseguridad de las explotaciones avícolas – Rodríguez, de la Torre, Aznar, Tablada, Iglesias – 16-INIA
WP6 presentation – 23 Sep 2021 – Designing a One Health website: Tips for user-friendliness and visual appeal – Koren 32-FHI/NIPH – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/2021_09_23_MATRIX_presentation_userfriendliness_Clemence_Koren.pdf
Presentation – Oct 2021 – JIP CARE Consortium meetings – MATRIX Work Plan – Benedetti 13-SSI
Presentation – Oct 2021 – 39th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses monitoring data – One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a framework for harmonization of surveillance data reports – Lopez de Abechuco, Filter 9-BfR
Presentation – Oct 2021 – International Symposium on Zoonoses Research Online – Environmental factors associated with the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in wild boars (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) – Zoonoses 2021 – Günther, Kramer-Schadt, Fuhrmann, Belik 9-BfR
WP5 Workshop – 12 Oct 2021 – Food Safety Knowledge eXchange (FSKX) format and RAKIP Model Repository Workshop – Lopez de Abechuco, Filter, Ganas, Mesa Varona 9-BfR
WP5 Workshop – 19 Oct 2021 - FSKX & Food Safety Knowledge Lab (FSK-Lab) workshop, Lopez de Abechuco, Filter, Ganas, Mesa Varona 9-BfR
WP6 workshop – 28 Oct 2021– Co-analysing One Health data: considerations, pitfalls and biases – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/data/
Presentation – Nov 2021 – JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP Consortium meeting – MATRIX EU-Epi-Cap tool – Prada 23-UoS (WP4)
Presentation – Nov 2021 – 13-SSI (Denmark) OHEJP activity meeting – Promoting the FSKX format use at Statens Serum Institut (Denmark) – Nauta, Benedetti 13-SSI
Poster (WP6) – Nov 2021 – One Health in the 21st century 2021 conference – “Forecasting human gastrointestinal outbreaks in Norway with <i>Campylobacter</i> broiler farm surveillance data and results dissemination to health authorities” – Swanson, Koren, Hopp, Jonsson, Grøneng – available at: https://www.med.uio.no/helsam/english/research/centres/global-health/news-and-events/events/global-health-and-the-2030-agenda/2021/national-one-health-conference-2021-.html
WP6 presentation – 25 Nov 2021– One Health forecasting of gastrointestinal illness with <i>Campylobacter</i> broiler farm surveillance – Swanson 32-FHI/NIPH

Year 5 (2022)

WP6 presentation – 24 Feb 2022 – Presentation about the COHESIVE Information System – Di Pasquale 28-IZSAM – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/20220224_cohesive-system.pdf
Workshop – 25 Mar 2022 – OHEJP WP5 Dissemination Workshop, Improving One Health Preparedness to (re)emerging infectious threats <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cito, Amato – Mapping existing surveillance chains at country level (WP2)• Hénaux, Prada – How to assess capacity to perform One Health surveillance? (WP4)
Poster – 11-13 Apr 2022 – One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 – BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS TO ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE AT THE NATIONAL LEVEL IN EUROPE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE (WP5) – Eves et al.
Poster – 11-13 April 2022 – One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 – A PRACTICAL MANUAL FOR ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE DASHBOARDS (WP6) – Gustafsson, Grøneng – Available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/ASM_poster_Wp6.pdf
WP6 presentation – 19 Apr 2022 – Presentation about the work behind the Danish COVID-19 dashboard – Dibba White 13-SSI – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/Dashboards_connecting_people_2022.04.19.pdf
Poster – 27-28 Apr 2022 – Greifswald One Health Conference 2022 – An inventory of zoonotic and food borne disease surveillance systems: expanding and understanding the One Health knowledge base (WP1)
Poster – 03-05 May 2022 – International conference on animal health surveillance (ICAHS) – OH-EpiCap: a semi quantitative tool for the evaluation of One Health Surveillance capacities and capabilities (WP4) – Tegegne et al.
Poster – 03-05 May 2022 – International conference on animal health surveillance (ICAHS) – Evaluating the capacities and capabilities of a One Health Surveillance system is feasible: a case study on psittacosis in Denmark (WP4) – Lefèvre et al.
Webinar – 19 May 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – OH-EpiCap tool – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below
Seminar – 25 May 2022 – One Health seminar: a workshop for One Health stakeholders where the results from MATRIX WP6 were presented – MATRIX partner 32-FHI/NIPH, Oslo, Norway
Webinar – 8 Jun 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – FOOD SAFETY KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE (FSKX) FORMAT – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below
Workshop – 20 Jun 2022 – EFSA ONE Conference 2022, Side Event – WORKSHOP FOR ONE HEALTH PROFESSIONALS ON EFFICIENT EXCHANGE OF MATHEMATICAL MODELS AND DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURES WITH THE HARMONIZED FSKX FORMAT – more information here: https://www.one2022.eu/satellite-and-side-events/FSKX-workshop
WP6 presentation – 28 Jun 2022 – Presentation of the Swedish annual disease surveillance report workflow and dashboards – Gustafsson (41-SVA) – Available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/20220628_monthly_meeting_presentation.pdf
Presentation – 18 Jul 2022 – TECHNICAL MEETING INIA – Directorate General for Environment and Territory of the Government of Andalusia (Spain) in wild boars (and other wild animals) – IA solutions for foodborne diseases surveillance in wildlife – 16-INIA
Presentation – 08-12 Aug 2022 – 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE16) – An inventory of zoonotic and food borne disease surveillance systems: expanding and understanding the One Health knowledge base (WP1)
Presentation – 31 Aug-02 Sep 2022 - Tagung der DVG-Fachgruppe Epidemiologie & Dokumentation (DACH-Epidemiologietagung 2022) – Exploring and understanding the One Health knowledge base (WP1)
Webinar – 15 Sep 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – MANUAL FOR ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE DASHBOARDS – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below

Webinar – 6 Oct 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – ROADMAP TO DEVELOP NATIONAL ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below
Article – 13 October 2022 – An article about One Health EJP including results from the MATRIX project in English and Norwegian – 32-FHI/NIPH, Oslo, Norway – available at: https://www.fhi.no/en/id/infectious-diseases/smitte-fra-mat-vann-og-dyr/flere-artikler/the-largest-ever-health-project-funded-from-the-eus-horizon-2020/
WP6 workshop – 14 Oct 2022 – Developing an OHS dashboard: step-by-step guide – Gustafsson 41-SVA – Available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/step-by-step/
Webinar – 10 Nov 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE CODEX: KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION PLATFORM – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below – recording available at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377759
WP6 presentation – 23 Nov 2022 – Gottschald (9-BfR) – Presentation of the FoodChain Lab project – available at: https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/20221123_Gottschald_FCL_An_integrative_modular_software_MATRIXmonthly_pub.pdf
Webinar – 24 Nov 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – INTERACTIVE GUIDE TO DEVELOPING MULTI-SECTORAL SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below
Presentation – 5-7 Dec 2022 – ONE HEALTH EJP FINAL SCHOOL 2022: SUSTAINABILITY IN ONE HEALTH: HOW CAN IT BE ACHIEVED? – Short Term Missions: outcomes and insights from researchers who have undertaken OHEJP Short Term Missions – 16-INIA
Presentation 5-7 Dec 2022 – ONE HEALTH EJP FINAL SCHOOL 2022: SUSTAINABILITY IN ONE HEALTH: HOW CAN IT BE ACHIEVED? – Sustainability by practice: the experience of the OHEJP MATRIX project – Benedetti 13-SSI
Webinar – 15 Dec 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – WHAT IS SPECIAL AND COMMON FOR FOODBORNE HAZARDS IN ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE? – see <i>JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability</i> below

Training materials e.g. tutorials and videos

FSKX format, RAKIP Model repository and FSK-Lab supporting training material in the Moodle platform (https://bfr-elearning.de/ ; Username: fsk-workshop21; Password: Matrix.2110)
Case Study: One Health, outbreak investigations and the importance of harmonized microbiological methods – A case study based on the investigation of outbreaks of cryptosporidiosis among veterinary students in Denmark. This case study was initially released only as part of the activities related to the One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 'Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests', 2022 . A manuscript about this experience is planned under OHEJP WP5 Work Package 5: Science to Policy Translation
WP5 – Video recording from the One Health Surveillance CODEX: The Knowledge Integration Platform Webinar – 10 Nov 2022 – available here: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377759

WP6 Decision and collaboration dashboards

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T1 Country-based Identification of existing cross-sectorial OHs activities – M25-36 – A live document titled *Decision and Collaboration Dashboards: an Inventory* (<https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/> – later renamed as the *Dashboard Information Centre*) collected the ongoing developments of the entire WP and a list of the planned, ongoing or finished dashboard projects of participating partners. This WP was impacted by the pandemic in Year 3 (2020), and its activities fully took off in Year 4 (2021). This task gathered information from the first round of OHEJP projects i.e. the lessons learned in JIP ORION regarding multi-agency collaboration and data interoperability in One

Health; the documentation from JIP COHESIVE on dissemination of surveillance results; and the achievements of JRP NOVA recommending new methods for analysis of surveillance data. The WP also organized monthly meetings with project partners to foster the achievement of Task 1, 2 and 3 objectives via exchanging knowledge and first-hand experiences of dashboard development and use at country level. An expert list of people knowledgeable in One Health surveillance and in the development of dashboards was also maintained. No deliverable was attached to this task.

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T2 Defining the content needs for cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards – M34-60 – Following the work in WP6-T1, and considering the hazards of relevance to MATRIX, this task invited partners to have inter-agency discussions on the possibilities and problems that can be addressed with joint analyses and/or visualization of data. The design of cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards was driven from the end user perspective, including information gaps and methodological limitations, technical and legal barriers associated with data sharing. The result of this task is the Dashboard Information Centre, a practical manual for the development of One Health dashboards (<https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/>). This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP6.1 User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open-source tools (source codes)* (delivered in M58).

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T3 Technical implementation and testing of dashboards – M37-60 – This task implemented country-specific, cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards. The deliverable of this task was a dashboard inventory, to be used within MATRIX and beyond. A specific focus was on the sustainability of information (data usefulness and relevance) and the technical sustainability of dashboards (the used platforms). The inventory is hosted in the Dashboard Information Centre (<https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/>) together with the practical manual produced in WP6-T2. This task provided the content of deliverable *D-WP6.2 A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability* (delivered in M58).

MATRIX Hazard Tracks

The problem-oriented approach of the project was reflected in the creation of hazard-specific tracks to ensure that the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* were relevant to specific pathogens. In actuality, MATRIX meant “a frame of solutions and hazards”. The hazards were chosen based on the operational priorities of MATRIX partner institutes and their One Health relevance. They were *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance (AMR), viruses and parasites. Figure 2 shows an overview of the links between WPs and HTs in MATRIX. It is important to note that MATRIX never intended to cover all the possible combinations among countries, hazards and sectors.

Hazard Track – *Listeria* – The work of this HT primarily contributed to:

- Interviews about *Listeria* surveillance systems in MATRIX WP1;
- The development of a questionnaire about sampling, analytical methods and capacities of *Listeria monocytogenes* surveillance in the AH, PH and FS sectors and the collection of responses from three countries;
- Based on operational observations about OHS during Year 3 (2020), the development of checklists for best practices e.g. in outbreak management and active surveillance (MATRIX WP2);
- Reports of *Listeria* surveillance from the AH and FS sectors through the OH-EpiCap tool (MATRIX WP4);
- A review of barriers and facilitators to integrated OHS systems (MATRIX WP5);
- An in-depth study about challenges with sharing whole-genome sequencing data between One Health partners, based on a specifically developed interview guide (MATRIX WP5 and WP6);

- Planning a pilot dashboard for *Listeria* inspired by, although not included in, “Sykdomspulsen One Health dashboard” in Norway, focusing on official surveillance data and selected metadata, for food and human illness cases. This activity further built upon projects JRP ListAdapt and JIP ORION.

Hazard Track – *Salmonella* – The work of this HT primarily contributed to:

- MATRIX WP2 in providing country specific responses to questionnaires on *Salmonella* surveillance across the sectors. This was the primary contribution of this HT;
- Existing sources of *Salmonella* surveillance information and data across Europe (such as the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, ECDC and EFSA activities) were detailed and made available across the WPs;
- Additional ad hoc feedback across the WPs was given through specific questions and reviews of work in progress. For example, the HT identified opportunities in collaborating with MATRIX WP1, where the surveillance of *Salmonella* spp. is included in the WP inventories, and in the interviews of existing OHS systems;
- Several examples for the task JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T3 Selection of appropriate output-based surveillance systems.

Hazard Track – *Campylobacter* – The work of this HT primarily contributed to:

- MATRIX WP1, where the surveillance of *Campylobacter* spp. is included in the package’s inventories;
- MATRIX WP2, where a questionnaire about *Campylobacter* spp. (*jejuni* and *coli*) surveillance chains was developed for the PH, AH and FS sectors and responses were collected and analysed for three countries (MATRIX WP2-T1); the HT is also represented in MATRIX WP2-T2;
- MATRIX WP5, where barriers and facilitators in the cross-sectoral surveillance of *Campylobacter* spp. were considered in Task 1;
- MATRIX WP6, where the integration of *Campylobacter* spp. in the Norwegian “One Health Sykdomspulsen” dashboard is in progress.

Hazard Track – Emerging threats (including AMR) – The work of this HT primarily contributed to:

- Integrating AMR in the work of MATRIX WP4; AMR is described as a relevant topic also from the perspective of other hazards; MATRIX WP3, WP5 and WP6 offered opportunity for collaboration, too;
- Integrating Hepatitis E in the work of MATRIX WP2 and WP4;
- Integrating SARS-CoV-2 in the work of MATRIX WP2, WP3 and WP4, and potentially of MATRIX WP1 and WP5; also, this work advanced in close collaboration with the JIP COVRIN;
- Integrating *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the work of MATRIX WP3. Integrating psittacosis in the work of MATRIX WP1 and WP4, West Nile Virus in the work of MATRIX WP1, other zoonotic pathogens in the work of MATRIX WP1 and WP6. Despite initially being considered, MATRIX partners have not prioritized Norovirus as a hazard of interest since 2021.

In 2022, HT leaders actively documented their lessons learned by ensuring the representativeness and relevance of their specific hazard in the work of the different WPs. Monthly meetings were organized accordingly. Additionally, one ad hoc webinar was organized about the lessons learned by the HTs in the ***Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022***, titled: WHAT IS SPECIAL AND COMMON FOR FOODBORNE HAZARDS IN ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE? – see JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability below.

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
<i>Listeria</i>	Norway	Human / Food / Animal Sector Norway, Italy, Netherlands		Netherlands, Finland, Norway	Norway	
<i>Salmonella</i>	France, Germany	Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Spain, Germany, Norway, UK	Human / Food / Animal Sector UK, Sweden, Denmark	France, Netherlands, Germany	Sweden	
<i>Campylobacter</i>	Germany	Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Germany, Norway, Denmark, Sweden		Sweden, Norway	Finland	Norway
Emerging threat: <i>Hepatitis E</i>		Human / Food / Animal Sector Portugal, Netherlands, Italy, Norway				
Emerging threat: SARS-CoV-2		Animal Sector UK	Human / Animal Sector Netherlands			
Emerging threat: <i>E. multilocularis</i>			Human / Animal Sector Poland			
Emerging threat: AMR	England			France - Portugal - More applications conducted in the framework of the CoEvalAMR project		
Emerging threat: Psittacosis	Denmark			Denmark		
Emerging threat: WNV	Italy, Austria					
Emerging threat: Zoonotic pathogens	Tanzania, Netherlands					Sweden
Whole Genome Sequencing for microbial pathogens						Italy

Figure 2. A matrix of the links between WPs and HTs, as per December 2022. Cells describe the specific interactions among the MATRIX WPs and HTs, including the related countries, sectors and hazards. Empty blue cells describe a specific interaction between a WP and a HT that did not encompass a country-, sector- or hazard-specific output e.g. studying a specific surveillance system or piloting one of the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*.

AMR: antimicrobial resistance; UK: United Kingdom; WNV: West Nile Virus

WP0 Coordination

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T1 Internal coordination – M25-60 – from M39³ activities included:

- Managing the handover of the MATRIX leadership and vice-leadership;
- Managing the withdrawal of the partner 12-DTU Food from the MATRIX Consortium (starting on 01 Jan 2021), including the redistribution of the partner activities and budget;

³ In M39 (March 2021), MATRIX had its third project leader who remained in the position until the end of the project. Previous project leaders (from M25 to M38) similarly contributed to the listed activities including, among others, i) managing the withdrawal of the partner 17-UCM from the MATRIX Consortium (early in 2020); ii) writing the 9-month and 12-month reports for Year 3 (2020).

- Welcoming and orientating new colleagues in the Consortium e.g. after handover at partner institute level;
- Managing routine meetings with the MATRIX Consortium and the WP/HT leaders;
- Supporting the routine management of WPs;
- Defining a Consortium internal procedure for the validation of the project deliverables;
- Continuous documentation/reporting of the project progresses; writing the 9-month and 12-month reports for Year 4 (2021), writing the 9-month report for Year 5 (2022), writing the final project report and revising the Year 5 (2022) Work Plan in collaboration with WP and HT leaders;
- Routine and extraordinary budgetary management;
- Ongoing housekeeping of the project webpage.

The redistribution of the 12-DTU Food activities included: i) expanding the evaluation of the OH-Epi-Cap tool by partners 1-ANSES, 23-UoS and 13-SSI; ii) strengthening the involvement of partner 33-NVI in MATRIX WP2-T3, WP5-T1 and WP 6; iii) expanding the work of WP3 including output-based surveillance of *Echinococcus multilocularis* by partner 34-PIWET; iv) including a concept called "Forum for preparedness epidemiology" in the work of MATRIX WP5 by partner 41-SVA; v) extending the work of partner 13-SSI in MATRIX WP5-T2.

Overall, MATRIX WP0 organized 8 Consortium meetings with the participation of the full Consortium and 8 operational meetings with WP, Task and HT leaders ([see the MATRIX webpage](#)).

In autumn 2021, the original project proposal was reviewed and compared to the AWP Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5. Discrepancies were found among the different documents. Particularly, discrepancies were found regarding the Work Plan as described on pages 11-14 of the original project proposal document. Considering this, it is important to highlight that the only documents guiding the activities of the different MATRIX WPs were the AWPs Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5 (and the related amendments agreed with the OHEJP Project Management Team), in line with the related yearly budgets.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning:

- The original project proposal (page 21) described "integrative missions" around the MATRIX HTs but these were not included in the AWPs Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5 and their related budgets. However, in consideration of the impact that HTs can have beyond the project, MATRIX HTs and WP0 explored opportunities to summarise and disseminate the lessons learnt during the work of specific HTs (see also above [MATRIX Hazard Tracks](#) and below [JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability](#))
- The original project proposal describes the project's outputs several times using different words i.e. under "objectives description" at page 7, "primary impacts" at page 9, "progresses beyond state-of-the-art" at page 10, "project aims" at page 10, "objectives" under Annex 7 of the original project proposal at page 24.
- The original project proposal (page 21) states: "The bi-annual project meetings will have a dedicated session for participation of external stakeholders. Representatives from other projects, EFSA and ECDC will be welcomed via teleconference or physical attendance (at their own cost)". However, MATRIX had dedicated resources in the Year 5 (2022) budget for this, after the reallocation of 12-DTU-Food activities. In Year 5 (2022), MATRIX invited representatives from OHEJP and stakeholders to the project's Consortium meetings.
- The original project proposal often confused the concept of the European Union member states and the countries represented by the project partners.

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T2 External coordination and communication – M25-60 – from M39⁴ activities included:

- Routine communication with OHEJP WP4 and the OHEJP Coordination Team;
- Inclusion of new partners i.e. Ruokavirasto (Finland) expressed their interest to participate in MATRIX. Therefore, an activity plan and an estimated budget were drafted and submitted for approval. Ruokavirasto (45-RUOKA) became a partner of the MATRIX Consortium in June 2021;
- Communicating with other OHEJP projects (from the first and second call), and with external relevant projects and stakeholders;
- Applying for a 6-month extension of the project (agreed at Consortium level);
- Applying for the extension of project tasks and related deliverables;
- Additionally, in 2022, two briefing documents were written to disseminate the use of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** to OHEJP stakeholders and other relevant initiatives like SIS OT.

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T3 Data management – M25-60 – Within the MATRIX Consortium, the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (9-BfR) was responsible for the MATRIX Data Management Plan from spring 2021 onward. Partner 9-BfR periodically updated the project Data Management Plan in the CDP-tool. Deliverable *D-WP0.2 Data Management Plan - Final* was completed in M58.

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability – M25-60 – The original MATRIX project proposal and work plan stated the following:

- “Sustainability refers specifically to the maintenance of project outputs after its conclusion”;
- “The main contributor to sustainability is MATRIX’s focus on ‘adoption in practice’ in individual countries”;
- “The sustainability of the outputs from MATRIX lies primarily with each country that chooses to adopt the proposed frameworks”;
- “The expected gains in surveillance quality and/or efficiency will be the main driver for countries to keep their adoption”;
- “Maintaining sustainability and extending the MATRIX approach is up to the individual countries, but the frameworks will be kept publicly available”;
- “MATRIX is sustainable as almost all outputs will be made freely available to stakeholders after the project has ended”;
- The project operates to the “continuous identification and documentation of sustainability challenges and opportunities to address them”.

MATRIX was designed in a way that most of its impact (the change produced by the project), which primarily depends on the use that others will make of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**, is expected after its end. Logically, this placed the sustainability of the change produced by the project (impact) beyond the control of the project itself. Therefore, MATRIX always had a primary interest in spreading the knowledge of its work and promoting the solutions that it developed.

In November 2021, the 19 partners composing the MATRIX Consortium agreed to maintain a continuous focus on the project’s sustainability during 2022 and until its end, thus making the project’s sustainability strategy a shared commitment and responsibility of all partners.

The MATRIX Consortium worked and agreed on the project’s sustainability strategy to be applied in 2022, when the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** took shape.

⁴ In M39 (March 2021), MATRIX had its third project leader who remained in the position until the end of the project. Previous project leaders (from M25 to M38) similarly contributed to the listed activities.

The project's sustainability strategy was built around the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* and it included 5 action points:

1. To support MATRIX partners in making use of the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*. This point focused on subjects that were internal to the MATRIX Consortium. The MATRIX Consortium developed a self-assessment tool to support the MATRIX partners defining how they were using, planning to use or could use the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* in their respective countries. The tool was applied by several partners throughout 2022.
2. To disseminate and pilot the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* among non-partners. This point focused on subjects that were external to the MATRIX Consortium. In addition to the manifold initiatives that the project partners and WP leaders took to disseminate their work, in 2022 the MATRIX Consortium organized and delivered a series of seven webinars, [the Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars](#), to present the project's outcomes.
3. To support the production of original peer-reviewed publications. To facilitate this, JIPs MATRIX, CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP jointly launched the thematic call titled "One Health Surveillance in Practice: Experiences of Integration among Human Health, Animal Health, Environmental Health, and Food Safety Sectors" in the peer-reviewed journal *Frontiers in Public Health* ([here](#)).
4. To continue and whenever possible enhance training/dissemination activities aiming to reach the broadest audience. See above [JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination](#).
5. To continue the advancement and use of the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* ([here](#)). See above [JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T3 Knowledge-Integration Platform](#).

For a complete description of the MATRIX Sustainability Strategy, its activities and its achievements, see Deliverable *D-WP0.2 Sustainability Document*, which was completed in M58 – available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7410987#.Y5nT4XbMJPY>.

Furthermore, the MATRIX Sustainability strategy showed to be in line with the *OHEJP priority (sustainable) activities – The 7 Wonders of OHEJP*, as presented during the OHEJP ASM 2022 in Orvieto (Terni), Italy ([here](#)):

- Point 3 – integrating & exchanging knowledge;
- Point 4 – implementing, strengthening and assessing OHS;
- Point 6 – fostering (inter)national collaborations.

8.3 Project self-assessment

The MATRIX Consortium always worked in a spirit of collaboration and openness. No conflicts, lack of commitment, poor relationships or other negative experiences were reported. Maintaining the closest possible working proximity among Consortium partners was a paramount aspect of this collaboration. This was particularly evident in the tight exchanges that the different partners, WPs and HTs established with each other. For example, the manifold participations in the interviews and case studies of MATRIX WP1, in the mapping exercises of MATRIX WP2, in the evaluations of the OH-EpiCap tool, the various contributions to the work about dashboards in MATRIX WP6, the integrations of various project outputs into the OHS Codex/KIP and roadmap for OHS.

It is important to reference one of the primary objectives of the OHEJP program in building and improving relationships within the One Health sector. The MATRIX project has significantly contributed to this objective in building multiple WP collaborations across all the partner institutes involved in the project. While the specific deliverables of MATRIX have been delivered, the scientific community that was established to deliver them persists and will continue to grow in generating future scientific research and

operational One Health activities. Additionally, we should also mention here the large number of competencies that were developed within the project Consortium during the lifetime of MATRIX: this was primarily possible thanks to the constant exchange occurring among the many experienced professionals from diverse backgrounds who have been working together.

The project managed to deliver all the outputs that were initially proposed and that today are known as the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*. In this process, it faced a few challenges. However, the project showed an adequate response and resilience every time.

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic reshuffled the operational relationship among WPs and among MATRIX and other projects. The Pert chart described in the original project proposal (page 11) eventually was only partially relevant. The pandemic also affected the way of working, making the use of digital resources widespread, while many of the originally intended physical meetings did not happen. MATRIX experienced the loss of key-persons (staff and leaders). The project had three leaders from partner 13-SSI (one from M25 to M30, one from M31 to M38, one from M39 to M60) and two deputy leaders from partner 41-SVA (one from M25 to M38, one from M39 to M60). This represented another challenge, especially in the initial phase of the project and for partners not in the position of being WP or task leaders.

In 2021, the OHEJP Coordination Team gave MATRIX the opportunity to apply for a 6-month extension and to update the AWP Year 5 and budget accounting for that. This was a valuable opportunity for MATRIX (and for other JIPs) to complete activities despite the postponements due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic.

In January 2021, the National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU Food) left the MATRIX Consortium. Despite the scientific loss related to the specific 12-DTU Food expertise in FS, the Consortium managed to take over the related activities (see at section 3 of this report under *JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T1*). Before that, partner VISAVET-University Complutense, Madrid (17-UCM) left the project Consortium. Additionally, the originally imagined collaboration with the Ross University School of Veterinary Medicine on the Caribbean island of St. Kitts never started due to the loss of key personnel. The original project members of several partners were replaced by new colleagues. This not only affected the operational aspects of the project but also the overall sense of ownership of the project. The ad hoc developed project sustainability strategy (see at section 3 of this report under *JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4*), especially with its point 1, aimed to reinforce the sense of ownership among the project's partners.

On the other hand, a new partner, the Finnish Food Authority, Ruokavirasto (45-RUOKA), joined the OHEJP and specifically the MATRIX project Consortium in June 2021 and effectively integrated in the work of MATRIX WP5 and MATRIX WP6.

Considering the proximity of the 3 Integrative Projects CARE (led by the OHEJP partner 12-DTU Food, Denmark), OH-HARMONY-CAP (also led by the OHEJP partner 13-SSI, Denmark) and MATRIX, a strong collaboration was built with the management teams of JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP to ensure a joint sustainability strategy. The three projects participated in each other's annual/interim meetings sharing knowledge and the progress on their projects. The three projects also jointly organized their final meetings in September 2022 in Copenhagen, Denmark. Representatives from the leading partners of the 3 projects also successfully organised the third OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2022 with a theme on "Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests". Additionally, point 3 of the MATRIX sustainability strategy (see above *JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability*) describes another initiative among the 3 projects i.e. a thematic call for original publications in the Journal *Frontiers in Public Health*.

Finally, it is worth highlighting a challenge to the sustainability of MATRIX, and possibly of many other OHEJP projects. MATRIX developed the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* thanks to

the partner-specific project resources. In line with the original project proposal, MATRIX partners made the solutions available to the public audience either on the specific partner institute websites, on GitHub or Zenodo. The *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* have been hosted in different spaces. Now, the risk to disperse the outputs of MATRIX and in general of all the OHEJP projects represent a challenge to their sustainability. Ideally, OHEJP could ensure the sustainable hosting of the projects' outputs in a common platform.

8.4 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

8.4.1 Deliverables – ordered by date delivered and work package

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP0.2	Data Management Plan – final	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022. Public Yvonne Mensching. (2022). Deliverable D-WP0.2_20221031_MATRIX_data_management_plan_final. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7414182	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP0.3	Sustainability document	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022. Public Benedetti, Guido. (2022). Deliverable D-WP0.3_20221031_MATRIX_Sustainability_Document. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410987	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.3	Report on the evaluation of the common framework using examples within the consortium	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022. Public Dups-Bergmann, Johanna, & Sauter-Louis, Carola. (2022). Deliverable D-WP1.3_20223110_MATRIX_Evaluation_Common_Framework_Report. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7403134	1, 6

JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.3	Common framework of OHS surveillance	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	<p>The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022.</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Ingrid Friesema, & Caroline Eves. (2022). Deliverable D-WP2.3_20221031_MATRIX_Common_Framework_OHS. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7386412</p>	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP3.2	Combined report for all subtasks within the development of output-based metrics	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	<p>The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022.</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Verity Horigan, Maciej Kochanowski, Samantha Rivers, Anna Ziętek-Barszcz, Rob Dewar, Agnieszka Stolarek, & Mirek Różycki. (2022). Deliverable D-WP3.2_20221031_MATRIX_Output_Based_Metrics. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390006</p>	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.3	<p>Report on the implementation of the OH-EpiCap evaluation tool on several study cases</p> <p>Original title: Report on the implementation of evaluation approaches on two studies cases</p>	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	<p>The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022.</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Viviane Henaux, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). MATRIX Deliverable D-WP4.3 – Report on the implementation of the OH-EpiCap evaluation tool on several study cases. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7375651</p> <p>Note: the change in the name of the tool from “EU-EpiCap” to “OH-EpiCap” was approved by OHEJP WP4 in March 2022.</p>	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP5.2	<p>Development of a national One Health surveillance roadmap</p> <p>Original title: OHS roadmap template document</p>	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	<p>The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022.</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Mia Holmberg, & Estelle Ågren. (2022). Deliverable D-WP5.2_MATRIX_OHS_Roadmap_Template. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7385314 https://zenodo.org/record/7385314#.Y5ykRIGZNPZ</p>	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP6.1	User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open	M58 as per the revised AWP	M58	<p>The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022.</p> <p>Public</p>	1, 6

		source tools (source codes)	Year 5 (2022)		Wiktor Gustafsson, & Gry Marysol Grøneng. (2022). Deliverable D-WP6.1_20221031_MATRIX_Dashboard_User_Manual. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7398545	
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP6.2	A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability	M58 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M58	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022. Public Wiktor Gustafsson, & Gry Marysol Grøneng. (2022). Deliverable D-WP6.2_20221031_MATRIX_Dashboard_Sustainability. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7398589	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.2	Description of a common framework for OH surveillance	M54 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M54	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022 Public Johanna Dups-Bergmann, & Carola Sauter-Louis. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP1.2 Description of a common framework for One Health surveillance. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7064374	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.2	Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS Original title: Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)	M54 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M54	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022 Public Francesca Cito, Laura Amato, Taran Skjerdal, Stine Kjær Lefèvre, Joaquin Prada, Charlotte Cook, & Caroline Eves. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP2.2 Best practices. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7053387	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP3.1	Report on output-based surveillance system selection methodology Original title: Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as	M54 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M54	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022 Public Verity Horigan, Beate Conrady, Liza Rosenbaum Nielsen, Hans Houe, Mark Arnold, Jo Lawes, Rob Davies, Arianna Comin, Beth Young, Estelle Agren, Lukasz Bocian, Anna Zietek-Bocian, Agnieszka Stolarek, Mirek Rozycki, Rob Dewar, Sam Rivers, Alex Kent, Jose Gonzales, Nora Gerhards, & Wim van der Poel. (2022). D-WP3.1_MATRIX Report on output-based surveillance	1, 6

		many of the approaches as possible			system selection methodology. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6984562	
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.2	OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial Original title: EUEpiCap tool and tutorial	M54 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M54	The original delivery date was revised in the AWP 2022 Public Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailier, Lucie Colineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP4.2 OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006654 Note: the change in the name of the tool from “EU-EpiCap” to “OH-EpiCap” was approved by OHEJP WP4 in March 2022.	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP5.1	Report on requirement analysis for “OHS roadmap template”	M51 as per the revised AWP Year 5 (2022)	M51	Public Eves, Caroline, Friesema, Ingrid, Skjerdal, Olaug Taran, Holmberg, Mia, Ågren, Estelle, Lopez de Abechuco, Estibaliz, Daugaard Larsen, Helle, Kjær Lefèvre, Stine, & Benedetti, Guido. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP5.1 - Report on requirement analysis for "OHS roadmap template". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504418 Note: the last extension of this deliverable (from M48 to M51), which was approved by OHEJP WP4 in October 2021, was not documented in the AWP 2022 at the time when the 12-month report for Year 4 (2021) was drafted.	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.1	Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages	Originally M36; then M42; postponed to M48 (see comments)	M48	Public Francesca Cito, Laura Amato, Estelle Ågren, & Mia Holmberg. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP2.1 MAPPING OF THE SURVEILLANCE CHAIN FOR ALL HAZARD TRACKS, AND CROSS-SECTORIAL LINKAGES. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406150 The deliverable was originally expected in M36. It was then postponed to M42. In May 2021, a request was made for its postponement until M48. The request was approved by the OHEJP WP4.	1, 6

JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.1	Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities	M39	M39	Public Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailier, Lucie Collineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2021). OHEJP MATRIX D-WP4.1. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4750976	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP0.1	Data Management Plan - draft	M36	M37	Public MATRIX. (2021). D-WP0.1_Data Management Plan_draft_MATRIX. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471349 The Draft was created on 31/10/2020. Reviews were received by 04/01/2021. The report was written and uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX webpage and Zenodo in M37.	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.1	Report on the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in AH, PH, and FS	M36	M36	Public Dups-Bergmann, Johanna Nina, & Sauter-Louis, Carola. (2021). D_WP1.1_20210630_MATRIX - COMMONALITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF THE DIFFERENT OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORKS IN ANIMAL HEALTH, PUBLIC HEALTH AND FOOD SAFETY. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5062548 Uploaded to the OHEJP MATRIX site on 04/10/2021.	1, 6

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

8.4.2 Milestones – ordered by date delivered and work package

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2022 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	Comments
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP4.1	Deployment of the OH-EpiCap survey tool in several European countries on study cases Original title: Deployment of the EUEpiCap survey tool in several European countries on study cases	M54	Yes	Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailier, Lucie Collineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). Milestone M-JIP-MATRIX-WP4.1 Deployment of the OH-EpiCap survey tool in several European countries on study cases. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006609
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP6.1	Dashboards operational within the pilot participating agencies	M54	Yes	MATRIX. (2022). M-MATRIX-WP6.M1 - "DASHBOARDS OPERATIONAL WITHIN THE PILOT PARTICIPATING AGENCIES". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6867595
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP3.1	End of the first round of OHEJP projects Original title: End of the first round of OHEJP projects: this will coincide with the end of the inventory and requirement analysis phase in most WPs	M48 (not in the AWP 2022)	Yes	The end of the first round of OHEJP projects was extended due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Therefore, MATRIX inventories and requirement analysis obtained the relevant resources directly from the projects instead of relying on the publicly available expected outcomes. A full achievement of this milestone was obtained during 2021. The milestone was achieved in December 2021. Verity Horigan, Mirosław Rozycki, & Guido Benedetti. (2022). Milestone M-JIP-MATRIX-WP3.1 End of the first round of OHEJP projects. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5992510
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP5.1	Knowledge-platform operational	M42	Yes	The milestone was achieved on time. The platform is operational at: https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html Esther M. Sundermann, & Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco. (2021). MILESTONE M-WP5.1 "KNOWLEDGE-PLATFORM OPERATIONAL". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5175982

8.5 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Sundermann EM, Nauta M, Swart A (2021). A ready-to-use dose-response model of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> implemented in the FSKX-standard. Food Modelling Journal 2: e63309. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.63309 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/4923018	Published	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro
Sundermann EM, Correia Carreira G, Käsbohrer A (2021). A FSKX compliant source attribution model for salmonellosis and a look at its major hidden pitfalls. Food Modelling Journal 2: e70008. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.70008 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5674165#.YZ5rANDMJPY	Published	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro
Swanson D, Koren C, Hopp P, Jonsson ME, Rø GI, White RA, Grøneng GM (2022). A One Health real-time surveillance system for nowcasting <i>Campylobacter</i> gastrointestinal illness outbreaks, Norway, week 30 2010 to week 11 2022. Euro Surveill. 2022;27(43):pii=2101121. Available at: https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.43.2101121 Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.43.2101121	Published	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro
Rodríguez A, Iglesias I, de la Torre A (2022). Prioritisation tool for targeting the monitoring of veterinary pharmaceuticals at national level: the case of	Published	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro

Spain. European Journal soil sciences, 73(4):e13268. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13268				
Tegegne HA, Bogaardt C, Collineau L, Cazeau G, Lailier R, Reinhardt J, Taylor E, Prada J, Hénaux V (submitted). OH-EpiCap: a semi-quantitative tool for the evaluation of One Health epidemiological surveillance capacities and capabilities – partner 1-ANSES	Submitted	Yes		Yes, 3125 €
Provisional title/subject: Mapping food surveillance chains through a One Health approach – partner 28-IZSAM	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Commonalities and differences in surveillance approaches to zoonotic and food borne diseases between the sectors – partner 10-FLI	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Implementation of One Health surveillance system, opportunities, and challenges: Lesson learned from the OH-EpiCap tool application – partner 23-UoS	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: A framework for the design, implementation, and evaluation of output-based surveillance systems against zoonotic threats – partner 21-APHA	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Systematic review of the use of output-based surveillance from a One Health perspective – partner 21-APHA	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: De la Torre A et al. Using machine learning algorithms to identify critical points of <i>Salmonella</i> surveillance systems in channel food in Spain – partner 16-INIA	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: De la Torre A et al. Using machine learning algorithms to predict occurrence of food borne diseases in wild animals and their associated risk factors – partner 16-INIA	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Better understandings barriers and triggers for data sharing, with a focus on WGS and <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> – partner 33-NVI	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Sundermann E et al. Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format: an open community-driven format for the exchange of food safety	Under writing	Yes		Yes, 3125 €

data, data processing routines and models – partner 9-BfR				
Provisional title/subject: Günther T et al. Linked data as an approach towards efficient data integration and exchange between One Health sectors – partner 9-BfR	Under writing	Yes		Yes, 3125 €
Provisional title/subject: Genetic characterization of Hepatitis E genotypes circulating in Portugal January 2009-December 2022 – partner 36-INSA	Under writing	Yes		
Additional manuscript – preliminary title to be defined – partner 36-INSA	Under writing	Yes		
Provisional title/subject: Methods to be applied to output-based surveillance data related to animal health. Submitted in Preventive Veterinary Medicine. This work is also based upon work from COST Action SOUND control – University of Copenhagen (UCPH), no publication cost is expected	Submitted	Yes		

8.6 Additional output

See above the list of activities covered by task [*JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination.*](#)

Relevant outputs from MATRIX WP2-T1 have been included in the Ph.D. project by an expert from partner 28-IZSAM, member of the MATRIX Consortium and specifically working on MATRIX WP2, as a case study on the application of the One Health approach. The project focused on case studies about the application of One Health in different contexts i.e. vector-borne and food-borne diseases. The project belongs to the Ph.D. course in “Infectious Diseases, Microbiology and Public Health” at the Sapienza University of Rome, Italy.

One scientific abstract (by partner University of Copenhagen, UCPH) related to *Salmonella* Dublin STOC free Model (described under the work of MATRIX WP3) was accepted as an oral presentation for the [SVEPM conference](#) in Toulouse, France in 2023. Conference proceedings are submitted in December 2022.

One article focusing on MATRIX and the activities of MATRIX WP2 has been prepared for the next issue of the Italian national bulletin for epidemiology, [BENV - Bollettino Epidemiologico Nazionale Veterinario](#). It will be published in both Italian and English, under the title of "MATRIX: integrated and multisectoral surveillance in a One Health perspective".

8.7 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

MATRIX created solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance, also known as the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**. All the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** are relevant outputs to national and regional PH, AH, FS institutes (within and outside OHEJP), OHEJP stakeholders (e.g. EFSA and ECDC) and other relevant One Health initiatives (e.g. SIS OT). They are:

- OH-EpiCap Tool – an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS of a hazard of choice, identifying strengths and opportunities for improvement. Additionally, the tool allows the benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities for comparison. More information is available here: [OH-EpiCap tool flyer](#) and [OH-EpiCap tool user guide](#).
- Roadmap to develop national OHS – a guideline that countries can use to develop OHS according to their needs and resources. The roadmap expanded the work of the OHEJP COHESIVE project and is available at <https://www.ohras.eu/page/home> – copy-paste this link in your browser.
- Manual for OHS Dashboards – an online dashboard inventory and practical manual to facilitate the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open-source tools. More information is available here: [Dashboard Information Centre](#).
- Guidelines and checklists:
 - An interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems. A beta version is available [here](#).
 - Best-practices to operationalize cross-sectoral collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results – available [here](#).
 - A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards – available [here](#).

MATRIX also promoted and expanded:

- [The OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform](#) – a framework to integrate various resources that help to implement OHS in all sectors.
- [Food Safety Knowledge Exchange \(FSKX\) Format](#) – a format that supports the One Health community in sharing and re-using mathematical models as well as data analysis procedures.

8.8 Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

The first action of the MATRIX Sustainability Strategy (*Deliverable D-WP0.3 Sustainability document* – available [here](#)) aimed to support MATRIX partners in making use of the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*. The MATRIX Consortium developed a self-assessment tool to support MATRIX partners defining how they were using, planning to use or could use the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* in their respective countries. MATRIX partners utilized the self-assessment tool throughout 2022 until the end of the project. By updating their own assessment, they shared it with other partners (e.g. during operational and Consortium meetings) to inspire each other.

It was clarified that none of the conclusions of the self-assessment could have been considered an official commitment to the actual application of the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* after the end of the project by the partner institutes.

The results of this continuous self-assessment remain in the hands of the MATRIX partners and it is up to them to take initiative and build upon the identified interests and opportunities. This is in line with the project originally intended strategy: “the sustainability of the outputs from MATRIX lies primarily with each country that chooses to adopt the proposed frameworks”.

MATRIX partners engaged with regional/national authorities and stakeholders. By the end of the project, these collaborations were ongoing according to partner-/country-specific possibilities and needs.

It is important to highlight also here that the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* is today included in the toolbox of the Surveillance and information sharing operational tool (SIS OT): an operational tool of the tripartite zoonoses guide by WHO, FAO and WOA – [here](#).

8.9 One Health impact

MATRIX created practical solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of OHS i.e. the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*. In line with the original project proposal, MATRIX invited European institutes working in the PH, AH and FS sectors to consider the opportunity to adopt these solutions and to further build upon them.

By transferring knowledge to countries, MATRIX represented the last mile of the translation of such knowledge into practice. By breaking the barriers of individual surveillance frameworks, the project contributed to cross-linking and fertilizing the next generation of integrated OHS systems.

All the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* are relevant outputs to European countries. As per the original project proposal, the impact and sustainability of these solutions depend on their adoption in practice by individual countries, in view of their needs and expectations. European countries and institutes (among the OHEJP partners and beyond) can now e.g. evaluate their OHS capacities and capabilities; utilize Systems Thinking along the roadmap to integrated OHS; develop OHS dashboards.

International stakeholders, including the OHEJP stakeholders EFSA and ECDC, can also utilize, contribute to and build upon the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* e.g. by facilitating

evaluation activities across countries and/or hazards with the OH-EpiCap tool or by supporting the use of the *OHS CODEX: the Knowledge Information Platform*.

It is important to highlight also here that the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* is today included in the toolbox of the Surveillance and information sharing operational tool (SIS OT): an operational tool of the tripartite zoonoses guide by WHO, FAO and WOA – [here](#).

MATRIX made the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance* relevant for different countries, which are at different stages of their OHS development. For example:

- The interactive guide to developing multi-sectoral surveillance systems specifically moves from existing AH, PH and FS surveillance systems at the country level, providing 7 generic steps towards integrating sectoral surveillance systems (MATRIX WP1).
- The best practices to operationalize cross-sectorial collaborations are rooted in a collection of maps of surveillance chains and cross-sectorial linkages for different hazards and from different countries. This ensures that the best practices can be operationalized to answer various objectives (MATRIX WP2).
- The guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the food sector using output-based standards is written both for those who already implement output-based standard surveillance and those who do not, yet (MATRIX WP3).
- The OH-EpiCap tool specifically addresses the context-specific capacities and capabilities of any country or region by supporting the identification of areas in the studied surveillance system that could lead to improvements in the organization of collaborations across sectors, in the extent of collaborations in operational activities, in the impact of multi-sectoral collaborations on surveillance (MATRIX WP4).
- The roadmap to develop national OHS can be used by countries to develop OHS according to their needs and resources. Countries can use it both to build a new OHS system or to advance an existing one (MATRIX WP5).
- The Dashboard Information Centre is a toolbox and a companion for developers, future and current implementers of OHS dashboards, which make use of open-source tools (MATRIX WP6).

MATRIX also built and strengthened the networking and relationships among other partners of OHEJP and beyond. Many collaborations were established including, but not limited to:

MATRIX WP1 closely collaborated with and further built on JIP ORION's OHS inventories. The final guidelines delivered by the WP were developed in collaboration with JIP COVRIN. Furthermore, 10-FLI (MATRIX WP1 leader) was engaged in different working groups and projects with EFSA, working on surveillance and different animal diseases, and ECDC, regarding their terminology and inventory variables.

MATRIX WP2 collaborated with the JRP BeONE in the evaluation and implementation of national level data sharing as lead and deputy lead on several tasks. In addition, national-level collaborations were developed in France with surveillance actors: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, national reference laboratories on *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, and Santé Publique France, the National Public Health Agency.

MATRIX WP3 interacted with EFSA, which provided information on current output-based surveillance within the EU and links to the EFSA catalogue browser. Additionally, MATRIX WP3 collaborated with JIP COHESIVE regarding the use of the Mendelow's matrix for *JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T2 Identification of operational partners and stakeholders*.

In the framework of the MATRIX WP4, national-level collaborations were developed in France with the Food chain surveillance platform (website, in French: <https://www.plateforme-sca.fr/> - description of platform objectives and organisation), especially the research group on *Salmonella* surveillance.

International collaborations were identified with ECDC, regarding the OH-LabCap tool by JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP. Moreover, MATRIX WP4 extensively engaged with the SIS OT leadership, discussing the OH-EpiCap tool specifically, but also more broadly about evaluation of surveillance activities. This has led to invitations to several meetings and participation in the United Against Rabies Forum, particularly to discuss evaluation of tools for surveillance and implementation activities. Members of MATRIX WP4 also led activities in JIP COVRIN WP3, with significant benefits to extending MATRIX surveillance work in the area of the hazard SARS-CoV-2.

MATRIX was naturally very close and collaborated with JIP ORION, particularly in MATRIX WP5. MATRIX WP5 members participated in the first JRP DiSCoVer Stakeholder Web-meeting and got the chance to determine potential synergies and collaboration. The extension of the FSKX format and the mathematical models compliant to the FSKX format are relevant in multiple other EJP projects e.g. JRP DiSCoVer and RADAR. The development of the FSKX format and the including metadata schema to annotate knowledge started within the research project "Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platforms (RAKIP)" (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip-web-portal/>). The RAKIP community, with partners from 1-ANSES, 12-DTU Food, 9-BfR, 13-SSI and 45-RUOKA, continued the collaboration to improve and extend the community-driven metadata schema. MATRIX WP5-T2 collaborated with JIP COHESIVE and the Epidemiology Department of the University of Zurich, and built upon their work on Systems Thinking. The Systems Thinking workshops, which were conducted at the country level, reinforced and expanded contacts among One Health actors e.g. participants put the basis for more efficient data sharing.

MATRIX WP6 dealt with the creation of "data for decision dashboards". The WP built on the experienced gained within previous OHEJP projects. The JRP NOVA project developed automated routines for data analyses and visualisation and it planned dashboards for surveillance: this work inspired MATRIX WP6 in the gathering of knowledge and development of decision and collaboration dashboards. Knowledge from the JIP ORION project on collaboration and interoperability was also used, especially the OHEJP Glossary. MATRIX WP6 provided an information centre, which serve as a best-practice guide to the development of OHS dashboards, including underlying data management and analysis workflows. Throughout the project, MATRIX WP6 invited speakers from institutes within and outside the MATRIX consortium to present on topics relevant to OHS and dashboard development, which promoted collaboration and knowledge exchange.

MATRIX partner 9-BfR supported the project JRP BIOPIGEE with an infrastructure that was developed in the former JIP ORION project for the OHEJP Glossary (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>), and adapted the infrastructure to the needs of the JRP BIOPIGEE consortium. Several terms related to biosecurity measures in primary pig production were defined within the project. The result is an online solution to host, search, filter and access the terms and definitions defined by the BIOPIGEE consortium (<https://bit.ly/3oQwbom>).

Coherently with the original project proposal, MATRIX did not engage with the private sector/industry.

8.10 Data Management Plan

The MATRIX Data management plan is published with the *Deliverable D-WP0.2_20221031_MATRIX_data_management_plan_final*, which is available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7414182#.Y5nbenbMJPY>

8.11 Future dissemination activities

The above sections 7 and 8 addressed the topic of future dissemination activities.

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

It is worth reporting here some of the highlights from the Joint Final Meeting that was organized by JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP, JIP MATRIX and JIP CARE in Copenhagen, Denmark in September 2022:

- Now that the JIPs have delivered what they promised, it is time to return to the stakeholders of the programme, those who envisaged it. The legacy of JIPs lie in the needs of those who can utilize and advance the knowledge generated by the projects.
- Countries and partner institutes have the opportunity to utilize and advance the knowledge generated by the projects, also in consideration of the large investments they made into OHEJP.
- Social sciences are key to ensure a change (in the direction of One Health) that necessarily requires a change in the knowledge, attitudes and practices of many professionals across different sectors and at different levels of the decision-making process.
- Studying the cost-effectiveness of One Health is another opportunity to secure the necessary attention that the approach requires.

After the end of MATRIX in December 2022, partners will consider the appropriateness to further disseminate the *MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance*, based on their own operational strategies, capacities and resources.

9. JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparedness-COVRIN

9.1 Summary of the work carried out

In Year 5 of the One Health EJP COVRIN project, research work and integration activities were continued as planned on the two main overall operational objectives: A) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, B) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. In the research area 1) Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment, data of SARS-CoV-2 genome testing were further shared and immunoassays methodologies were further shared and harmonized. Approaches in the tasks on assessment of bioavailability were agreed and further developed. In work package 2 on SARS-CoV-2 characterization, genome analyses and next generation sequencing of detected isolates and metagenomic sequencing of different samples were taken forward. Surveys were executed to make a summary description of protocols and to make an overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics analyses. A bioinformatics ring trial was undertaken to harmonize bioinformatics pipelines. Regarding *in vitro* and *ex vivo* biological characterization of circulating SARS-CoV-2 strains, cell line models have been collated and shared between partners. Animal model protocols have also been categorized and shared between partners. This will allow better analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission. In work package 3 on SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance, formats/procedures for sampling and surveillance in wildlife, livestock and pets and the environment were evaluated and reported. Several workshops were organized to involve partners in the surveillance data collection. A review of surveillance activities in the different countries was produced. Risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals and the environment are being studied and analyses of transmissions in pets were produced. An overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals was reported. All from a One health perspective. In work package 4 of COVRIN on coronavirus preparedness, isolations of virus from different wildlife species were performed. As a start on the evaluations of the impacts on ecological factors and interventions, a report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling was put together. In year 5, more work was done on the study of virus – host interactions and on the identification of drivers of virus emergence through evaluation of phylodynamic and cross-species interactions with focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations. Generated data and research outcomes will be used in future national programmes and collaborative networks to develop control strategies, intervention strategies and prevention.

9.2 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

. WP0 - Coordination

JIP06-WP0-T0.1 - Internal project organisation (M40 – M63)

ST0.1.1 – Development of share-point for data exchange (M40 – M42)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.1.2 – Management reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

Management reports are uploaded on the SharePoint and on zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7445670#.Y5wqOnbMJPY>.

JIP06-WP0-T0.2 - Communication and reporting (M40 – M63)

ST0.2.1 – Communications reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

The COVRIN project page and group were set up on the OH EJP website. A comprehensive list of contact details for each work package, task and subtask has been compiled and uploaded to the secure area of the OHEJP website and is in use for organising meetings and compiling reports. See Deliverable D0.2.1: <https://zenodo.org/record/7448604#.Y5zB-3bMJPY>

JIP06-WP0-T0.3 - Meetings and stakeholder connections (M40 – M66)

ST0.3.1 – Scoping exercise on related projects (M40 – M45)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.3.2 – Organisation and evaluation of the kick-off meeting (M40 – M48)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.3.3 – Reporting mid-term (M40 – M57)

A mid-term meeting was held online 27th June 2022. Updates and outputs of all 5 work packages were presented by the work package leaders. Presentations are available on the COVRIN project group site and uploaded on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/7433656#.Y53kAnbP02w>).

WP1 Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

JIP06-WP1-T1.1 SARS-CoV2 molecular diagnostics in livestock, wildlife, pets and environment

ST1.1.1, Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in companion animals and livestock , ST 1.1.2, Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in wildlife and ST 1.1.3 Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in environmental samples

Testing for SARS-CoV-2 by genome detection (with molecular methods) continues in the participating COVRIN laboratories as the most widely implemented method of detection.

Six molecular assays have been assessed in partner laboratories and shared, including real-time quantitative PCR and nested PCR. These data will contribute to deliverables 1.1.1, 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 (reports on available data from virus genome detection in companion animals, wildlife and the environment) due month 63, and have also contributed to activities in WP3. In addition, a general CoV probe capture target enrichment assay has been designed and shown to increase the sensitivity of detection by two orders of magnitude.

As an example of partner activities in this area, APHA (P21) has screened several wildlife, pet and environmental samples for the presence of SARS-CoV-2. 547 wildlife samples have been tested and all were negative by SARS-CoV-2 E-gene RRT-PCR:). In total, three dogs, one cat and three tigers were found to be positive for SARS-CoV-2 as part of disease investigations. Environmental samples consisting of guano samples from Daubenton's, Lesser horseshoe and Greater horseshoe bats have been collected and tested (n=15) and all found to be negative for SARS-CoV-2.

JIP06-WP1-T1.2 Immunological SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics in domestic and wildlife animals

ST1.2.1 – Evaluation of virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals (M40 – M63)

Antigen tests detect viral proteins, often using immunochemistry, for rapid application. More than five possible assay protocols have been compiled (FLI, PIWET, APHA). A draft proposal for a harmonized protocol for rapid antigen test establishment and comparison has been developed and an interlaboratory trial is ongoing. The protocol database and finalised comparison will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.1 "Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals", due M63. Novel antibodies have also been generated and assessed for their ability to bind different SARS-CoV-2 variants with potential for use in antigen tests.

ST1.2.2 – Evaluation of antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife (M40 – M63)

The final crucial type of test is serology, indirectly detecting current or previous infection through the presence of specific antibodies. The database for sharing of established protocols for antibody detection between partners now includes Double antigen ELISAs (IZSLER), virus neutralisation test (VNT) (APHA, IZSLER), Pseudotype Virus Neutralization test (APHA), and another ELISA INGEZIM COVID 19 S VET – INGENAZA (PIWET)). An interlaboratory test for antibody detection was organised and a panel of 20 sera including positive and negative controls from different animal species was prepared and sent to partners. Recombinant proteins developed in ST1.2.1 are also being assessed for their potential in double-antigen ELISAs which can be used to detect antibodies

in any species.

Serological surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 was also conducted in domestic and wildlife animals. As an example, in addition to the molecular testing described in T1.1, APHA (P21) has undertaken serological testing on a total of 188 wildlife samples. Samples from one badger, one fallow deer and one fox were positive by both ELISA and VNT in two independent tests. A total of 3288 serum samples from the pet travel scheme for rabies were tested for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. A total of 54/619 cat sera (8.72%) and 208/2668 dog sera (7.80%) samples tested ELISA positive for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies.

Results will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.2 "Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife", due M63.

JIP06-WP1-T1.3 - Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and in the environment (M40 – M63)

This task is important to understand the relevance of detecting virus in the environment, by assessing whether the virus is infectious over time and at different temperatures.

ST1.3.1 - Discuss the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in fomites and the environment (M40 – M60) (delayed to M63)

Detection data can provide insight whether and to what extent different environmental routes may play a role in the human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. A graphical scheme was drafted to provide an overview of various potential environmental routes that may play a role in human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. Next to the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in the environment, challenges faced by environmental sampling of live SARS-CoV-2 have been discussed among partners, but it needs further elaboration prior to inclusion into deliverable D1.3 'Report on the bioavailability of virus on fomites, water and the environment' consequently delayed to M63.

ST1.3.2 - Assess infectivity of the virus over time, and at different temperatures (M40 – M60) (Delayed to M63)

Infectivity data of live SARS-CoV-2 from environmental sampling (field studies) is still only limitedly available among partner institutes. Activities of partner institutes that are continuing in this area include for example persistence in food and packaging, sewage water surveillance (humans), experimental SARS-CoV-2 studies on survival/decay in environmental matrices, SARS-CoV-2 transmission in animal models, environmental sampling at (mink) farms and in aerosols. To obtain information on infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 in environmental sources of both field and experimental studies, a literature is being conducted. Literature searches and data collection from partner institutes continue, and together will contribute to deliverable 1.3 report on the bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and the environment. As new data is coming available, a decision was made to delay the deliverable to M63 to maximise the quality and value of the output.

ST1.3.3 - Comparison with RNA quantification (PCR versus live virus) to inform risk assessments (M40 – M63)

Work on this task is underway. At the final meeting a decision was made to delay the deliverable to maximise the quality and value of the output. Detection data of live SARS-CoV-2 studies will be compared to detection data from PCR studies (obtained in T1.1). This is crucial to inform the risk of SARS-CoV-2 detection in the environment

WP2: – SARS-CoV-2 characterization

JIP06-WP2-T2.1 – Genome analyses (M40 – M54)

Task 2.1 was focused on the analyses of whole genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2 strains

circulating in humans and animals. This approach aims not only at promoting protocol sharing/harmonization, but also at mapping evolutionary changes of SARS-CoV-2 viruses isolated within and across human and different animal species, as a means to identify mutations and recombination events driving adaptation to alternative hosts.

ST2.1.1 – Protocol repository (M40 – M45)

Sub-task completed. More details in Deliverable JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5342577>).

ST2.1.2 – Harmonisation of sampling and methods for NGS (M40 – M50, extended from M48)

Sub-task completed. A Bioinformatics Ring Trial was carried out in order to assess the reproducibility of bioinformatics pipelines (i.e., from raw reads to consensus sequences, using reference-based mapping) currently being applied for genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses - CoV) across the partners institutes. Despite the good congruence between participants, a few critical issues were identified in some pipelines that challenged the comparative analysis and discussion of the results. More details in Deliverable JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6458214>).

ST2.1.3 – Development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment (M40 – M54)

Sub-task completed. ST2.1.3 focused on building bridges between several One Health EJP projects to promote the integration of bioinformatics tools that enable phylogenetic analysis and investigation for virulence traits (e.g., mutations known to play a direct role in receptor binding or antibody recognition) that can aid the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new viral threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment. In summary, activities in ST2.1.3 shows the advantage of building bridges between ongoing One Health EJP projects to enhance the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new pathogen threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment. More details in Deliverable JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6784043>).

JIP06-WP2-T2.2 - In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV-2 (M40 – M57)

ST2.2.1 – Cell culturing (M40 – M48)

Sub-task completed. Various animal cell lines have been tested for SARS-CoV-2 susceptibility. Samples from infection experiments have been exchanged between FLI – P10 and NVI – P33.

ST2.2.2 Antigenicity studies [D2.2.2 – March 2022]

Subtask completed. ST2.2.2 focused on the development and validation of serological techniques suitable for detecting the presence of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. Experimental data include tests using sera from domestic, wild and human animals on a series of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and virus neutralisation test (VNT). A series of serological tests capable of detecting different types of antibodies were evaluated. Cross-reactivity of pre-and post-pandemic human and farm animal sera with alpha- and beta-coronaviruses (CoV) including SARS-CoV-2 were also investigated. Results demonstrate that although SARS-CoV-2 is antigenically distinct, cross-reactivity should be considered when interpreting serological assays and this will vary between ELISA and VNT. See deliverable D2.2.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434267>

ST2.2.3 Complex cultures [D2.2.3 – Due M57, delayed to M63]

ST2.2.3 sought to investigate SARS-CoV-2 replication in various complex cell culture systems such as air-liquid interphase (ALI) cultures, *ex vivo* organ cultures or organoids of several animal species. At FLI, established ALI-cultures from pigs and ferrets, where bronchial epithelia are considered non-susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, were confirmed to be resistant to infection with SARS-CoV-2 B1. To study SARS-CoV-2 infection in animal models with more pronounced SARS-CoV-2 lung

infection primary bronchial epithelial cells from hamsters were tested for ALI-cultivation. Whereas ALI cultivation turned out to be inefficient for the hamster model, stone marten ALI-cultures were resistant to infection with various SARS-CoV-2 viruses (B1, human isolated of mink origin, alpha, delta). Complementary, precision lung slice cultures ALI-cultures have been established and used (WBRV and FLI) and lung organoids for SARS-Cov-2 infection are being established at WBRV. Completion has been delayed due to infection data from organoid-derived ALI-cultures and precision cut lung slices from different partners not yet complete or under evaluation. For finalization and comparative report postponement to M63 is required.

JIP06-WP2-T2.3 – Development and optimization of animal models (M43 – M60)

Task 2.3 focuses on the development of animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection and biomarker analysis.

ST2.3.1 – Animal model protocols (M43 – M45)

Sub-task completed.

ST2.3.2 – Pathology toolbox (M43 – M51)

Subtask completed. Within ST2.3.2 work has been ongoing to develop, optimise and share reagents and methodologies for pathological analyses amongst the COVRIN participants. These activities have not been solely focussed on viral detection, but also in understanding the localisation of the SARS-CoV-2 receptors within host tissues of different animal species. This work was published here: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232>, and has been expanded to assess different host receptors in a wider range of species in deliverable JIP06-WP2-D2.3.2 “Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259840>).

ST2.3.3 Establishment of virus-host interaction parameters (M43-M60) (delayed to M61)

Work within ST2.3.3 by COVRIN participants: FLI (P10), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33) is near completion. Techniques include: Transcriptome – RNASeq, Proteomics, Metabolomics, Bead-based multiplex analysis (xMAP), Biomark Fluidigm qPCR platform, Mucosal protease activity, Plasma organ injury biomarkers and cytokines, and Multicolor RNA-Scope. Antiviral responses in cells will be analysed and an in vivo trial is underway. This work includes a multi-omics approach for biomarker identification. The deliverable D2.3.3 is postponed to M61 due to data availability.

JIP06-WP2-T2.4 - Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic transmission (M49 – M63)

ST2.4.1 Variant analyses species jumps [D2.4.1 – M54], delayed until M57

Virological data (infection in animals and genetic characteristics of found isolates) have been combined with conservation of ACE-2 receptor within mammal families to examine the host-range potential of SARS-CoV-2 and to analyse any viral reasonable specific mutations that occurred in animal hosts. 1,527 complete genomes of SARS-CoV-2 from animals in 41 countries and available on GISAID were aligned to the SARS CoV-2 reference strain. Our findings suggest that it would seem reasonable concentrating and intensifying surveillance efforts in animal species that are closely related to those shown to be susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, especially focusing on certain endangered animal species. More details in D2.4.1 ‘Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity’ <https://zenodo.org/record/7454516#.Y58cgnbP02w>.

ST2.4.2 – Identification of antigenic site modifications (M49 – M57)

Subtask completed. Antigenic distances have been estimated for 9775 (Wuhan), Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Omicron BA.1 variants using human and animal sera (rabbit). See deliverable 2.4.2 'Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits'.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434388>.

ST2.4.3 In vivo studies virus variants [D2.4.3 Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study due M60, delayed to M62].

Partners 10, 21, and 28 are undertaking *in vivo* experiments with SARS-CoV-2 variants (alpha, beta gamma, delta) in hamsters, ferrets and humanised mice respectively, investigating infection parameters, drug efficacy, modes and routes of transmission contact and aerosol, disease pathogenesis, and virus survival on bio-matrix i.e. fur and skin.

As described in ST2.4.1, SARS-CoV-2 viruses were used to infect ferrets with SARS-CoV-2 viruses as an asymptomatic/mild SARS-CoV-2 challenge infection model. Another study investigated skin-to-skin and bioaerosol transmission with the aim to evaluate the ability of SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant to remain infectious on skin, to assess whether skin can act as a viable source for initiating SARS-CoV-2 infection in ferrets. The key findings showed that SARS-CoV-2 variants can persist on skin and be transferred through skin-to-skin contact initiating infection (manuscripts in preparation). Further studies have been undertaken with Delta and Omicron variants to investigate longevity and re-infection dynamics and the extent of homologous and heterologous re-infection and transmission parameters in ferrets are being assessed. Environmental samples from the *in vivo* studies including ferret fur, air samples, cage fronts and drinking water bottles have been sampled and has contributed to ST1.3.2.

WP3 – SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance

JIP06-WP3-T3.1 - Integration of surveillance activities (M40 – M63)

ST3.1.1 – Design format and procedure for surveillance data (M40 – M45)

Sub-task is completed.

ST3.1.2 – Collection of surveillance data (M40 – M54)

In Y5, a database has been created, with access to data requiring approval by the data holders/contacts for each of the countries, these, along with a summary of the data are uploaded to the OHEJP COVRIN group site as well as available from Zenodo
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006321> as part of deliverable D3.1.2.

ST3.1.3 – Identification of additional sources of surveillance data (M40 – M57)

The primary goal of Task 3.1 is the integration of surveillance data. The harmonized and integrated database developed as part of Task 3.1 activities will serve as a source of parameters for risk models in Task 3.4 and other risk assessments in WP4. Given the primary use of data, in consultation with Task 3.4 and WP4, Deliverable D3.1.3 focused on collecting and summarizing SARS-CoV-2 prevalence data in dogs and cats from published studies, as the most relevant type of studies for the extraction of data and their integration into a common framework.

A systematic review was conducted on the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in household dogs and cats. A manuscript has been submitted and is under review: Guo R., Wolff C., Prada J.M., Mughini-Gras L. (under review). Deliverable D3.1.3, which summarizes the review and the results, has been submitted to the OHEJP COVRIN group site in M57 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430425>). For data sources identified in Subtask 3.1.3, data that were accessed or retrieved were added to and integrated in the database using the same protocol from D3.1.1., and shared with T3.4. In parallel with Deliverable D3.1.3, a scientific article has been

prepared and submitted for publication.

JIP06-WP3-T3.2 - Mapping of surveillance data (M40 – M63)

ST3.2.1 – Evaluation of current surveillance activities (M40 – M48)

The sub-task has been completed.

ST3.2.2 – Identification of key stakeholders (M40-M63)

Progress has been made in the identification of stakeholders, which relates to Deliverable D3.2.2. The database created between T3.1 and T3.2 will be used to identify broad categories of actors and stakeholders that need to be involved. A number of project partners have been engaged to potentially add a specific “case-study” applied to the UK context.

JIP06-WP3-T3.3 - Risk factors for virus transmission (M40 – M63)

This task, risk factors for virus transmission, has been initiated through meetings of task leader and contributors and will be dependent on the outcomes from T3.1, 3.2 and Work package 1.

ST3.3.1 – Analyses of transmission in pets (M40 – M54)

This task has been completed . Finalization of the *epidemiological survey to analyse the transmission of SARSCov-2 in both heavily and normally exposed pets* (i.e. healthcare personal households and "normal" households, respectively) linked to Deliverable D3.3.1 "Report on the design of the epidemiological survey and clinical data.". Deliverable D3.3.1 is available open access page ([pdf \(ijidonline.com\)](https://www.ijidonline.com)).

Sampling pets and diagnosis of infections with SARS-Cov-2 using PCR-ELISA : Incorporating a more specific ELISA test (ID-VET: DOUBLE ANTIGEN MULTI-SPECIES ELISA) produced new results (increasing the proportion of positive results) in dog samples. The epidemiology investigation also included 70 more dog samples from a research group at the University of Alfonso X in Madrid. The new findings and samples will be included in the analysis of SARS-CoV-2 transmission in pets, thereby increasing the sample size and information for the identification of potential risk factors for SARS-CoV-2 transmission at the human-pet interface, which can be used to feed mathematical modelling and risk analysis, and contributing to the completion of subtask 3.3.2. Currently, a manuscript is being finalised that includes the conduct of the epidemiological study to analyse the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in pets, as well as the new data and samples.

ST3.3.2 – Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets (M40 – M60)

A literature search was conducted to collect information on potential risk factors of SARS-CoV-2 transmission. It is difficult to consult and explore global information regarding SARS-CoV2 in pets and other animals. In order to bridge this gap, an easy tool that allows for the exploration of spatial parameters and SARS-CoV-2 presence in animals was developed: SARS-board is an open-source dashboard application that combines data on a variety of parameters based on scientific studies of risk for SARS-Cov-2 in humans (socioeconomic and climate factors) and displays them on interactive maps that may be used that may be use to track the evolution of the epidemic. Currently, the SARS-board tool is being developed, and a pilot app may be accessed [here](#). SARS-board contains 3 tabs, displays, or sections which integrates SARS-CoV-2 outbreak data (WOAH, formerly OIE), temperature data (Climate Data Online) and socioeconomical factors (World Bank Data) and includes options to change the base map in order to explore outbreaks combining with roads, topografics dats etc, as well as a timeline to select outbreaks worldwide in pets and other types of animals in a specific time period since 2020.

A Short Term Mission (STM) was approved in collaboration with Dr. Vitor Borges and Dr. Joao Gomes from INSA, involved in WP2. The applicant, a postdoctoral researcher at the INIA, spent 12 days in November 2022 at INSA (one of Europe's reference laboratories for metagenomics techniques and bioinformatics technologies). The aims of this short-term mission were: 1) learning modern metagenomics techniques and bioinformatics tools and 2) collaboration strengthening between INSA and CISA INIA-CSIC. The results of this collaboration will be particularly valuable to the applicant in regard to COVRIN project. A short video summarizing the experience of the short-term mission was presented at the final COVRIN meeting in Teramo, December 2022.

Literature searches, final results of epidemiological survey and laboratory analysis in pets, the interactive dashboard (SARS-board), and future approaches based on metagenomics analysis, together will contribute to deliverable 3.3.2. due in M61.

JIP06-WP3-T3.4 - Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective (M40 – M63)

ST3.4.1 – Listing of existing models (M40 – M45)

This subtask is completed.

ST3.4.2 – Reviewing transmission parameters (M40 – M54)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.2 “Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species”, systematic reviews (SR) were carried out to collect data and generate summaries for this biological information matrix. Three SR reviews on this topic have been finished: assessing persistence in pets (Decaro et al. 2021); assessing the risk of cat-to-cat transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Gonzales et al. 2021) and hamsters and ferrets <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447098>.

ST3.4.3 – Listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk (M40 – M60) delayed to M61

Integrating on the work from ST3.4.2, and T3.3, progress on the listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk is being completed. We have been collaborating with EFSA, writing an opinion on SARS-COV-2 in animals. In this opinion systematic reviews were done to develop a comprehensive list of susceptible species, based on both experimental and natural infections. In addition, an assessment of the risk some of the most relevant species may play in transmission and maintenance of the virus at the human-animal interface is being performed. The EFSA opinion is expected to be published in the EFSA journal and the contribution of COVRIN will be acknowledged. Deliverable delayed to M61 to align with EFSA publication.

ST3.4.4 – Reviewing of challenge experiments (M40 – M63)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.4 “Report on systematic review of challenge experiments using different host species”, a systematic review was carried out on challenge experiments in non-human primates and is available as a preprint: [Counotte et al. \(2021\)](#)

ST3.4.5 – Description of transmission characteristics in mink (M51)

Work on the analysis of the spatio-temporal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in minks (between farm transmission) has been performed and a manuscript is being finalised, which will link to deliverable D3.4.5 available here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447016>. This study identified differences in the between farm transmission dynamics between four different virus genomic clusters, with one cluster in particular showing higher risk of transmission than the other 3 clusters. Some factors associated with transmission were the frequency of between farm contacts and presence of specific mutations at the level of the spike protein, in the virus cluster identified as the most transmissible

cluster.

WP4 - Coronavirus preparedness

JIP06-WP4-T4.1 - Virus-host interactions (M40 – M63)

ST4.1.1 – *In vivo and in vitro studies of animal coronaviruses (M40 – M57)-delayed to M63*

Research is ongoing within this task: In several partner institutes animal coronaviruses are being passaged *in vitro* and *in vivo* and *ex vivo* in their homologous host or in alternate animal hosts, cells or tissues. *In vitro* studies for this deliverable have been submitted in M57 according to the initial planning. However, *in vivo* studies have been delayed due restrictions on movement of animals following the avian influenza crisis. *In vivo* trials have been completed in in October and December 2022 and planned for January 2023, thus this section of D4.1.1 will be submitted in M63.

ST4.1.2 – *In vitro and ex vivo studies of experimental co-infections (M40 – M63)*

Experimental co-infections are being performed *in vitro* or *ex vivo* in several institutes. This subtask seems to have an overlap with subtask 4.1.1. Therefore, an inventory will be made of ongoing studies, and reporting will be combined with subtask 4.1.1. Genetic make-up of viral progeny will be investigated by deep sequencing.

ST4.1.3 – *Virus isolation from wildlife (hedgehogs) (M40 – M63)*

Work on the isolation of hedgehog coronavirus has been executed. However, coronaviruses were not successfully isolated from hedgehogs. Coronavirus sequences were obtained and will be reported. Studies on the zoonotic potential of the viruses cannot be performed.

JIP06-WP4-T4.2 - Drivers of virus emergence (M40 – M63)

ST4.2.1 – *Analyse coronavirus phylodynamics at global time and geographical scales (M40 – M49, extended from M42)*

Subtask completed: An evaluation of potential sample types and hot spots for SARS-CoV-2 infections has been made, and a report about this has been written (M49): Deliverable D4.2.1 “Relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling” <https://zenodo.org/record/7448858#.Y5zSqnbMldU>. This deliverable was delayed due to a delayed start of the project and staffing issues due to COVID-19.

ST4.2.2 – *Trace relevant virus mutations and recombinations (M40 – M51)- delayed to M63*

An *in vivo* study with TGEV and PEDV is set up in pigs. Studies on relevant mutations and recombination events in coronavirus isolates to gain insights into genetic variation under “natural” conditions (as compared with ST4.1.1 and ST4.1.2) are going to be performed. Virus sequencing protocols are being evaluated and discussed. This deliverable will be delayed to M63 due to problems with the purchase of experimental animals because of the Avian Influenza crisis.

ST4.2.3 – *Evaluate the impact of ecological factors and interventions (M40 – M63)*

Of surveyed SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks the observed genetic changes are being investigated concerning their correlation with ecological factors (species interactions, habitat etc) and human interventions (vaccination, trading of animals), and how such factors may impact coronavirus evolution (evolution rates, composition of recombinants, possible contribution of vaccine viruses). This is done for the mink outbreak in the Netherlands to gain more insight into the role of ecological factors and human interventions. Other SARS-CoV-2 outbreak samples may be included in these studies.

JIP06-WP4-T4.3 - Virus emergence risk modelling (M40 – M63)

ST4.3.1 – *Coronavirus sampling and surveillance in bats (M40 – M60)- delayed to M61*

A total of 503 samples (397 oral swabs and 106 faecal) were collected from bats roosting in Poland between May and September of 2020–2022.

The detection of sarbecoviruses with rtRT-qPCR obtained positive results for 18 samples (3.6%, 95% CI 2.3–5.6) in four roosts of lesser horseshoe bats (*Rhinolophus hipposideros*) in Lower Silesia. A further investigation performed on all 503 bat samples using nested pan-coronavirus primers additionally detected *Alphacoronavirus* in two faecal samples collected from *Myotis* bats (*M. daubentonii*) in two roosts. The overall prevalence of BtCoVs was estimated at 4.0% (95% CI 2.6–6.1), whereas for lesser horseshoe bats it reached 31.0% (95% CI 20.6–43.8). For *Myotis* bats the prevalence was 3.68% (95% CI 0.6–12.3).

ST4.3.2 Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in cats (M40 – M63)

Samplings have been started of cats in domestic environments. A monthly faecal sampling of cats and kittens under breeding farm conditions is being performed to assess the impact of human interventions (link with ST4.2.3). Faecal samples are seldom tested SARS-CoV-2 positive. Also in cats, the virus seems to be mainly transmitted through the respiratory tract. NGS analyses of samples will be performed in 2023.

ST4.3.3 – Coronavirus infections in wildlife (including hedgehogs and bats) (M40 – M63)

Various species of wildlife have been sampled and tested for coronaviruses. This includes bats, foxes, marmots, deer, etc. A frequent sampling of animals hosted in wildlife shelters (incl. hedgehogs) are being performed to assess the impact of modified interactions on the evolution of wildlife coronaviruses (link with ST4.2.3).

ST4.3.4 – Risk assessment and modelling of animal coronavirus evolution (M40 – M63)

Data from WPs 1, 2, 3 and WP4 tasks will be analysed on their potential to be integrated into future risk assessments on the question which animal species/conditions offer the highest potential for future emergencies. This work includes a literature review and an overview on how deliverables of the COVRIN project can contribute to a coronavirus risk assessment.

9.3 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

9.3.1 Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2022 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.1.2	First management report	51	53		https://zenodo.org/record/7445670#.Y5wqOnbMJPY	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.2.1	First annual communication report	51	53		https://zenodo.org/record/7448604#.Y5zB-3bMJPY	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.3	Report Mid-term meeting (presentations)	57	55		https://zenodo.org/record/7433656#.Y53kAnbP02w	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.4.1	(optional ST) Ad hoc reports to REA and EU stakeholders on relevant interim knowledge/data results as relevant for potential risk assessment	n/a				

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		and/or risk management activities					
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.1.1	Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 virus genome testing in companion animals and livestock	60		63	Delayed due in part to COVID-19 and availability of data. On target for completion in M63	
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.3	Report on the bioavailability of virus on fomites, water and the environment	60		63	Delayed due in part to COVID-19 and availability of data. On target for completion in M63	
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.1	Report on the established website protocol repository	44			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5342577	2
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.2	Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange	52			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6458214	2
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.3	Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment.	54			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6784043	2
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.2	Report on assessment of VNA techniques	51	60		Work completed in M51. Upload delayed due to approvals https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434267	2

		and comparison with ELISA reactivity data.					
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.3	Report on complex culture viral characterisation.	57		63	Delayed due to infection data from organoid-derived ALI-cultures and precision cut lung slices from different partners are not yet complete or under evaluation. For finalization and comparative report postponement to M63 is required	
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.2	Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes.	51	51		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259840	2
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.3	Report on virus-host interaction parameters across susceptible species.	60		61	Delayed due to staff recruitment and data availability	
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.1	Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity.	54	60		https://zenodo.org/record/7454516#.Y58cgnbP02w	2
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.2	Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits.	57	60		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434388	4,5, 8 (network)

JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.3	Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study.	60		62	Delayed due to COVID-19	
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.1.2	Database on sampling on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment.	54	54		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006321	3
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.1.3	Report on the investigation and possibilities of integration.	57	57		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430425	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.3.1	Report on epidemiological survey design and clinical data (including anamnesis and lab results).	54	54		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059	3
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.3.2	Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets	60		61	In progress, prototype app available here: https://gis.inia.es/portal/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/5d44a9b0d8fc427e836dd266ef1125a6	3
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.2	Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.	54	54		https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480 (cats) https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14375.1 (non-human primates) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447098 (hamster / ferrets)	3,4

JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.3	List of susceptible hosts and relative risk ranking of susceptibility	60		61	The deliverable here comes with the EFSA opinion which is scheduled to be endorsed on Jan 19 and published thereafter	
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.4	Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species	63	54		Pre-print open access: Counotte et al. (2021)	3,5
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.5	Report describing the transmission characteristics of the mink outbreaks for the countries where data was available.	51	51		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447016	3,5
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.1	Reports of in vivo and in vitro experimentations	57		63	This deliverable will be delayed to the end of the project due to problems with the purchase of experimental animals because of the Avian Influenza crisis'	
JIP06-COVRIN	D.4.2.2	Report on harmonized methods for coronavirus detection and metagenomic sequencing and detected coronavirus genomes.	51		63	This deliverable will be delayed to the end of the project due to problems with the purchase of experimental animals because of the Avian Influenza crisis.	

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JIP06-COVRIN	D.4.3.1	Coronavirus sampling and surveillance in bats	60		61	Work is complete but this deliverable is delayed due to staff shortages	
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.2	Full-length genomes of viruses from a, b and c	63				
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.2.3	Report of analyses of detected variations in Coronavirus sequences related to ecological factors and human interventions.	63				
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.2	Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in cats	63				
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.3	Coronavirus infections in wildlife (including hedgehogs and bats)	63				
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.4.	Report on established models and risk assessments for viral emergence.	63				

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** Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);*

9.3.2 Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.1	In vitro and in vivo experiments performed	54	Yes		
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.2	M4.2 Samples collected under farming and natural conditions	57	Yes		
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.3	Coronavirus evolution under experimental and natural conditions analyzed	63			On target
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.4	impact on the capacity to cross the species barrier evaluated and risk modeled	63			On target

9.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Hagag IT, Weber S, Sadeghi B, Groschup MH, Keller M. Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2021.109243	Yes		~3132 Euro (USD 3,220)
Lean FZX, Núñez A, Spiro S, Pristnall SL, Vreman S, Bailey D, James J, Wrigglesworth E, Suarez-Bonnet A, Conceicao C, Thkur N, Byrne AMP, Ackroyd S, Delahay RJ, van der Poel WHM, Brown IH, Fooks AR, Brookes SM. Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterization DOI: https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232 Zenodo Reference: https://zenodo.org/record/5795457#.YcG5QGjP3IU	Yes		4100 Euro
Newman, J., Thakur, N., Peacock, T.P., Bialy, D., Elreafey, A.M., Bogaardt, C., Horton, D.L., Ho, S., Kankeyan, T., Carr, C., Hoschler, K., Barclay, W.S., Amirthalingam, G., Brown, K., Charleston, B., Bailey, D., 2021. Neutralising antibody activity against SARS-CoV-2 variants, including Omicron, in an elderly cohort vaccinated with BNT162b2. medRxiv. https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.23.21268293	Yes		9500 Euro
Gonzales JL, de Jong MCM, Gerhards NM, Van der Poel WHM. The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R0 in Cats. Viruses. 2021; 13(12):2480. https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480	Yes		1578 Euro
Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B.,	Yes		4100 Euro

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<p>Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. <i>Transboundary and emerging diseases</i>, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication. https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308</p>			
<p>Counotte, Michel J., Mariana A. de Souza Santos, Koert L. Stittelaar, Wim H. van der Poel, and Jose L. Gonzales. 2021. "Assessment of the Efficacy of SARS-cov-2 Vaccines in Non-human Primate Studies - a Systematic Review." OSF Preprints. April 23. doi:10.31219/osf.io/u3fwj.</p>	Yes	Yes- preprint freely available	
<p>Romito, G., Bertaglia, T., Bertaglia, L., Decaro, N., Uva, A., Rugna, G., Moreno, A., Vincifori, G., Dondi, F., Diana, A., Cipone, M. Myocardial Injury Complicated by Systolic Dysfunction in a COVID-19-Positive Dog. <i>Animals (Basel)</i>. 2021 Dec 8;11(12):3506. doi: 10.3390/ani11123506 Zenodo Reference: https://zenodo.org/record/5849858#.YfGJAurMJdg</p>	yes		~1822 Euro (1800 CHF)
<p>Moreno, A., Lelli, D., Trogu, T., Lavazza, A., Barbieri, I., Boniotti, M., Pezzoni, G., Salogni, C., Giovannini, S., Alborali, G., Bellini, S., Boldini, M., Farioli, M., Ruocco, L., Bessi, O., Maroni Ponti, A., Di Bartolo, I., De Sabato, L., Vaccari, G., Belli, G., Margutti, A., Giorgi, M. SARS-CoV-2 in a Mink Farm in Italy: Case Description, Molecular and Serological Diagnosis by Comparing Different Tests. <i>Viruses</i>. 2022 Aug 8;14(8):1738. doi: 10.3390/v14081738.</p>	Yes		2466 Euro
<p>A. Mendez, M.A. Jiménez-Clavero, C. Calvo, E. Pérez-Ramírez, J. Fernández-Pinero, F. Llorente, T. Sainz, P. Aguilera-Sepúlveda, S. Alcolea, L. Escolano, C. Cano, I. Novoa, A. De la Torre I. Iglesias. (2022) SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain, <i>International Journal of Infectious</i></p>	Yes		USD 2200 (~2075 Euro)

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research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Diseases, Volume 116: S25. ISSN 1201-9712 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059			
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9.5 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

COVRIN cooperates with a lot of nationally funded projects in partner countries, and also with international organisations like WHO, FAO, ECDC and EFSA. Links have been established with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project. COVRIN research outputs are reported nationally and internationally. All significant results have been reported to the national Ministries and also to ECDC and EFSA as appropriate. Preliminary findings have been presented at meetings and conferences on emerging diseases (i.e. IMED 2021) The aim is to make all COVRIN results available for the entire scientific community, primarily through peer reviewed publications, and also to the general public. COVRIN has also linked closely with the UK-Internation Coronavirus Network.

9.6 List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	no

Additional information

Many of the partners are also undertaking mandatory SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics and characterization as part of their normal duties, which has the potential to impact on delivery. Several deliverables have been delayed from M60 to M63 as a consequence but risk has now reduced and completion is expected in M63 as planned.

